

**Marlene Gomes
Brás**

**Eficiência de custo energético de sistemas de
abastecimento de água através de metodologias
de otimização**

Energy-cost efficiency of water supply systems through optimization methodologies

Marlene Gomes
Brás

Eficiência de custo energético de sistemas de abastecimento de água através de metodologias de otimização

Energy-cost efficiency of water supply systems through optimization methodologies

Tese apresentada à Universidade de Aveiro para cumprimento dos requisitos necessários à obtenção do grau de Doutor em Engenharia e Gestão Industrial, realizada sob a orientação científica da Doutora Ana Maria Pinto de Moura, Professora Auxiliar do Departamento de Economia, Gestão, Engenharia Industrial e Turismo da Universidade de Aveiro e do Doutor António Gil d'Orey de Andrade-Campos, Professor Catedrático do Departamento de Engenharia Mecânica da Universidade de Aveiro.

Marlene Brás acknowledges the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) for the financial support from the PhD grant 2022.12310.BD. Additionally, it was supported by the Regional Operational Program of the Center Region (CENTRO2020) within project I-RETIS-WATER (CENTRO-01-0247-FEDER-069857), through the COMPETE 2020 Programs, by the Regional Operational Program of the Center Region (CENTRO2030) within project I-ReTiS-LeaksD&Op n^o 17304 (CENTRO2030-FEDER-01177300), by the Research Unit on Governance, Competitiveness and Public Policies (UIDB/04058/2020) + (UIDP/04058/2020), and by the project/support UID/00481 Centre for Mechanical Technology and Automation, all funded by Portuguese funds through FCT. Moreover, it was supported by the Recovery and Resilience Plan (PRR), within project I-ReTiS-Leaks (2024.07270.IACD, <https://doi.org/10.54499/2024.07270.IACDC>). The author also acknowledges the important contribution of Scubic (Gotas Digitais, Lda) and Águas do Centro Litoral (AdCL) in the development of this work.

O júri / The jury

Presidente / President

Prof. Doutor Vítor António Ferreira da Costa
Professor Catedrático da Universidade de Aveiro

Vogais / Committee

Prof. Doutora Maria Antónia da Silva Lopes e Carravilla
Professora Catedrática da Universidade do Porto

Prof. Doutor Carlos Alberto Henggeler de Carvalho Antunes
Professor Catedrático da Universidade de Coimbra

Prof. Doutora Elsa Marília da Costa Silva
Professora Auxiliar da Universidade do Minho

Prof. Doutora Inês Osório de Castro Meireles
Professora Auxiliar da Universidade do Aveiro

Prof. Doutora Ana Maria Pinto de Moura
Professora Auxiliar da Universidade de Aveiro (orientador principal)

Agradecimentos / Acknowledgements

À Professora Ana, que já me acompanha desde o mestrado, agradeço os ensinamentos transmitidos, o apoio contínuo, e a paciência em todas as etapas deste percurso. Ao Professor Gil, agradeço a partilha de conhecimento e visão, bem como a oportunidade de integrar o grupo ReachOptimum-TEMA, uma experiência que contribuiu para o meu crescimento académico e pessoal. Esta jornada não teria sido a mesma sem cada um deles. O meu muito obrigada.

À Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia, pelo apoio financeiro concedido através da bolsa de doutoramento 2022.12310.BD.

À minha família, em especial aos meus pais, ao meu irmão Tiago e à minha cunhada Ana, pelo amor, pelo apoio constante e pela confiança que sempre me transmitiram.

Ao Raul, o companheiro de todos os dias, cuja alegria trouxe leveza e equilíbrio a este percurso.

Às Chineleiras, por ouvirem os meus longos *Wednesday Waffles* e por nunca faltarem com uma mensagem que animasse o resto da minha semana.

Aos meus colegas, e amigos, da Universidade de Aveiro, em especial à Ana, à Sara e ao Zé, pelo apoio nos momentos mais desafiantes e por partilharem comigo a vossa jornada.

Com todo o carinho que possa existir, obrigada a todos.

Por fim, agradeço a mim, pela coragem de reescrever os meus próprios planos, quando o mais fácil seria continuar no caminho já traçado.

Palavras-chave

Programação Não Linear, Sistemas de Abastecimento de Água, Problema de Agendamento de Bombagem, Otimização, Eficiência de Custo, Sistemas de Apoio à Decisão

Resumo

Os Sistemas de Abastecimento de Água (SAA) são infraestruturas críticas que garantem o acesso a água potável, apoiam o desenvolvimento económico e salvaguardam a saúde pública. No entanto, a prestação destes serviços requer um elevado consumo energético, sendo que as estações elevatórias representam, por si só, entre 70 e 80% do consumo energético total do sistema. O aumento do consumo de água associado ao crescimento populacional, a flutuação dos tarifários energéticos e a crescente pressão por práticas sustentáveis tornaram a operação eficiente e económica dos SAA um desafio estratégico para as entidades gestoras. Apesar de décadas de investigação sobre metodologias de otimização aplicadas ao Problema de Agendamento de Operação de Bombagem, a sua implementação prática continua limitada, condicionada por questões de escalabilidade, interpretabilidade e integração nos fluxos operacionais existentes.

Esta tese aborda estes desafios através do desenvolvimento de uma ferramenta de otimização e apoio à decisão para o agendamento da operação das estações elevatórias dos SAA. A investigação inicia-se com uma análise sistemática e uma comparação quantitativa das formulações matemáticas existentes, evidenciando os seus compromissos de modelação e limitações. Desta análise destaca-se o modelo de otimização baseado em *duty-cycles*, que fornece uma representação contínua das operações de bombagem, aumentando a flexibilidade operacional mantendo, simultaneamente, a escalabilidade para configurações de rede mais complexas.

Com base nesta formulação, foi desenvolvida uma metaheurística híbrida designada *Smart Dynamic Local Search* (Smart-DLS). O algoritmo combina um método de pesquisa local determinístico com perturbações baseadas em regras predefinidas e estratégias de *multi-start*, resultando em soluções de elevada qualidade em diversos cenários operacionais. O Smart-DLS é integrado, numa fase subsequente, num Sistema de Apoio à Decisão (SAD) modular que incorpora o operador no ciclo de decisão e possibilita a otimização através da geração e avaliação de múltiplas alternativas de agendamento, com base em *key performance indicators* (KPI) definidos por cada entidade gestora.

O SAD proposto é validado em dois casos de estudo da literatura, sendo eles a rede de VanZyl e a rede modificada de AnyTown. Adicionalmente, foi testado em dois sistemas reais de abastecimento de água em Portugal: o SAA de Ronqueira, operado com bombas de velocidade fixa, e o Sistema de Abastecimento de Água de Referência Português (SAARP), equipado com bombas de velocidade variável.

Para a rede de Ronqueira, os resultados demonstraram reduções significativas nos custos energéticos de aproximadamente 20%, preservando a fiabilidade operacional e a conformidade dos níveis dos reservatórios de água. No SAARP, o DSS exibiu escalabilidade e robustez em condições hidráulicas e operacionais mais complexas, produzindo soluções energeticamente eficientes que resultaram numa redução total de custos de 22%.

Para garantir robustez face à incerteza no consumo de água, é ainda introduzido um mecanismo de controlo adaptativo que permite o ajuste em tempo real da operação das bombas, assegurando um desempenho operacional fiável quando as condições reais divergem das previsões. Esta funcionalidade aumenta a confiança dos operadores na implementação de metodologias baseadas em otimização.

Esta tese contribui significativamente para a área de otimização aplicada aos SAA através do desenvolvimento de uma revisão sistemática e comparação quantitativa das formulações existentes, validando o modelo de *duty-cycles* e desenvolvendo o algoritmo híbrido Smart-DLS. Estes avanços são incorporados num SAD modular que é validado em condições operacionais reais. O SAD demonstra o impacto que terá nas entidades gestoras ao melhorar a eficiência de custos, a transparência e a adaptabilidade na gestão dos SAA, enquanto promove a aproximação entre a teoria da otimização e a prática operacional.

Keywords

Nonlinear Programming, Water Supply Systems, Pump Scheduling Problem, Optimization, Cost-Efficiency, Decision Support Systems

Abstract

Water Supply Systems (WSS) are critical infrastructures that ensure access to safe drinking water, support economic development, and safeguard public health. However, delivering these services requires substantial energy resources, with pumping operations typically accounting for 70-80% of total system energy use. As energy prices rise and sustainability goals become increasingly demanding, water utilities face the challenge of operating these systems in a cost-efficient, reliable, and environmentally responsible manner. Despite decades of research on optimization-based pump scheduling and control, the practical implementation of such methodologies remains limited, constrained by problems of scalability, interpretability, and integration within existing operational workflows.

This thesis addresses these challenges through the development of an optimization and decision-support framework for pump scheduling in WSS. The work begins with a systematic analysis and quantitative comparison of the existing mathematical formulations, highlighting their modelling trade-offs and limitations. From this analysis, the duty-cycle optimization model is highlighted, providing a continuous-time representation of pump operations that enhances operational flexibility while maintaining scalability to complex network configurations.

Building upon this formulation, a novel hybrid metaheuristic designated Smart Dynamic Local Search (Smart-DLS) is developed. The algorithm combines deterministic local search with rule-based perturbation and multi-start strategies, achieving high-quality solutions across diverse operational scenarios. The Smart-DLS is subsequently integrated into a modular Decision Support System (DSS) that enables operator-in-the-loop optimization through the generation and evaluation of multiple scheduling alternatives according to the water utility specific key performance indicators (KPI).

The proposed DSS has been successfully validated using two literature benchmarks, the Van Zyl network and the AnyTown modified network. Additionally, it was tested in two real Portuguese water supply systems: the Ronqueira WSS, which operates with fixed-speed pumps, and the Portuguese Reference WSS (PRWSS), which uses variable-speed pumps. For the Ronqueira network, the results demonstrated consistent energy-cost reductions of approximately 20% while preserving operational reliability and water tank levels compliance. In the PRWSS, the DSS exhibited both scalability and robustness under more complex hydraulic and operational conditions, consistently producing feasible and energy-efficient pumping schedules that resulted in a cost reduction of 22%.

To ensure robustness under demand uncertainty, an adaptive control mechanism is also introduced, allowing real-time adjustment of pump operation to maintain a feasible and reliable system performance. This feature further increases operator confidence in the adoption of optimization-based methodologies.

This thesis contributes significantly to the field of pump scheduling optimization by providing a systematic review and quantitative comparison of existing formulations, validating the duty-cycle model and developing the hybrid Smart-DLS algorithm. These advancements are incorporated into a modular DSS that has been tested and validated in real operational conditions. The DSS demonstrates its impact on water utilities by improving the cost-efficiency, transparency, and adaptability of WSS management, while also reducing the gap between optimization research and practical operational applications.

Acknowledgements of use of AI tools

I acknowledge the use of ChatGPT 4.0 (OpenAI, <https://chat.openai.com>) to summarize the initial notes and rephrase some sentences, the use of Grammarly (<https://www.grammarly.com>) to ensure grammatical correctness of the document.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Background and motivation	1
1.2	Objectives and impact	3
1.3	Scientific contributions and dissemination of results	4
1.4	Thesis structure	5
2	An applied state-of-the-art on pump scheduling optimization problems	9
2.1	Optimization in water supply systems	10
2.2	Pump scheduling problem	11
2.2.1	PSP as an explicit control problem	14
2.2.2	PSP as an implicit control problem	20
2.2.3	Other proposed mathematical formulations	25
2.3	Quantitative comparison of different approaches	26
2.3.1	Methodology	26
2.3.2	Case study: single pump-tank network	28
2.3.3	Case study: Van Zyl network	33
2.4	Final remarks	41
3	Proposal of a novel optimization approach	43
3.1	Problem of multiple optimal and near-optimal solutions	44
3.1.1	Sensitivity analysis	44
3.1.2	Stability analysis	51
3.2	Model scalability analysis	53
3.2.1	KPIs for a global optimum: energy consumption cost vs. maintenance cost	54
3.3	Proposed optimization framework	55
3.3.1	Smart Dynamic Local Search (Smart-DLS)	56
3.3.2	Demonstration of the Smart-DLS: single pump-tank network	60
3.4	Results and validation	62
3.4.1	Case study: Van Zyl network	62
3.4.2	Case study: AnyTown modified network	67
3.4.3	Real WSS: Ronqueira network	71
3.5	Final remarks	75

4	Smart-DLS as the model management of a decision support system	77
4.1	Decision support systems for pump scheduling optimization	78
4.2	Decision support system based on the Smart Dynamic Local Search	81
4.2.1	Decision support system architecture based on Smart-DLS	81
4.3	Results and validation	83
4.3.1	Real WSS: Ronqueira network	84
4.3.2	Real WSS: Portuguese reference water supply system	88
4.4	Real-time adaptive control	99
4.4.1	Slope-based Control Method	99
4.4.2	Real WSS: Ronqueira network	100
4.4.3	Real WSS: Portuguese reference water supply system	103
4.5	Final remarks	110
5	Conclusions and future perspectives	111
5.1	Closing remarks	111
5.1.1	Perspectives for future work	113
	References	114
A	Appendices	127
A.1	Appendix of Chapter 2	127
A.1.1	Mathematical formulations proposed for the pump scheduling optimization problem	127
A.2	Appendix of Chapter 3	132
A.2.1	Smart-DLS results for each network	132
A.2.2	Ronqueira network: water consumption demands from February 20th of 2024	133
A.3	Appendix of Chapter 4	134
A.3.1	Ronqueira network: real and forecasted water demands from September 25 to 29, 2024	134
A.3.2	PRWSS: real and forecasted water demands from May 7 to 11, 2025	135
A.3.3	Systematic literature review: article analysis	136

List of Figures

1.1	Schematic representation of a typical water supply system, highlighting the division between the bulk supply and distribution segments, as well as the focus area of this thesis.	2
1.2	Schematic representation of the studied problem, methodology implemented to solve it, and the impact and outcomes of the work developed throughout this thesis.	7
1.3	Overview of this thesis structure, highlighting the objectives, applications, and scientific publications resulting from each chapter.	8
2.1	Curves of a variable-speed pump for different speeds: (a) characteristic curves and (b) power consumption curves.	11
2.2	Information flow between the optimization model and the hydraulic simulator. The converter translates the decision variables \mathbf{X} into pump status \mathbf{s} and pump frequency \mathbf{f} , which are used by the simulator to solve $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{F}$. The simulator returns the hydraulic information $(\mathbf{L}, \mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{H})$, which is fed back into the optimization process.	13
2.3	Classification of the mathematical formulations of the pump scheduling problem considering the definition of the decision variables.	13
2.4	Example of the differences between explicit approaches: (a) discrete and (b) continuous TPR, and (c) discrete and (d) continuous TPU. In the TPR explicit formulation, the decision variables are the time each pump operates during a specific predefined time interval, while in the TPU formulation pumps are given the flexibility to operate at any point within the entire time horizon. The difference between discrete and continuous formulations is related to the existence or not of a time resolution Δt^{res} over which the value of the variables must be defined.	14
2.5	Representation of \mathbf{X}^{bin} , \mathbf{M}^{bin} , $s_1^{\text{bin}}(t)$, and $L_1(\mathbf{X}^{\text{bin}})$ for the binary formulation applied to a WSS with one pump ($P=1$) and one water tank ($WT=1$).	16
2.6	Representation of \mathbf{X}^{rc} , \mathbf{M}^{rc} , $s_1^{\text{rc}}(t)$, and $L_1(\mathbf{X}^{\text{rc}}, \mathbf{M}^{\text{rc}})$ for the real-continuous formulation applied to a WSS with one pump ($P=1$) and one water tank ($WT=1$).	18
2.7	Representation of $s_1^{\text{dc}}(t)$ and $L_1(\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}}, \mathbf{M}^{\text{dc}})$ for the duty-cycles formulation applied to a WSS with one pump ($P=1$) and one water tank ($WT=1$).	19
2.8	Summary of the main mathematical formulations proposed for the pump scheduling optimization problem.	24

2.9	Variable Trigger Levels and Reduced Fixed Levels in Additional Time Slots methodologies for setting on/off trigger levels for one pump. The main difference between these models lies in the strategy employed to define the minimum water level during off-peak periods and the maximum water level during peak periods. This strategy aims to ensure the water level is positioned close to the maximum allowed level at the beginning of the peak period.	26
2.10	Model predictive control framework, where (a) represents the simulation module, (b) the prediction module, and (c) the optimization module. In this quantitative comparison, a framework based on the optimization and predictive modules was implemented.	27
2.11	Schematic of the single pump-tank network, a benchmark based on a real Portuguese water supply subsystem.	28
2.12	Characteristics curves of the pump in the single pump-tank network and water demands of each consumption point.	29
2.13	Results of the single pump-tank network optimization for (a) B-GA, (b) RC-SLSQP, and (c) DC-SLSQP approaches.	30
2.14	Results of the (a) V-LINPROG and (b) FTL-SLSQP optimization approaches applied to the single pump-tank network.	33
2.15	Van Zyl Test Network. This water supply system was intentionally designed to accommodate a wide array of viable operational strategies. . . .	34
2.16	Characteristics curves of the pumps in the Van Zyl test network. Both the hydraulic and efficiency curves are defined piecewise.	34
2.17	Demand daily pattern of Van Zyl network. The demands change every hour during the total time horizon of 24 h.	35
2.18	Results from the original paper methodology for the Van Zyl test network: (a) pump scheduling solution and water tank levels, (b) pump flows from the pump scheduling solution, and (c) pump scheduling solution and water tank levels with no water limit defined on the EPANET simulation file. As the Van Zyl case study defines the optimization process as starting at 07:00, the 00:00 time simulation in the graph corresponds to 07:00.	36
2.19	Pumps operation of the initial solution. All optimization models started with the same operation as the initial solution. Since the Van Zyl case study defines the optimization process as starting at 07:00, the 00:00 time simulation in the chart corresponds to 07:00.	38
2.20	Results of the Van Zyl network optimization using (a) B-GA, (b) RC-SLSQP, and (c) DC-SLSQP approaches. Considering that the Van Zyl case study defines the optimization process as starting at 07:00, the 00:00 time simulation in the chart corresponds to 07:00.	39
3.1	Cost sensitivity to the decision variables related to the duty-cycle starting time st_4^{dc} (dC/dst_4^{dc}). For a WSS with one pump and one water tank with water inlet from below, and considering the randomly chosen pump operation, $\mathbf{X}^{dc} = [0, 2, 3, st_4^{dc}, 17, 1, 1, 1, 1, 2]$, the cost sensitivity was calculated for different values of the fourth duty-cycle starting time ($st_4^{dc} \in [4, 15.9]$ h). It should be highlighted that $\Delta t_4^{dc} = 1h$	45

3.2	Pump curve and hydraulic power relation to the variation in the pump operating point. For water tanks fed from below, as the water level in the tank varies, the pump operating point shifts along its characteristic curve. This movement implies that a lower head, directly associated with the tank level, reduces power consumption. Additionally, given the quadratic nature of the curve relating the head to hydraulic power, identical alterations in the pump head at distinct operating points lead to different adjustments in the hydraulic power and, as a consequence, in the energy consumption cost.	46
3.3	Cost surface for the possible values of the 3 rd and 4 th duty-cycles starting time, considering a randomly chosen pump operation $\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}} = [0, 2, st_3^{\text{dc}}, st_4^{\text{dc}}, 17, 1, 1, 1, 1, 2]$	47
3.4	Cost sensitivity to the decision variables related to the duty-cycle duration, Δt_4^{dc} . Considering the randomly chosen pump operation $\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}} = [0, 2, 3, 4, 17, 1, 1, 1, \Delta t_4^{\text{dc}}, 2]$, for a WSS with one pump and one water tank with water inlet from below, the cost sensitivity was calculated for different values of the fourth duty-cycle duration ($\Delta t_4^{\text{dc}} \in [0.25, 12.75]$ h). For this case, $st_4^{\text{dc}} = 4$ h.	48
3.5	Cost surface for the possible values of the starting time st_4^{dc} and time duration Δt_4^{dc} of the fourth duty-cycle, considering the randomly chosen pump operation $\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}} = [0, 2, 3, st_4^{\text{dc}}, 17, 1, 1, 1, \Delta t_4^{\text{dc}}, 2]$	48
3.6	Water tank level and corresponding sensitivity of the fourth duty-cycle starting time st_4^{dc} , considering the possible optimal pump operation for 5 duty-cycles ($D = 5$) $\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}} = [0.95, 1.70, 10.84, 14.80, 17.80, 0.75, 5.24, 0, 1.05, 3.27]$	50
3.7	Water tank level and corresponding sensitivity of the fourth duty-cycle duration Δt_4^{dc} , considering a possible optimal pump operation for 5 duty-cycles ($D = 5$): $\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}} = [0.95, 1.70, 10.84, 14.80, 17.80, 0.75, 5.24, 0, 1.05, 3.27]$	50
3.8	Optimization results applying different approaches to define the initial solution: (a) uniformly distributed initial solution with $D = 5$, (b) one duty-cycles at each tariff transition by setting $D = 5$, (c) one duty-cycle centered in each energy tariff by defining $D = 6$, and (d) initial solution with 6 duty-cycles ($D = 6$), where the first two duty-cycles are in the same position as those of the initial set of Approach 3, and the other four are distributed in the last energy tariff of the total time horizon.	52
3.9	Optimization results with the initial solution strategically defined for each D value ($D \in \{2, 10\}$), focusing on prioritizing duty-cycles towards the day's: (a) pump status and (b) respective costs.	54
3.10	Multi-starting approach of Smart-DLS. By exploring the solution space from multiple entry points, this strategy reduces the risk of getting stuck in local minima and increases the chances of finding a global optimum. . .	59
3.11	Example of the shaking process using the single pump-tank network. A maximum of 3 iterations was defined for the stopping criteria of the Smart-DLS.	61

3.12	Solutions obtained in different shaking processes within the same multi-start for the Van Zyl network. Although the initial solutions started with a different number of duty-cycles, both iterations converged to very similar solutions in terms of pumping operations but with completely different values of the decision variables: (a) iteration 1 and (b) iteration 2 of the Smart-DLS second start.	63
3.13	Smart-DLS results for the Van Zyl network considering as priority KPI: (a) total cost and (b) number of pump starts. To analyze the chart, consider that the Van Zyl case study defines the starting time of the optimization process at 07:00; therefore, the 00:00 time simulation in the chart corresponds to 07:00.	65
3.14	Multi-objective analysis of the Van Zyl network optimization results considering different weights for the number of pump starts.	67
3.15	AnyTown modified network, a modified version of the original network, designed to increase the complexity of the optimization process.	67
3.16	Smart-DLS results for the AnyTown modified network considering as priority KPI: (a) total cost and (b) number of pump starts.	69
3.17	Multi-objective analysis of the AnyTown modified network optimization results considering different weights for the number of pump starts.	71
3.18	Ronqueira network, a real Portuguese network.	71
3.19	Smart-DLS results for the Ronqueira network considering as priority the total cost (a and b), and the number of pump starts (c and d). Pump operation and water tank levels of the left and right sides of the network.	74
3.20	Solution proposed by Scubic for the day in analysis regarding the (a) left and (b) right sides of the Ronqueira network.	75
3.21	Multi-objective analysis of the Ronqueira network optimization results considering different weights for the number of pump starts.	75
4.1	Methodology applied for the article selection of the systematic literature review on decision support systems.	79
4.2	Distribution of reviewed articles by classification, highlighting the optimization model type (mono <i>vs</i> multi-objective) and type of application (real-world <i>vs</i> benchmark). There are no articles classified as C-DSS, as reflected by the absence of data for that category.	80
4.3	Overview of the Smart-DLS algorithm, a hybrid optimization method combining deterministic local search with intelligent shaking operations and a multi-start strategy. It explores multiple initial solutions to avoid local minima, dynamically adjusts the number and timing of duty-cycles, and identifies cost-efficient schedules for WSS.	81
4.4	Architecture of the proposed DSS for pump scheduling. The system integrates SCADA data, water demands and energy tariffs forecasts, user-defined inputs, and EPANET simulations. The Smart-DLS-based Model Management module generates and evaluates pump schedules using the user-defined KPIs, supported by historical data stored in the Knowledge Management module. The User Interface allows configuration and result exploration, while final decisions are made by the decision maker.	82
4.5	Methodology conducted to test the Smart-DLS-based DSS.	83

4.6	Energy tariffs of the Ronqueira network from september 25 (wednesday) to 29 (sunday), 2024.	84
4.7	Smart-DLS results for the Ronqueira network considering the total cost KPI (a and b) and number of pump starts (c and d).	87
4.8	Schematic of the PRWSS with tanks and pumps main characteristics.	89
4.9	Energy tariffs of the PRWSS network from may 7 (wednesday) to 11 (sunday), 2025.	89
4.10	Water tank levels of the Smart-DLS results for the PRWSS considering the KPI: (a) total cost, (b) number of pump starts, and (c) frequency variation.	95
4.11	Pumps operation in the Smart-DLS results for the PRWSS considering the KPI: (a) total cost, (b) number of pump starts, and (c) frequency variation.	98
4.12	Example of superior ($t^{\text{a-sup}}$) and inferior ($t^{\text{a-inf}}$) duty-cycle time anticipation with slope-based method.	100
4.13	Results of the adaptive control method for the Ronqueira network considering the Smart-DLS solutions for the KPI:(a and b) total cost and (c and d) number of pump starts.	103
4.14	Water tank levels of the Smart-DLS results for the PRWSS with the adaptive control method considering the KPI: (a) total cost, (b) number of pump starts, and (c) frequency variation.	106
4.15	Pumps operation in the Smart-DLS results for the PRWSS with the adaptive control method considering the KPI: (a) total cost, (b) number of pump starts, and (c) frequency variation.	109
A.1	Water demands of each consumption point on February 20th of 2024: (a) São Pedro Dias and Casais, (b) Outeiro Castro and Entroncamento, (c) Travanca, (d) Albarqueira, (e) Espinheira, and (f) Avelreira.	133
A.2	Real and forecasted water demands of each consumption point from September 25 to 29, 2024: (a) São Pedro Dias and Casais, (b) Outeiro Castro and Entroncamento, (c) Travanca, (d) Albarqueira, (e) Espinheira, and (f) Avelreira.	135
A.3	Real and forecasted water demands of each location from May 7 to 11, 2025.	136

Intentionally blank page.

List of Tables

2.1	Energy tariffs of the single pump-tank network.	29
2.2	Comparison of the single pump-tank network optimization results.	30
2.3	Comparison of optimization results for the single pump-tank network obtained with the DC-SLSQP approach and with implicit models (V-LINPROG and FTL-SLSQP) reported in the literature	32
2.4	Results of each optimization approach (B-GA, RC-SLSQP and DC-SLSQP) for the Van Zyl network.	37
2.5	Comparison of Van Zyl test network optimization results.	40
3.1	Results of each optimization approach for the single pump-tank network.	53
3.2	Results of the Smart-DLS applied to the single pump-tank network. $\mathbf{X}^{\text{ini}} = [0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2]$ was used as initial solution, which corresponds to an initial cost of 136.35€, and a maximum of 3 iterations for the stopping criteria.	62
3.3	Results of each Smart-DLS multi-start for the Van Zyl network.	64
3.4	Comparison of Van Zyl network optimization results.	66
3.5	Energy tariffs of the AnyTown modified network.	68
3.6	Results of each Smart-DLS multi-start for the AnyTown modified network.	68
3.7	Comparison of AnyTown modified network optimization results.	70
3.8	Energy tariffs of the Ronqueira network on February 20th of 2024.	72
3.9	Results of each Smart-DLS multi-start for the Ronqueira network.	72
3.10	Comparison of the Smart-DLS results with those of the Scubic company for the optimization of the Ronqueira network.	74
4.1	Classification framework used in the literature review.	79
4.2	Results of the Smart-DLS for each day using the forecasted water demands alongside with the real Ronqueira WSS operation.	85
4.3	Results of the Smart-DLS for each day alongside the Ronqueira network real operation.	88
4.4	Results of the Smart-DLS for each day using the forecasted water demands alongside with the PRWSS real operation.	92
4.5	Results of the Smart-DLS for 5 days of operation alongside the PRWSS operation.	93
4.6	Results of the adaptive control method for the Ronqueira network.	101
4.7	Results of the adaptive control method for the PRWSS.	104

A.1	Model's mathematical formulations proposed for the pump scheduling optimization problem.	128
A.2	Smart-DLS results for the Van Zyl network.	132
A.3	Smart-DLS results for the Anytown modified network.	132
A.4	Smart-DLS results for the Ronqueira network.	132
A.5	Systematic literature review: article analysis.	137

Acronyms

ACO Ant Colony Optimization.

AdCL Águas do Centro Litoral.

AL Affinity laws.

AOC Automated optimization controller.

C-DSS Classical decision support system.

CP Consumption point.

CPU Central Processing Unit.

DC Duty-cycle.

DNN Deep neural network.

DSO Decision-support-oriented optimization framework.

DSS Decision support system.

FSP Fixed-speed pump.

FTL Fixed trigger levels.

FV Frequency variation.

FWD Forecasted water demands.

GA Genetic algorithm.

HP Hydropressor.

I-SQP Improved Sequential Quadratic Programming.

KPI Key performance indicator.

MILP Mixed integer linear programming.

MINLP Mixed integer nonlinear programming.

ML Machine learning.

MPC Model predictive control.

OM Optimization model.

PRWSS Portuguese reference water supply system.

PS Pumping station.

PSP Pump scheduling problem.

RC Real-continuous.

RFLATS Reduced fixed levels in additional time slots.

RFTL Reduced fixed trigger levels.

RWD Real water demands.

SCADA Supervisory control and data acquisition.

SCM Slope-based control method.

SDGs Sustainable Development Goals.

SLSQP Sequential least squares programming.

Smart-DLS Smart dynamic local search.

TOU Time-of-use.

TPR Time-position restricted.

TPU Time-position unrestricted.

VFD Variable-frequency driver.

VSP Variable-speed pump.

VTL Variable trigger levels.

WSS Water supply system.

WTP Water treatment plant.

Nomenclature

Constants

g	Gravitational acceleration
ρ	Water density

Index

d	Index of duty-cycles with $d = 1, \dots, D$
D	Number of duty-cycles
i	Index of nodes with $i = 1, \dots, N^{\text{nodes}}$
j	Index of pipes with $j = 1, \dots, N^{\text{pipes}}$
N^{nodes}	Number of nodes
N^{pipes}	Number of pipes
N^{steps}	Number of hydraulic simulation time steps
n_s	Index of hydraulic simulation time steps with $n_s = 1, \dots, N^{\text{steps}}$
n	Index of optimization time horizons with $n = 1, \dots, N$
N	Number of optimization time horizons within T
p	Index of pumps with $p = 1, \dots, P$
P	Number of pumps
T	Total time horizon
wt	Index of water tanks with $wt = 1, \dots, WT$
WT	Number of water tanks

Matrices & Vectors

\mathbf{A}	Matrix containing the information of the hydraulic network characteristics
\mathbf{F}	Vector of water demands
\mathbf{L}_{wt}	Vector of water levels of the tank wt
\mathbf{g}^{dc}	Vector of temporal gaps between successive duty-cycles

H	Vector of unknown flow rates and pressures in the network
M	Matrix of decision variables related to the pumps relative speed
S ⁱⁿⁱ	Matrix of initial solution sets
X ⁱⁿⁱ	Vector of initial solution set
X	Matrix of decision variables associated with the pumps operation

Variables

$\$n$	Energy tariff applied to the optimization time horizon n
$\Delta L_{wt,n_s}$	Difference in tank wt head in the simulation time step n_s
$\Delta L_{wt,n}^{\text{demand}}$	Difference in tank wt water level caused by the external demands in the n -th optimization time horizon
$\Delta L_{wt,n}^{\text{pump}}$	Difference in tank wt water level due to the water pumped in the n -th optimization time horizon
$\Delta H_{j,n_s}^{\text{loss}}$	Difference in the pressure at two ends of a pipe j in the simulation time step n_s
Δt^{add}	Minimum time gap between duty-cycles for a duty-cycle addition
Δt^{del}	Maximum duration for duty-cycle elimination
Δt^{div}	Minimum duration for duty-cycles division
Δt^{gap}	Maximum time gap for duty-cycles merging
$\Delta t_n^{\text{horizon}}$	Duration of the optimization time horizon n
$\Delta t_{p,n}^{\text{op}}$	Pump p operating time at optimization time horizon n
$\Delta t_{n_s}^{\text{step}}$	Duration of the hydraulic simulation time step n_s
Δt^{prev}	Time interval between the current moment and the last water level reading
$\Delta t_{p,d}^{\text{dc}}$	Duration of the duty-cycle d of the pump p
$\dot{W}_{n,p}$	Hydraulic power of the pump p at each optimization time horizon n
$\eta_{p,n}$	Efficiency of pump p on the optimization time horizon n
A_{wt}	Area of the tank wt
$AB_{wt}^{\text{inf/sup}}$	Range of the adaptive controller inferior/superior activation band for tank wt
B_p	Auxiliary binary variable associated with the pump p status at each time t using the indirect control
C	Energy consumption cost
$CZ_{wt}^{\text{inf/sup}}$	Inferior/superior critical zone flag
f_p	Auxiliary continuous variable associated with pump p driver's frequency at each time t

H_i^{\max}	Maximum pressure at node i
H_i^{\min}	Minimum pressure at node i
H_{i,n_s}	Head of node i on the simulation time step n_s
H_p	Pump p head
L_{wt}^{initial}	Initial water tank level of the tank wt
L_{wt}^{end}	Water level of the tank wt at the end of the total time horizon T
$L_{p,wt}^{\text{hip}}$	Hypothetical water level of the tank wt at the next pump p state change
L_{wt}^{prev}	Previous recieved water level of the tank wt
L_{wt}^{real}	Current water level of the tank wt
$LD_{wt}^{\text{inf/sup}}$	Difference between real and predicted water level of the tank wt
M_p^{\max}	Maximum relative speed for pump p
M_p^{\min}	Minimum relative speed for pump p
N^{actual}	Actual speed of the pump
N^{nominal}	Nominal pump speed
n_p^{poles}	Number of poles of pump p
L_{wt}^{\max}	Maximum operational level for the tank wt
L_{wt}^{\min}	Minimum operational level for the tank wt
q^{external}	Forecasted water demands
$Q_{i,n_s}^{\text{in/out}}$	Node i inflow/outflow in the simulation time step n_s
Q_{j,n_s}	Flow of pipe j on the simulation time step n_s
Q_p	Pump p flow rate
R_j	Roughness coefficient of pipe j
s_p	Auxiliary binary variable associated with the pump p status at each time t
$st_{p,d}^{\text{dc}}$	Starting time of the duty-cycle d of the pump p
t_n	Starting time of the n -th optimization time horizon
$t_{p,wt}^{\text{new}}$	New duty-cycle time of pump p considering the water level of tank wt
t^{current}	Actual simulation/real time
$t_{p,wt}^{\text{a_inf/a_sup}}$	Superior and inferior anticipation time of pump p considering the water level of tank wt
X^{\max}	Maximum feasible value of the decision variables vector \mathbf{X}
X^{\min}	Minimum feasible value of the decision variables vector \mathbf{X}

Intentionally blank page.

1 | Introduction

Water supply systems (WSS) are among the most critical infrastructures for modern societies, ensuring access to drinking water and supporting economic and social development. However, their operation requires substantial amounts of energy, particularly for pumping stations, which represent the dominant component of total energy consumption in WSS. In a context of increasing water demand, fluctuating electricity prices, and growing sustainability concerns, improving the energy efficiency of WSS has become a pressing challenge. This thesis addresses this challenge by focusing on the optimization of pump operations, an area with high potential for cost reduction and immediate applicability in practice.

The organization of this chapter is as follows. Section 1.1 provides the background and motivation for the study. Section 1.2 outlines the objectives of the thesis and discusses its expected scientific and practical impacts. Section 1.3 summarizes the scientific contributions of this thesis. Finally, Section 1.4 presents the overall structure of the document, highlighting the contribution of each chapter.

1.1 Background and motivation

WSS are essential infrastructures responsible for delivering drinking water to populations with adequate pressure and quality. These systems are typically divided into several functional components, which include water intake, treatment, elevation, transport, storage, and distribution [1]. To fulfill their purpose, WSS rely on a variety of infrastructures such as sources and reservoirs, water treatment plants (WTP), storage tanks, connection elements (e.g., pipes and valves), and pumping stations [2].

In many European countries, there is a practical distinction between the bulk supply and the distribution segments of WSS [1]. Figure 1.1 illustrates the typical structure of a WSS, highlighting its main functional components, the distinction between bulk supply and distribution segments, and the subsystem that forms the scope of this thesis. The bulk supply side includes water intake, treatment, elevation, transport, and high-capacity storage tanks, and is often managed by regional or intermunicipal utilities. The distribution side covers the final delivery to consumers, usually handled by local water utilities or municipalities. While both segments are interconnected, this thesis focuses specifically on the bulk supply side due to its high energy consumption, with pumping stations alone accounting for up to 70–80% of a WSS’s total energy consumption [3, 4]. In Europe, this energy consumption was translated into annual costs ranging between 2.9 and 3.9 billion euros by 2017 [5]. In the context of highly fluctuating electricity prices, increasing water demand due to population growth, and growing pressure for

sustainability, improving the energy-cost efficiency of pumping operations has become a strategic objective for water utilities worldwide [6, 7].

Figure 1.1: Schematic representation of a typical water supply system, highlighting the division between the bulk supply and distribution segments, as well as the focus area of this thesis.

Although energy cost reduction in WSS can be achieved through several strategies, such as pump replacement, modernization of the pipe network, installation of energy-efficient components, or reconfiguration of system layouts, these typically require substantial financial investment and long implementation times [8]. In contrast, optimizing the operational strategy of existing pumping stations stands out as a highly cost-effective measure since it leverages existing infrastructure and leads to immediate reductions in energy consumption with minimal capital expenditure [3]. This makes operational optimization an attractive and practical first step for water utilities aiming to reduce costs and environmental impact while maintaining service quality.

At the operational level, energy-cost efficiency in WSS depends strongly on the ability to determine when and how pumps should operate to minimize cost while ensuring demand satisfaction and system stability. This challenge is formally known as the pump scheduling problem (PSP), which consists of defining pump operation schedules over a time horizon to minimize total energy cost [9]. The complexity of the problem arises from the non-linear dynamics of hydraulic systems, fluctuating energy tariffs, and the need to meet multiple constraints simultaneously, such as water tank level limits, water tank level continuity, and limited number of pump starts [10]. In addition to these modelling challenges, real-world implementation requires accurate system data, integration with real-time control systems, and sufficient computational resources to produce reliable solutions within operationally relevant time horizons, which often limits the direct adoption of optimization methods in practice.

Over the past two decades, numerous mathematical formulations and optimization techniques have been proposed to address the PSP. However, despite this extensive body of research, there is still no clear consensus on which methodological approach is most suitable for practical implementation. As highlighted in [11], most studies focus on the computational aspects of the approach, neglecting the implications of the chosen problem formulation. Yet, the way the PSP is formulated, for example, whether pump schedules are defined over fixed time steps or as unconstrained start-duration events, has a direct impact on the solution quality and performance of the optimization process.

In addition, despite the advances in the literature, many water utilities continue to rely on the domain knowledge from operators for determining pump schedules, frequently

without formal optimization tools, and often based only on predefined water tank level setpoints, further limiting the potential for energy-cost optimization. This gap between theory and practice contributes to inconsistency in methodological choices and limits the adoption of optimization strategies, which are often perceived as too complex to implement without specialized knowledge.

In summary, although the literature offers a wide variety of optimization techniques for the PSP, there is a clear need to clarify and structure the available methodological choices. This includes understanding the trade-offs between different formulations and identifying the performance boundaries of each approach. However, even when an appropriate optimization model is selected, the output often consists of a single solution, limiting the operator’s ability to explore alternatives or make informed trade-offs between cost, robustness, and operational flexibility. In this context, there is a growing need for decision support frameworks that provide not only optimal alternative solutions but also an intelligent and structured way to compare and select among them, empowering water utilities to adopt strategies that are aligned with their specific operational constraints and priorities.

1.2 Objectives and impact

The main objective of this thesis is to contribute to the optimization of pump operations in WSS by developing a decision support framework that enables water utility managers to define and select cost-efficient and operationally viable scheduling strategies. With this goal in mind, this work begins with a quantitative comparison of existing mathematical formulations for the pump scheduling problem, focusing on their level of operational abstraction and their computational efficiency. This comparative analysis represents a novel contribution to the field, as the literature lacks a systematic review that both formalizes the mathematical structure of each formulation and provides a quantitative performance assessment across typical literature benchmarks. It serves as foundation for the implementation of a novel mathematical formulation: the duty-cycle formulation. To fully leverage the performance of this formulation, a new hybrid optimization approach, the Smart Dynamic Local Search (Smart-DLS), is developed to enhance the model’s robustness and scalability. This approach integrates a gradient-based local search algorithm with rule-based shaking mechanisms that dynamically modify the initial search point and adapt the problem size, thereby improving the algorithm’s ability to explore complex and highly constrained solution spaces.

Building upon this optimization research, the thesis advances toward the design of an integrated decision support system (DSS). This framework combines the developments achieved so far and delivers multiple optimized pump schedules, each evaluated according to utility-specific key performance indicators (KPI). It integrates real operational data, such as SCADA measurements, demand forecasts, and dynamic electricity tariffs, ensuring that the proposed solutions are both technically feasible and context-aware. Rather than promoting a single “optimal” solution, the system is designed to support operator-in-the-loop decision-making by presenting a range of feasible alternatives tailored to different operational strategies. These KPIs include total energy cost, number of pump starts, water tank level compliance, and other water utility-defined performance criteria.

This research contributes to the field in three main dimensions. Scientifically, it advances the state of the art in PSP optimization by proposing a new hybrid algorithm built upon the duty-cycle formulation and adapted to the practical complexities of real WSS. Operationally, it improves the cost-efficiency and flexibility of water utility management by providing transparent, data-driven, and adaptable decision support. As a final contribution, this thesis delivers a functional and modular decision support system that empowers water utilities to make informed strategic decisions about pump operation, bridging the gap between optimization theory and day-to-day operational practice. A graphical overview of the problem, methodology and impact of this work is illustrated in Figure 1.2.

Furthermore, this work aligns with the United Nations 2030 Agenda for the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [12], particularly Goal 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation), Goal 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy), and Goal 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities). By improving the energy-cost efficiency of pump operations, water utilities contribute directly to these global sustainability targets.

1.3 Scientific contributions and dissemination of results

Several contributions to the scientific community were made during this thesis through publications in international journals (**J**) and conference proceedings (**C**). The work presented in this thesis resulted in five papers that are listed below:

- C1** M. Brás, A. Moura, A. Andrade-Campos, “Cost reduction of water supply systems through optimization methodologies: a comparative study of optimization approaches,” in *Proceedings of the 6th European Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management*, IEOM Society International, 306-318, 2023, DOI: 10.46254/EU6.20230097
- J1** M. Brás, A. Moura, A. Andrade-Campos, “Cost efficiency in water supply systems: an applied review on optimization models for the pump scheduling problem”, *European Journal of Operation Research*, vol. 323, pp. 1-19, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.ejor.2024.07.039
- J2** M. Brás, A. Moura, A. Andrade-Campos, “A novel hybrid optimization approach for cost-efficient pump scheduling in water supply systems”, *Omega*, vol. 138, pp. 103378, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.omega.2025.103378
- C2** M. Brás, A. Moura, A. Andrade-Campos, “A hybrid optimization approach for a continuous and efficient pump operation scheduling in water supply systems,” in *Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Control, Decision and Information Technologies*, IEEE, July, 2025. DOI: 10.1109/CoDIT66093.2025.11321341
- J3** M. Brás, M. Garruço, A. Moura, A. Andrade-Campos, “A decision support system for pump scheduling in water supply systems based on smart dynamic local search”, *Expert Systems with Applications*, 2025 (submitted for publication).

Additionally, six oral presentations (**O**) resulting from abstract submissions were made in international conferences, one of which resulted in a award of best presentation (**O1**):

- O1** M. Brás, A. Moura, A. Andrade-Campos, “Towards energy sustainability and cost reduction of water supply systems through operational optimization methodologies,” in *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Technologies for the Wellbeing and Sustainable Manufacturing Solutions*, TEMA - Centre for Mechanical Technology and Automation, 67, 2022.
- O2** M. Brás, A. Moura, A. Andrade-Campos, “Towards energy sustainability and cost reduction of water supply systems through operational optimization methodologies: a comparative study of problem formulations,” in *Proceedings of the Congress on Numerical Methods in Engineering*, International Center for Numerical Methods in Engineering (CIMNE), pp. 522-523, 2022.
- O3** M. Brás, A. Moura, A. Andrade-Campos, “Cost reduction of water supply systems through optimization methodologies,” in *Proceedings of the 11th IWA International Conference on Efficient Urban Water Use*, 2023.
- O4** M. Brás, A. Moura, A. Andrade-Campos, “Cost reduction of water supply systems through optimization methodologies: a comparative study of pump scheduling problem formulations,” in *Proceedings of the 7th ECCOMAS Young Investigators Conference*, 2023. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8393048
- O5** M. Brás, A. Moura, A. Andrade-Campos, “Cost efficiency of water supply systems through optimization methodologies,” in *Proceedings of the 10th Optimization Conference*, 2023.
- O6** M. Brás, A. Moura, A. Andrade-Campos, “Robust pump scheduling optimization model for energy cost reduction in smart predictive digital twins,” in *Proceedings of the 3rd IACM Digital Twins in Engineering Conference and 1st ECCOMAS Artificial Intelligence and Computational Methods in Applied Science*, 2025.

Finally, the following contributions were made as a co-author (**S**):

- S1** S. Mota, T. Pereira, A. Sousa, M. Brás, A. Reis, A. Andrade-Campos, “Differential machine learning model for simulation of water supply systems”, *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, vol. 151, no. 9, 2025, DOI: 10.1061/JWRMD5.WRENG-6698

1.4 Thesis structure

This thesis is structured into five chapters, including the present one, which introduces the research background, defines the main objectives, and outlines the overall organization of the document. An overview of this thesis structure and its relation to the main objectives and publications is illustrated in Figure 1.3. The organization reflects a logical progression from problem analysis, through method development, to system implementation and validation in real-world WSS:

Chapter 2 presents a detailed review of the state-of-the-art in pump scheduling optimization, with particular emphasis on the main mathematical formulations used to model the PSP in WSS with variable-speed pumps (VSP) **[J1]**. A quantitative comparison of the most relevant formulations, including one that had not been previously implemented (the

duty-cycle formulation), is performed using well-established benchmark networks [C1, J1]. The outcomes are compared with results from alternative methodologies reported in previous literature studies, enabling a critical analysis of each formulation's modelling assumptions, flexibility, and computational performance. Based on these results, the novel duty-cycle formulation, coupled with the sequential least squares programming (SLSQP) algorithm, is selected as the optimization model foundation for the subsequent developments.

Chapter 3 identifies the limitations of the current optimization model through a sensitivity, stability, and scalability analysis. These analyses expose key challenges such as the multiplicity of optimal solutions, vulnerability to local minima, and limited scalability in complex scenarios. Building on these findings, a new hybrid optimization method, the Smart-DLS, is developed to overcome the identified drawbacks [J2]. This chapter describes the algorithm's architecture and demonstrates its performance across both benchmark networks and real-world WSS.

Chapter 4 explores the integration of the Smart-DLS optimization method into a decision support framework, evaluating its effectiveness in assisting water utility operators in selecting appropriate pumping schedules under real operational conditions. The chapter begins with a sensitivity analysis of the pump scheduling problem using the duty-cycle formulation with variable-speed pumps, followed by a systematic review of recent literature, which highlights the limited presence of classical DSS within the water supply sector. A modular DSS architecture based on the Smart-DLS methodology is then proposed, and its performance is validated in two real WSS: the Ronqueira network, operating with fixed-speed pumps (FSP) [C2], and the Portuguese reference water supply system (PRWSS) network, featuring VSP [J3]. To deal with the discrepancies between forecasted and real water demands, which are outside the scope of this work, a real-time adaptive control method is proposed, ensuring that solutions remain feasible and effective under demand uncertainty.

Chapter 5 presents the main conclusions and contributions of this work, and outlines perspectives for future work within this research field.

Figure 1.2: Schematic representation of the studied problem, methodology implemented to solve it, and the impact and outcomes of the work developed throughout this thesis.

Figure 1.3: Overview of this thesis structure, highlighting the objectives, applications, and scientific publications resulting from each chapter.

2 | An applied state-of-the-art on pump scheduling optimization problems*

Although a WSS operates under demanding service standards and operational constraints, it still retains a degree of flexibility in pump and storage management. Given the high energy consumption associated, this flexibility provides opportunities for the application of optimization techniques to reduce energy costs.

This chapter presents an applied state-of-the-art review of optimization models for the PSP in WSS. The focus is towards the mathematical formulations used to represent pump operations, highlighting their modelling assumptions, operational constraints, and computational implications. In addition to resuming the existing literature, this chapter includes a quantitative comparison of the main optimization models using two well-established benchmark networks, providing a practical perspective on their performance and applicability.

The organization of this chapter is as follows: Section 2.1 introduces the optimization domains in WSS and justifies the focus on pump operation, particularly with VSP. Section 2.2 presents a detailed literature review of the PSP, including the mathematical formulations capable of representing both fixed-speed and variable-speed operation. Section 2.3 describes the methodology adopted for the quantitative comparison of approaches, including the case studies used, the implementation details, and the performance metrics applied. The results are analysed and discussed in relation to prior literature studies. Lastly, the chapter ends with some closing remarks.

*This chapter is based on the following published works:

M. Brás, A. Moura, A. Andrade-Campos, “Cost efficiency in water supply systems: an applied review on optimization models for the pump scheduling problem”, *European Journal of Operation Research*, vol. 323, pp. 1-19, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.ejor.2024.07.039.

M. Brás, A. Moura, A. Andrade-Campos, “Cost reduction of water supply systems through optimization methodologies: a comparative study of optimization approaches,” in *Proceedings of the 6th European Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management*, IEOM Society International, 306-318, 2023, DOI: 10.46254/EU6.20230097.

2.1 Optimization in water supply systems

The operation of WSS is typically guided by rules designed to meet multiple, often competing, objectives, such as minimizing operational costs, reducing energy use, avoiding overflows, and maintaining reliable service levels [14]. Optimization methods can be applied to different operational domains of WSS, with three main areas identified in the literature: water quality management, valve control, and pump operation [10].

Historically, research in WSS optimization initially focused on improving hydraulic performance. From the early 1990s, water quality emerged as a regulatory and public health priority, leading to greater attention to quality-based optimization [15]. Single-objective models in this domain include: (i) minimizing the operating cost of pumps while considering water treatment, source water, and utility turnout costs [16], (ii) minimizing the total cost of disinfectant mass dose [17], and (iii) minimizing the deviation of disinfectant concentration from target values at demand nodes [18]. Multi-objective approaches have also been developed, integrating water quality with economic and hydraulic performance goals [10].

Moreover, valve control plays a complementary role in WSS optimization, contributing to both energy and water quality objectives [19, 20]. Decision variables in valve control include valve status, positions, openings, flows, head losses, and pressure-reducing valve settings [21].

Among these areas, pump operation represents the greatest potential for cost savings, as pumping systems typically account for over 80% of total WSS energy consumption [4]. With the rising electricity costs worldwide, energy expenses incurred by pumping systems have become an increasingly significant part of the operational cost of WSS globally [22]. Beyond economic benefits, efficient pump scheduling can reduce unnecessary resource use and limit the ecological footprint associated with greenhouse gas emissions and pollution [6]. Energy cost optimization can be explored through various measures such as pump replacement, pumping station operational changes, pipe network modernization, network reconfiguration, and computer-based operational modelling [8]. Among these, changing the pumping operation is particularly attractive, as it requires no capital investment and can produce immediate energy cost reductions [3]. Typical operational strategies include aligning pump usage with lower electricity tariff periods and adopting VSP [23, 24]. However, their combination is not an easy task.

The adoption of VSP in place of FSP offers several advantages, including reduced energy consumption, decreased leakage, fewer pump switches, and improved control of WSS operations [25]. The main difference lies in the VSP ability to control flow rates according to system demand or pressure, enabled by variable frequency drives (VFD). Accurately modelling VSP operation requires adapting pump characteristic and efficiency curves for each speed [26]. The affinity laws (AL) provide a relationship between the performance of a given pump, as defined by its characteristic curve, and its modified performance curve resulting from speed changes [27]. The affinity laws articulate that the pump flow Q , head H , and power \dot{W} can respectively be represented by linear, quadratic, and cubic functions of the pump relative speed factor M [28], written as:

$$\frac{Q_1}{Q_2} = \frac{N_1}{N_2} = M; \frac{H_1}{H_2} = M^2; \frac{\dot{W}_1}{\dot{W}_2} = M^3, \quad (2.1)$$

where M denotes the relative speed factor, i.e., the ratio between the actual pump speed

N_1 and the nominal speed N_2 . Figure 2.1 illustrates the characteristic pump and power consumption curve for varying relative speeds.

Figure 2.1: Curves of a variable-speed pump for different speeds: (a) characteristic curves and (b) power consumption curves (adapted from [29]).

By adjusting pump speed to match the system requirements, both the pump characteristic curve and the power consumption vary according to the AL. Reducing the relative speed M shifts the characteristic curve downwards (Figure 2.1a) and lowers the corresponding power consumption curve (Figure 2.1b). As power consumption decreases with the cube of the relative speed, even moderate reductions can result in substantial energy savings. In practical terms, variable-speed operation typically results in more than 20% energy savings compared to fixed-speed operation [30].

Despite the well-documented benefits of variable-speed operation, most mathematical formulations for the PSP in the literature have been developed for FSP [31], with VSPs rarely considered due to the additional modelling complexity they introduce. This gap limits the applicability of many optimization models to real-world systems where VSP technology is increasingly implemented. Although comprehensive literature reviews on PSP already exist [10, 14], they largely provide a high-level overview of model functionality. In contrast, the present review offers a detailed mathematical definition of each main formulation and examines the implications of incorporating VSP-specific decision variables, thereby bridging a gap in the literature and establishing a solid foundation for the quantitative comparison that follows.

2.2 Pump scheduling problem

The formulation of the PSP requires defining the available operational options for the WSS, expressed through decision variables, constraints, and an objective function [16]. The general optimization model for the PSP, shown in Equations 2.2 to 2.8, aims to minimize the total energy cost of a given set of pumps P over the optimization horizon. The cost is typically calculated as the sum, across all simulation steps n_s , of the unit electricity price $\$_{n_s}$, the power consumption of each pump \dot{W}_{p,n_s} , and the duration of each step $\Delta t_{n_s}^{\text{step}}$. The power consumption depends on the operational status of each

pump, which is generally represented by the decision variables \mathbf{X} .

$$\text{minimize } C(\mathbf{X}) = \sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{n_s=1}^{N^{\text{steps}}} \left(\$_{n_s} \times \dot{W}_{p,n_s}(\mathbf{X}) \times \Delta t_{n_s}^{\text{step}} \right) \quad (2.2)$$

$$\text{subject to } Q_{i,n_s}^{\text{in}}(\mathbf{X}) - Q_{i,n_s}^{\text{out}}(\mathbf{X}) = q_{i,n_s}^{\text{external}}, \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N^{\text{nodes}}\}; \quad (2.3)$$

$$\forall n_s \in \{1, \dots, N^{\text{steps}}\}$$

$$Q_{wt,n_s}^{\text{in}}(\mathbf{X}) - \frac{A_{wt}}{\Delta t_{n_s}^{\text{step}}} \times \Delta L_{wt,n_s} = Q_{wt,n_s}^{\text{out}}(\mathbf{X}), \forall wt \in \{1, \dots, WT\}; \quad (2.4)$$

$$\forall n_s \in \{1, \dots, N^{\text{steps}}\}$$

$$\Delta H_{j,n_s}^{\text{loss}} = R_j \times Q_{j,n_s}(\mathbf{X}), \forall j \in \{1, \dots, N^{\text{pipes}}\}; \forall n_s \in \{1, \dots, N^{\text{steps}}\} \quad (2.5)$$

$$H_{n_s}^{\text{min}} \leq H_{i,n_s} \leq H_{n_s}^{\text{max}}, \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N^{\text{nodes}}\}; \forall n_s \in \{1, \dots, N^{\text{steps}}\} \quad (2.6)$$

$$\mathbf{L}_{wt}^{\text{min}} \leq \mathbf{L}_{wt}(\mathbf{X}) \leq \mathbf{L}_{wt}^{\text{max}}, \forall wt \in \{1, \dots, WT\} \quad (2.7)$$

$$X^{\text{min}} \leq X_{dv} \leq X^{\text{max}}, \forall dv \in \{1, \dots, DV\}. \quad (2.8)$$

The constraints can be grouped into three categories: (i) mass conservation, for nodes without tanks (Equation 2.3) and for nodes with tanks (Equation 2.4); (ii) energy conservation through head-loss relationships (Equation 2.5); and (iii) operational bounds, including minimum/maximum pressure limits (Equation 2.6), water tank level limits (Equation 2.7), and decision variables domain (Equation 2.8).

Mass conservation for non-tank nodes ensures that, at each simulation step n_s , the difference between inflow $Q_{n_s,i}^{\text{in}}$ and outflow $Q_{n_s,i}^{\text{out}}$ matches the external consumption $q_{n_s,i}^{\text{external}}$, or zero if no demand exists. For tank nodes, inflow is calculated from the tank area A_{wt} , the simulation time step $\Delta t_{n_s}^{\text{step}}$, and the change in tank head/level $\Delta L_{wt,n_s}$ caused by the inflow. Energy conservation is imposed by linking the head loss $\Delta H_{n_s,j}^{\text{loss}}$ in each pipe to the flow Q_{j,n_s} via the resistance coefficient R_j . Finally, operational bounds, including minimum and maximum pressure at non-tank nodes, admissible water tank levels, and limits on decision variables, ensure that the service levels remain within acceptable bounds and that the solutions remain feasible under real operating conditions.

Due to the nonlinear complexity of the hydraulic constraints related to mass and energy conservation, these are often not solved directly within the optimization model but instead verified externally through a hydraulic simulator. In the case of EPANET, a widely used hydraulic simulator, this is accomplished using Todini's Global Gradient Algorithm, which iteratively solves the nonlinear system of equations:

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{F}, \quad (2.9)$$

where \mathbf{A} is a symmetric matrix representing the hydraulic network characteristics, \mathbf{H} is the vector of unknown nodal heads, and \mathbf{F} is the demand vector. At each iteration, the algorithm updates flows and heads until mass and energy conservation are satisfied across the network.

As shown in Figure 2.2, the outputs of the hydraulic simulation include water tank levels \mathbf{L} , pump flow rates \mathbf{Q} , and pump heads \mathbf{H} , from which the pump hydraulic power consumption is computed as:

$$\dot{W}_{p,n_s} = \frac{\rho \times g \times H_{p,n_s} \times Q_{p,n_s}}{\eta_{p,n_s}}, \quad (2.10)$$

where ρ is the water density, g is the acceleration of gravity, and η_{p,n_s} is the pump efficiency. A detailed description of the algorithm implemented in EPANET can be found in [32].

Figure 2.2: Information flow between the optimization model and the hydraulic simulator. The converter translates the decision variables \mathbf{X} into pump status \mathbf{s} and pump frequency \mathbf{f} , which are used by the simulator to solve $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{F}$. The simulator returns the hydraulic information $(\mathbf{L}, \mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{H})$, which is fed back into the optimization process.

The formulation of the PSP has evolved considerably over time. In the literature, two main modelling concepts are identified: implicit control and explicit control [33]. In explicit control, pumps are directly represented by decision variables that specify their operating schedules, while in implicit control, pump operations are triggered indirectly by system characteristics such as pump flow/volume [34] or water tank levels [35], which serve as external activation signals. Figure 2.3 illustrates this classification according to the type of decision variables considered.

Figure 2.3: Classification of the mathematical formulations of the pump scheduling problem considering the definition of the decision variables.

Within the explicit formulations, two subcategories can be distinguished: time-position restricted (TPR) and time-position unrestricted (TPU). In the TPR approach, pump operation is defined in relation to a fixed set of time intervals (the time horizons), requiring pumps to start operating at the beginning of each interval. In the TPU approach, pumps

can start at any moment within the total time horizon, providing greater operational flexibility. Each of these can be further classified as discrete or continuous, depending on whether the decision variables are defined over a fixed time resolution Δt^{res} . Figure 2.4 illustrates the differences between the four main explicit formulations for P pumps over a total time horizon T .

Figure 2.4: Example of the differences between explicit approaches: (a) discrete and (b) continuous TPR, and (c) discrete and (d) continuous TPU. In the TPR explicit formulation, the decision variables are the time each pump operates during a specific predefined time interval, while in the TPU formulation pumps are given the flexibility to operate at any point within the entire time horizon. The difference between discrete and continuous formulations is related to the existence or not of a time resolution Δt^{res} over which the value of the variables must be defined.

This scheduling challenge is not exclusive to WSS. Similar problems arise in other engineering domains, such as chemical engineering, where comparable formulations are applied to batch scheduling [36]. As discussed by Méndez et al [37], there are strong parallels between these problems, with shared modelling concepts and solution approaches. The following sections present the main mathematical formulations proposed in the literature for solving the PSP.

2.2.1 PSP as an explicit control problem

As previously discussed, explicit formulations directly control pump operation through decision variables that define when pumps are switched on or off. The main formulations described in the literature include: the binary formulation (TPR), the binary formulation with relative frequency discretization (TPR), the real-continuous formulation (TPR), and the duty-cycles formulation (TPU). The last one has so far only been mentioned theoretically in [38], without mathematical formalization or practical implementation.

Time-position restricted: binary formulation

The binary formulation is one of the most common mathematical model used for optimizing pump operation and it belongs to the discrete time approaches. It involves using a set of binary decision variables, represented by \mathbf{X}^{bin} to determine whether the pump p , with $p=1, \dots, P$, is on or off during a specific time horizon n , with $n=1, \dots, N$. If $X_{p,n}^{\text{bin}}$ is set to zero, the pump p is off during the time horizon n . If $X_{p,n}^{\text{bin}}$ is set to one, the pump p is turned on. The decision variables are algebraically written as:

$$\mathbf{X}^{\text{bin}} = \begin{bmatrix} X_{1,1}^{\text{bin}} & \dots & X_{1,N}^{\text{bin}} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ X_{P,1}^{\text{bin}} & \dots & X_{P,N}^{\text{bin}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{size } P \times N). \quad (2.11)$$

In WSS with VSP, it is necessary to include in the decision variables the pump's frequency at each time horizon. Therefore, a matrix \mathbf{M}^{bin} defining each pump's relative frequency (fraction between the actual frequency, N^{actual} , and the nominal frequency, N^{nominal}) at each time horizon is added to the optimization model, and as a consequence, the binary problem with VSP has a total of $2 \times P \times N$ decisions variables. The matrix \mathbf{M}^{bin} is mathematically expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{M}^{\text{bin}} = \begin{bmatrix} M_{1,1}^{\text{bin}} & \dots & M_{1,N}^{\text{bin}} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ M_{P,1}^{\text{bin}} & \dots & M_{P,N}^{\text{bin}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{size } P \times N). \quad (2.12)$$

$M_{p,n}^{\text{bin}}$ is limited to the range between M_p^{min} and M_p^{max} , which represent the minimum and maximum relative frequencies that pump p can operate. The mathematical expression for the binary optimization model with VSP can be stated as follows:

$$\underset{\mathbf{X}^{\text{bin}} \in \{0,1\}, \mathbf{M}^{\text{bin}} \in \mathbb{R}^+}{\text{minimize}} \quad C(\mathbf{X}^{\text{bin}}, \mathbf{M}^{\text{bin}}) = \sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{n=1}^N \$_{p,n} \times \frac{\dot{W}_{p,n}(X_{p,n}^{\text{bin}}, M_{p,n}^{\text{bin}})}{\eta_{p,n}} \times X_{p,n}^{\text{bin}} \times \Delta t_n^{\text{horizon}} \quad (2.13)$$

$$\text{subject to } \mathbf{AH} = \mathbf{F} \quad (2.14)$$

$$\mathbf{L}_{wt}^{\text{min}} \leq \mathbf{L}_{wt}(\mathbf{X}^{\text{bin}}, \mathbf{M}^{\text{bin}}) \leq \mathbf{L}_{wt}^{\text{max}}, \quad \forall wt \in \{1, \dots, WT\} \quad (2.15)$$

$$X_{p,n}^{\text{bin}} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \quad \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\} \quad (2.16)$$

$$M_{p,n}^{\text{bin}} \in [M_p^{\text{min}}, M_p^{\text{max}}], \quad \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \quad \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \quad (2.17)$$

As shown in Figure 2.2, the WSS requires the pump status and frequency as input variables to control the pump's operation over the control horizon/total time horizon. To obtain this information, a converter was developed to transform each $X_{p,n}^{\text{bin}}$ and $M_{p,n}^{\text{bin}}$ into $s_p^{\text{bin}}(t)$ and $f_p^{\text{bin}}(t)$ in RPM, respectively. Considering t_n the n discrete time horizon starting time, N_p^{nominal} the pump p nominal frequency, and n_p^{poles} the pump p number of poles, these conversions can be translated into the following mathematical expressions:

$$s_p^{\text{bin}}(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } X_{p,n}^{\text{bin}} = 0, \\ 1, & \text{if } X_{p,n}^{\text{bin}} = 1, \end{cases} \quad \text{for } t_n \leq t < t_{n+1}, \quad \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \quad \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\}, \quad \text{and} \quad (2.18)$$

$$f_p^{\text{bin}}(t) = \frac{M_{p,n}^{\text{bin}} \times N_p^{\text{nominal}} \times 120}{n_p^{\text{poles}}}, \quad \text{for } t_n \leq t < t_{n+1}, \quad \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \quad \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \quad (2.19)$$

Figure 2.5 shows an illustrative example of the decision variables \mathbf{X}^{bin} , \mathbf{M}^{bin} , $s_1^{\text{bin}}(t)$, and $L_1(\mathbf{X}^{\text{bin}}, \mathbf{M}^{\text{bin}})$ for an example with one pump ($P=1$) and one water tank ($WT=1$).

Figure 2.5: Representation of \mathbf{X}^{bin} , \mathbf{M}^{bin} , $s_1^{\text{bin}}(t)$, and $L_1(\mathbf{X}^{\text{bin}})$ for the binary formulation applied to a WSS with one pump ($P=1$) and one water tank ($WT=1$).

Time-position restricted: binary formulation with relative frequency discretization

Usually, to simplify the binary mathematical formulation and reduce the number of decision variables, V relative frequencies within the available range are pre-defined for each pump. Therefore, the domain of the decision variables is transformed to $\mathbf{X}_{p,n}^{\text{dct}} \in \{0, M_p^1, M_p^2, \dots, M_p^V\}$, with $M_p^v \in [M_p^{\min}; M_p^{\max}]$, with $v=1, \dots, V$, and $p=1, \dots, P$. If $X_{p,n}^{\text{dct}}$ is equal to zero, the pump p is off during the time horizon n . On the other hand, if $X_{p,n}^{\text{dct}}$ is non-zero, the pump p is turned on during the time horizon n with a relative frequency of $X_{p,n}^{\text{dct}}$. Examples of application of this mathematical formulation application can be seen in [3, 39].

In this formulation, the pump always operates during the whole discrete time horizon, similar to the previous binary formulation. Nevertheless, the number of decision variables has been reduced by half ($P \times N$), and these decision variables are no longer binary. The optimization problem can be formulated as:

$$\underset{\mathbf{X}^{\text{dct}} \in \mathbb{R}_0^+}{\text{minimize}} \quad C(\mathbf{X}^{\text{dct}}) = \sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{n=1}^N \$_{p,n} \times \frac{\dot{W}_{p,n}(X_{p,n}^{\text{dct}})}{\eta_{p,n}} \times \Delta t_n^{\text{horizon}} \quad (2.20)$$

$$\text{subject to } \mathbf{AH} = \mathbf{F} \quad (2.21)$$

$$\mathbf{L}_{wt}^{\min} \leq \mathbf{L}_{wt}(\mathbf{X}^{\text{dct}}) \leq \mathbf{L}_{wt}^{\max}, \quad \forall wt \in \{1, \dots, WT\} \quad (2.22)$$

$$X_{p,n}^{\text{dct}} \in \{0, M_p^1, \dots, M_p^V\}, \quad \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \quad \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\}; \quad \forall v \in \{1, \dots, V\}. \quad (2.23)$$

The transformation of \mathbf{X}^{dct} into $s_p^{\text{dct}}(t)$ and $f_p^{\text{dct}}(t)$ can be represented mathematically as follows:

$$s_p^{\text{dct}}(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } X_{p,n}^{\text{dct}} = 0, \\ 1, & \text{if } X_{p,n}^{\text{dct}} > 0, \end{cases} \quad \text{for } t_n \leq t < t_{n+1}, \quad \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \quad \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\}, \quad \text{and} \quad (2.24)$$

$$f_p^{\text{dct}}(t) = \frac{X_{p,n}^{\text{dct}} \times N_p^{\text{nominal}} \times 120}{n_p^{\text{poles}}}, \quad \text{for } t_n \leq t < t_{n+1}, \quad \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \quad \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \quad (2.25)$$

Time-position restricted: real-continuous formulation

As in the previous formulations, the total time horizon is divided into discrete time horizons. However, in this approach, the set of decision variables \mathbf{X}^{rc} , with dimension $P \times N$, represents the normalized operation time of each pump during each time horizon. The pump p operating time at time horizon n , with a duration of $\Delta t_n^{\text{horizon}}$, is given by $\Delta t_{p,n}^{\text{op}}$. The decision variables can be written as:

$$\mathbf{X}^{\text{rc}} = \begin{bmatrix} X_{1,1}^{\text{rc}} & \cdots & X_{1,N}^{\text{rc}} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ X_{P,1}^{\text{rc}} & \cdots & X_{P,N}^{\text{rc}} \end{bmatrix}, \text{ with } X_{p,n}^{\text{rc}} = \frac{\Delta t_{p,n}^{\text{op}}}{\Delta t_n^{\text{horizon}}}, \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \quad (2.26)$$

Furthermore, a matrix of decision variables \mathbf{M}^{rc} , similar to the one described in Equation 2.12, is added to the model. This matrix defines each pump's relative frequency in each time horizon. When $X_{p,n}^{\text{rc}}$ is set to zero, the pump p is off during the time horizon n . Dissimilar from the previous formulations, when $X_{p,n}^{\text{rc}}$ is set between zero and one, the pump p is turned on during a period of time of $X_{p,n}^{\text{rc}} \times \Delta t_n^{\text{horizon}}$ with a relative frequency of $M_{p,n}^{\text{rc}}$. In each time horizon, the pumps can only start operating at the beginning of that time horizon. Examples of the use of this mathematical formulation can be found in [40]. The mathematical model is described as:

$$\underset{\mathbf{X}^{\text{rc}} \in \mathbb{R}_0^+, \mathbf{M}^{\text{rc}} \in \mathbb{R}_0^+}{\text{minimize}} \quad C(\mathbf{X}^{\text{rc}}, \mathbf{M}^{\text{rc}}) = \sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{n=1}^N \$_{p,n} \times \frac{\dot{W}_{p,n}(X_{p,n}^{\text{rc}}, M_{p,n}^{\text{rc}})}{\eta_{p,n}} \times X_{p,n}^{\text{rc}} \times \Delta t_n^{\text{horizon}} \quad (2.27)$$

$$\text{subject to } \mathbf{AH} = \mathbf{F} \quad (2.28)$$

$$\mathbf{L}_{wt}^{\min} \leq \mathbf{L}_{wt}(\mathbf{X}^{\text{rc}}, \mathbf{M}^{\text{rc}}) \leq \mathbf{L}_{wt}^{\max}, \forall wt \in \{1, \dots, WT\} \quad (2.29)$$

$$X_{p,n}^{\text{rc}} \in [0, 1], \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\} \quad (2.30)$$

$$M_{p,n}^{\text{rc}} \in \{0\} \cup [M_p^{\min}, M_p^{\max}], \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \quad (2.31)$$

For this formulation, the conversion process of \mathbf{X}^{rc} into $s^{\text{rc}}(t)$ is slightly more complex compared to the binary and discrete formulations:

$$s_p^{\text{rc}}(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } t_n \leq t < t_n + X_{p,n}^{\text{rc}} \times \Delta t_{p,n}^{\text{horizon}}, \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2.32)$$

However, the conversion of \mathbf{M}^{rc} into $f^{\text{rc}}(t)$ is similar to the discrete formulation, and its mathematical expression can be written as:

$$f_p^{\text{rc}}(t) = \frac{M_{p,n}^{\text{rc}} \times N_p^{\text{nominal}} \times 120}{n_p^{\text{poles}}}, \text{ for } t_n \leq t < t_{n+1}, \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \quad (2.33)$$

Figure 2.6 shows a schematic of \mathbf{X}^{rc} , \mathbf{M}^{rc} , $s_1^{\text{rc}}(t)$, and $L_1(X^{\text{rc}}, M^{\text{rc}})$ for an example with one pump ($P=1$) and one water tank ($WT=1$).

Figure 2.6: Representation of \mathbf{X}^{rc} , \mathbf{M}^{rc} , $s_1^{\text{rc}}(t)$, and $L_1(\mathbf{X}^{\text{rc}}, \mathbf{M}^{\text{rc}})$ for the real-continuous formulation applied to a WSS with one pump ($P=1$) and one water tank ($WT=1$).

Time-position unrestricted: duty-cycles formulation

In this TPU explicit formulation, pumps can start operating at any time during the total time horizon T , and the pumping operations are represented through the concept of duty-cycles (d). For example, if a pump is only allowed to operate once per day, there is only one duty-cycle per day. The set of decision variables $\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}} = [\mathbf{st}^{\text{dc}}, \Delta \mathbf{t}^{\text{dc}}]$ determines the starting time (st_d^{dc}) and time duration (Δt_d^{dc}) of each duty-cycle d . Consequently, two decision variables are associated with each duty-cycle, with values between 0 and T .

During the total time horizon T , pumps may operate multiple times. However, to minimize pump starts and correspondent maintenance costs, a maximum number of duty-cycles (D) per pump is set. This choice can reduce the number of constraints because possible constraints related to the maximum number of pump starts are not necessary. For each pump, the first D decision variables dictate the starting time, and the last D define the duration of each duty-cycle, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}} = \begin{bmatrix} X_{1,1}^{\text{dc}} & \cdots & X_{1,2D}^{\text{dc}} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ X_{P,1}^{\text{dc}} & \cdots & X_{P,2D}^{\text{dc}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{size } P \times 2D). \quad (2.34)$$

For WSS with VSP, a matrix \mathbf{M}^{dc} with size $P \times D$ is added to the decision variables. The element $M_{p,d}^{\text{dc}}$ determines the relative frequency of pump p on duty-cycle d . Therefore, compared to the time-position restricted formulations, only a single decision variable needs to be added per pump operation, rather than per time horizon, regardless of pump operation. The optimization model can be now formulated as:

$$\underset{\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}} \in \mathbb{R}_0^+, \mathbf{M}^{\text{dc}} \in \mathbb{R}_0^+}{\text{minimize}} \quad C(\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}}, \mathbf{M}^{\text{dc}}) = \sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{d=1}^D \$_{p,d}(X_{p,d}^{\text{dc}}, X_{p,d+D}^{\text{dc}}, M_{p,d}^{\text{dc}}) \times \frac{\dot{W}_{p,d}(X_{p,d}^{\text{dc}}, X_{p,d+D}^{\text{dc}}, M_{p,d}^{\text{dc}})}{\eta_{p,d}} \times X_{p,d+D}^{\text{dc}} \quad (2.35)$$

$$\text{subject to } \mathbf{AH} = \mathbf{F} \quad (2.36)$$

$$\mathbf{L}_{wt}^{\text{min}} \leq \mathbf{L}_{wt}(\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}}, \mathbf{M}^{\text{dc}}) \leq \mathbf{L}_{wt}^{\text{max}}, \quad \forall wt \in \{1, \dots, WT\} \quad (2.37)$$

$$X_{p,d+1}^{\text{dc}} - (X_{p,d}^{\text{dc}} + X_{p,d+D}^{\text{dc}}) \geq 0, \quad \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \quad \forall d \in \{1, \dots, D\} \quad (2.38)$$

$$X_{p,d}^{\text{dc}} \in [0, T], \quad \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \quad \forall d \in \{1, \dots, D\} \quad (2.39)$$

$$M_{p,d}^{\text{dc}} \in [M_p^{\text{min}}, M_p^{\text{max}}], \quad \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \quad \forall d \in \{1, \dots, D\}. \quad (2.40)$$

In addition to the typical constraints applied to this problem related to the variable's domain and to the minimum and maximum water tank levels, it is necessary to add another one related to the pump operations (Equations 2.38 and 2.39). This constraint ensures that the starting time for a particular duty-cycle is equal or greater than the stopping time of the previous duty-cycle. The conversions of \mathbf{X}^{dc} and \mathbf{M}^{dc} into $s^{\text{dc}}(t)$ and $f^{\text{dc}}(t)$ are mathematically translated in:

$$s_p^{\text{dc}}(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } X_{p,d}^{\text{dc}} \leq t < X_{p,d}^{\text{dc}} + X_{p,d+D}^{\text{dc}}, \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \forall d \in \{1, \dots, D\} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \text{ and} \quad (2.41)$$

$$f_p^{\text{dc}}(t) = \frac{M_{p,n}^{\text{dc}} \times N_p^{\text{nominal}} \times 120}{n_p^{\text{poles}}}, \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \forall d \in \{1, \dots, D\}. \quad (2.42)$$

A schematic of this conversion and $L_1(\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}}, \mathbf{M}^{\text{dc}})$ values is illustrated in Figure 2.7, for a practical case with one pump ($P=1$) and one water tank ($WT=1$).

Figure 2.7: Representation of $s_1^{\text{dc}}(t)$ and $L_1(\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}}, \mathbf{M}^{\text{dc}})$ for the duty-cycles formulation applied to a WSS with one pump ($P=1$) and one water tank ($WT=1$).

An extension of the duty-cycle formulation can be considered to further improve solution performance, although at the cost of increasing the model complexity. This variant allows the relative frequency to vary within each duty-cycle. In this case, the vector of decision variables $\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}} = [\mathbf{st}^{\text{dc}}, \Delta \mathbf{t}^{\text{dc}}, \mathbf{M}^{\text{start}}, \mathbf{M}^{\text{end}}]$ captures the operational schedule by specifying the starting time $st_{p,d}^{\text{dc}}$, the duration $\Delta t_{p,d}^{\text{dc}}$, the relative frequency at the start $M_{p,d}^{\text{start}}$, and the relative frequency at the end $M_{p,d}^{\text{end}}$ of each duty-cycle d for each pump p .

When comparing the previous formulations, the solutions space of the binary formulation is a subset of the real-continuous formulation, and the solution space of the latter is a subset of the duty-cycles formulation. Therefore, it is possible to write these mathematical models starting from the duty-cycles formulation. The duty-cycles formulation which incorporates the discrete formulation with N time horizons can be written as:

$$\underset{\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}} \in \mathbb{R}_0^+, \mathbf{M}^{\text{dc}} \in \mathbb{R}_0^+}{\text{minimize}} \quad C(\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}}, \mathbf{M}^{\text{dc}}) = \sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{d=1}^D \mathcal{S}_{p,d}(X_{p,d}^{\text{dc}}, X_{p,d+D}^{\text{dc}}, M_{p,d}^{\text{dc}}) \times \frac{\dot{W}_{p,d}(X_{p,d}^{\text{dc}}, X_{p,d+D}^{\text{dc}}, M_{p,d}^{\text{dc}})}{\eta_{p,d}} \times X_{p,d+D}^{\text{dc}} \quad (2.43)$$

$$\text{subject to } \mathbf{AH} = \mathbf{F} \quad (2.44)$$

$$\mathbf{L}_{wt}^{\min} \leq \mathbf{L}_{wt}(\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}}, \mathbf{M}^{\text{dc}}) \leq \mathbf{L}_{wt}^{\max}, \quad \forall wt \in \{1, \dots, WT\} \quad (2.45)$$

$$X_{p,d+1}^{\text{dc}} - (X_{p,d}^{\text{dc}} + X_{p,d+D}^{\text{dc}}) \geq 0, \quad \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \quad \forall d \in \{1, \dots, D\} \quad (2.46)$$

$$X_{p,d}^{\text{dc}} = t_d, \quad \text{for } D = N, \quad \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \quad \forall d \in \{1, \dots, D\} \quad (2.47)$$

$$X_{p,d}^{\text{dc}} \in [0, T], \quad \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \quad \forall d \in \{1, \dots, D\} \quad (2.48)$$

$$M_{p,d}^{\text{dc}} \in [M_p^{\min}, M_p^{\max}], \quad \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \quad \forall d \in \{1, \dots, D\}. \quad (2.49)$$

In this case, the number of duty-cycles is equal to the number of time horizons ($D = N$), and the starting time of each duty-cycle is equal to the starting time of each time horizon (t_d). Modifying the constraint that guarantees the time logic of the duty-cycles in Equation 2.46 to $X_{p,d+1}^{\text{dc}} - (X_{p,d}^{\text{dc}} + X_{p,d+D}^{\text{dc}}) = 0$, results in the binary formulation. This proves that it is possible to obtain, with the duty-cycles formulation, any solution within the solution space of the others formulations presented above. However, due to the large solution space, the optimization problem using the duty-cycle formulation requires more effort.

Although the general idea of this formulation was theoretically mentioned in [38], it was addressed only briefly and at a conceptual level, without providing a mathematical formalization or reporting any practical implementation. As a result, its potential remains largely unexplored in the literature, and no comparative performance assessment with other formulations has been documented.

2.2.2 PSP as an implicit control problem

The implicit control involves controlling the pumps' operations using external triggers. The most commonly used methods include the pump control through the volume of water supplied to each water tank and through the water levels in the tank.

Volume formulation

Implicit volume control is the method of controlling the pump operation by defining the amount of pumped water that feeds each WT water tanks. Within this mathematical formulation, a set of decision variables, \mathbf{X}^{v} , defines the volume of water supplied to each water tank within each N time horizons. The domain of these decision variables ranges from 0 (when the pumps are inactive) to the maximum water volume that can be supplied to each tank within a time horizon. This maximum volume can be determined by the duration of each time horizon and the maximum inlet flow rate. Therefore,

$$0 \leq X_{wt,n}^{\text{v}} \leq \Delta t_n^{\text{horizon}} \times Q_{wt}^{\max}, \quad \forall wt \in \{1, \dots, WT\}; \quad \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \quad (2.50)$$

The main advantage of this implicit formulation is the reduced computation time. This reduction is achieved by simplifying the pump scheduling problem by linearizing the system, which involves disregarding head losses and considering constant flows rates, thereby reducing computational complexity, as shown in [41]. A disadvantage of this

formulation is its applicability exclusively to non-meshed networks, as it requires a direct relationship between the volume of water supplied to each tank and the volume pumped by each pump. In this context, the volume of water pumped by a specific pump, denoted as p , directly corresponds to the water volume supplied to a particular water tank, denoted as wt . As a result, the operating time of pump p during time horizon n can be calculated using the formula: $\Delta t_{p,n}^{\text{op}} = \frac{X_{wt,n}^{\text{v}}}{Q_{wt,n}^{\text{op}}}$. Here, $Q_{wt,n}^{\text{op}}$ denotes the flow rate of pump p within that same time horizon.

Assuming that pumps and water tanks have a direct connection (pump 1 - water tank 1, pump 2 - water tank 2, ..., i.e. $p = wt$ etc.) and considering the $Q_{p,n}^{\text{op}}$ constant within each time horizon, it is possible to simplify the objective function as:

$$\begin{aligned}
C(\mathbf{X}^{\text{v}}) &= \sum_{wt=1}^{WT} \sum_{n=1}^N \$n \times \frac{\dot{W}_{p,n}(X_{wt,n}^{\text{v}})}{\eta_{p,n}(X_{wt,n}^{\text{v}})} \times \frac{X_{wt,n}^{\text{v}}}{Q_{wt,n}^{\text{op}}} \\
&= \sum_{wt=1}^{WT} \sum_{n=1}^N \$n \times \frac{\rho \times g \times h(X_{wt,n}^{\text{v}}) \times \cancel{Q_{wt,n}^{\text{op}}}}{\eta_{p,n}(X_{wt,n}^{\text{v}})} \times \frac{X_{wt,n}^{\text{v}}}{\cancel{Q_{wt,n}^{\text{op}}}} \\
&= \sum_{wt=1}^{WT} \sum_{n=1}^N \$n \times \frac{\rho \times g \times h(X_{wt,n}^{\text{v}})}{\eta_{p,n}(X_{wt,n}^{\text{v}})} \times X_{wt,n}^{\text{v}}.
\end{aligned} \tag{2.51}$$

Regarding the constraints of the water tank level, as the pump flow is considered constant for each time horizon, it is possible to directly calculate the water level in the tank at the end of each time horizon. Considering:

- L_{wt}^{initial} the initial water level in the tank wt ,
- $\Delta L_{wt,n}^{\text{pump}}$ the water level difference due to the pumped water in the n -th time horizon,
- $\Delta L_{wt,n}^{\text{demand}}$ the variation in the water level caused by consumers' demand in the n -th time horizon,
- t_n the n -th time horizon starting time,
- A_{wt}^T the area of the tank wt ,
- q^{demand} the forecasted water demand by consumers,

the water level of the tank wt at the end of the k -th time horizon can be calculated using the following simplified equation:

$$L_{k,wt} = L_{wt}^{\text{initial}} + \sum_{n=1}^k (\Delta L_{wt,n}^{\text{pump}} - \Delta L_{wt,n}^{\text{demand}}) = L_{wt}^{\text{initial}} + \frac{1}{A_{wt}^T} \left(\sum_{n=1}^k X_{wt,n}^{\text{v}} - \int_0^{t_{n+1}} q^{\text{demand}}(t) dt \right). \tag{2.52}$$

This implicit model formulation linearizes the problem and simplifies the hydraulic simulation, non considering non-linear head losses, as exemplified in [42]. Otherwise, a non-linear hydraulic simulator must be implemented to estimate the water tank levels and head at each time horizon, which means that this approach would have lost its advantage of low processing times.

The linear programming optimization model is translated into:

$$\underset{\mathbf{X}^v \in \mathbb{R}_0^+}{\text{minimize}} \quad C(\mathbf{X}^v) = \sum_{wt=1}^{WT} \sum_{n=1}^N \$n \times \frac{\rho \times g \times h(X_{wt,n}^v)}{\eta_{p,n}(X_{wt,n}^v)} \times X_{wt,n}^v \quad (2.53)$$

$$\text{subject to } \mathbf{L}_{wt}^{\min} \leq \mathbf{L}_{wt}(\mathbf{X}^v) \leq \mathbf{L}_{wt}^{\max}, \quad \forall wt \in \{1, \dots, WT\} \quad (2.54)$$

$$X_{wt,n}^v \in [0, \Delta t_n^{\text{horizon}} \times Q_{wt}^{\text{op}}], \quad \forall wt \in \{1, \dots, WT\}; \quad \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\}. \quad (2.55)$$

Once the solution of the optimization model has been obtained, it can be converted into pumping operations using the following expression:

$$s_p^v(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } t_n \leq t < t_n + \frac{X_{wt,n}^v}{Q_{wt,n}^{\text{op}}}, \quad \forall wt = p \in \{1, \dots, P\}; \quad \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2.56)$$

For WSS with VSP, the adjustment of their speed and flow rate allows them to operate more efficiently. By finding the optimal flow rate and relative speed, it is possible to minimize the amount of power consumed by the pump while still meeting the demand for water in the system. For the implicit mathematical models, the definition of the pump's speed at each time interval is established after obtaining the optimal operation. As in the explicit formulations, a set of V possible relative speeds at which each pump can operate is considered: $\mathbf{M}_p^v \in \{M_p^1, \dots, M_p^V\}$. Therefore, considering that the relationship between the relative speed and power consumed is known (see Equation 2.1) and considering the decision variables' value (water volume) and the set of possible relative speeds, it is possible to calculate which flow rate and relative speed combination results in the most economical combination of power consumed for each time horizon.

Water tank level formulation

In the water tank level formulation, the operation of the pumps is indirectly controlled by the water level in the tank. In the first proposed formulation of this type, the fixed trigger level (FTL) formulation, the decision variables define each water tank's admissible minimum and maximum levels [43]. Consequently, when the water level reaches the maximum threshold, the pump is turned off, and contrarily, when the level reaches the minimum threshold, the pump is turned on. This leads to only two decision variables for each water tank - the minimum and maximum water levels. A more sophisticated variant was proposed by Kazantzis et al. [44], the reduced fixed trigger levels (RFTL) formulation, where the decision variables, $\mathbf{X}^{\text{wtl}} = (\mathbf{X}^{\text{wtl},\min}, \mathbf{X}^{\text{wtl},\max})$, define the minimum and maximum water levels for each time horizon or energy tariff.

This formulation relies on a model that benefits from the capabilities of the majority of hydraulic simulators, such as the previously mentioned EPANET, to control pump operations based on predefined rules for the minimum and maximum water tank levels. Consequently, the model consists mainly of the objective function, the constraints associated with the domain of decision variables determining the minimum and maximum water volumes each tank can accommodate, and the constraint that defines that the model solution for the maximum water volume must be higher than the minimum water volume. The hydraulic simulator streamlines the process, making it a simple yet effective approach to pump scheduling optimization. For WSS with VSP, an auxiliary matrix \mathbf{M}^{wtl} of dimensions $P \times N$ can be introduced into the set of decision variables.

As in the previous formulation, it is assumed that pumps and water tanks are directly related (pump 1 - water tank 1, pump 2 - water tank 2,..., i.e. $p = wt$), and the value represented by $\mathbf{M}_{wt,n}^{wtl}$ signifies the relative frequency of pump wt at optimization time horizon n .

Due to the implicit nature of the problem, the objective function is calculated by aggregating the costs of the simulation steps contained in each optimization time horizon. Each time horizon n , characterized by a duration of $\Delta t_n^{\text{horizon}}$, is further subdivided into simulation time steps n_s , each with a duration of Δt^{step} . Furthermore, two arrays denoted \mathbf{N}^{st} and \mathbf{N}^{i} are defined. The first describes the total number of simulation steps in each time horizon n , which is calculated as $N_n^{\text{st}} = \frac{\Delta t_n^{\text{horizon}}}{\Delta t^{\text{step}}}$, and the second defines the position of the first simulation step included in each optimization time horizon. The optimization model would be:

$$\begin{aligned} \underset{\mathbf{X}^{\text{wtl}} \in \mathbb{R}_0^+, \mathbf{M}^{\text{wtl}} \in \mathbb{R}_0^+}{\text{minimize}} \quad & C(\mathbf{X}^{\text{wtl}}, \mathbf{M}^{\text{wtl}}) = \sum_{wt=1}^{WT} \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{n_s=N_n^{\text{i}}}^{N_n^{\text{i}}+N_n^{\text{st}}} \mathcal{S}_{n_s} \times \frac{\dot{W}_{wt,n}(\mathbf{X}_{wt,n}^{\text{wtl}}, M_{wt,n}^{\text{wtl}})}{\eta_{wt,n}} \times \\ & \Delta t_{n_s}^{\text{step}} \times B(\mathbf{X}_{wt,n}^{\text{wtl}}, n_s, M_{wt,n}^{\text{wtl}}) \end{aligned} \quad (2.57)$$

$$\text{subject to} \quad \mathbf{AH} = \mathbf{F} \quad (2.58)$$

$$X_{wt,n}^{\text{wtl,max}} - X_{wt,n}^{\text{wtl,min}} \geq 0, \quad \forall wt \in \{1, \dots, WT\}; \quad \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\} \quad (2.59)$$

$$X_{wt,n}^{\text{wtl,min}}, X_{wt,n}^{\text{wtl,max}} \in [L_{wt}^{\text{min}}, L_{wt}^{\text{max}}], \quad \forall wt \in \{1, \dots, WT\}; \quad \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\} \quad (2.60)$$

$$M_{wt,n}^{\text{wtl}} \in [M_p^{\text{min}}, M_p^{\text{max}}], \quad \forall p = wt \in \{1, \dots, WT\}; \quad \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\}, \quad (2.61)$$

where $B(X_{wt,n}^{\text{wtl}}, n_s, M_{wt,n}^{\text{wtl}})$ is a binary output function representing the indirect controller:

$$B(\mathbf{X}_{wt,n}^{\text{wtl}}, n_s, M_{wt,n}^{\text{wtl}}) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } L_{wt,n_s}(\mathbf{X}_{wt,n}^{\text{wtl}}, M_{wt,n}^{\text{wtl}}) \leq X_{wt,n}^{\text{wtl,min}}, \\ & \forall wt \in \{1, \dots, WT\}; \quad \forall n_s \in \{N_n^{\text{i}}, \dots, N_n^{\text{i}} + N_n^{\text{st}}\}; \\ & \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ 0, & \text{if } L_{wt,n_s}(\mathbf{X}_{wt,n}^{\text{wtl}}, M_{wt,n}^{\text{wtl}}) \geq X_{wt,n}^{\text{wtl,max}}, \\ & \forall wt \in \{1, \dots, WT\}; \quad \forall n_s \in \{N_n^{\text{i}}, \dots, N_n^{\text{i}} + N_n^{\text{st}}\}; \\ & \forall n \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ B(X_{wt,n}^{\text{wtl}}, n_s - 1, M_{wt,n}^{\text{wtl}}), & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2.62)$$

Specifically, the pump is activated when the water level is equal to or lower than the predefined minimum level (first condition of Equation 2.62), and it is turned off when the water level reaches or exceeds the specified maximum level for that simulation step (second condition of Equation 2.62). When the water level is within the range defined by the minimum and maximum levels, the pump maintains the status from the previous simulation step (third condition of Equation 2.62). If it is the first simulation step, the pump status is the predefined initial status s^{init} , i.e. $B(n_s = 1) = s^{\text{init}}$.

In summary, Figure 2.8 summarizes the main pump scheduling formulations and their characteristics.

Figure 2.8: Summary of the main mathematical formulations proposed for the pump scheduling optimization problem.

2.2.3 Other proposed mathematical formulations

In addition to the formulations described previously, several authors have proposed alternative approaches to improve model efficiency and achieve better operational solutions. Table A.1.1 in Appendix A presents a review of different mathematical formulations developed for the PSP.

Regarding explicit models, applying the formulations introduced earlier to WSS with multiple pumping stations (ST), each containing several pumps, can lead to a rapid increase in the number of decision variables. To address this issue, [38] proposed a TPR explicit formulation in which, instead of assigning a decision variable to each pump individually, a single variable is defined for each pumping station and time horizon. This variable, $X_{n,st}^{\text{stat}}$ with $n = 1, \dots, N$ and $st = 1, \dots, ST$, represents the set of pumps operating during that horizon. It is expressed in the form II.CC , where II is an integer identifying the pump combination, and CC specifies the percentage of the time horizon for which this combination is active. The special case $\text{II} = 0$ corresponds to no pumping activity, i.e., the decision of not to activate any pumps.

In [52], the authors proposed a TPU explicit formulation where pump operation is defined by pairs of integers $\{t_{\text{start}}, t_{\text{stop}}\}$, representing the start and stop times of each pump, measured in seconds from the beginning of the simulation. These pairs act as pump switches, and the total number of pairs determines the maximum number of allowable switches per pump. This formulation can be interpreted as a reformulation of the duty-cycle approach in a discrete-time model, where the decision variables explicitly define both the start and end of each operation. Unlike the duty-cycle formulation, where the operation duration is a decision variable, here the second integer explicitly dictates the stop time. In a subsequent work, Prasad et al. [53] proposed a variant, also based on a TPU explicit approach, in which the decision variables $\{t_{\text{off}}, t_{\text{on}}\}$ define the duration of pump inactivity and activity, respectively, measured in hours.

Later, Bagirov et al. [54] introduced another TPU explicit formulation by defining two sets of decision variables: a continuous vector t_m , which specifies the start and end times of each interval for pump m , and a binary vector X_m , which indicates whether pump m operates during each interval.

More recently, Marini et al. [55] proposed a TPU explicit formulation in which the decision variables specify the start time and duration of each pump operation. While similar to the duty-cycle formulation discussed earlier, this approach restricts decision variables to a predefined temporal resolution Δt_s (in minutes), thereby significantly reducing the solution space of the optimization problem.

In the field of implicit control models for water tank levels, [56] proposed the Variable Trigger Levels (VTL) formulation. This approach is typically applied to scenarios with two daily energy tariffs, commonly referred to as peak and off-peak periods. Pump operation is controlled by defining minimum and maximum tank levels at the beginning ($L_{\text{start}}^{\text{peak}}$) and end ($L_{\text{end}}^{\text{peak}}$) of the peak period. By specifying the exponents of a power law function ($y = ax^k$), it is possible to determine how the minimum level evolves during the off-peak period and how the maximum level evolves during the peak period. As a result, the tank filling and discharging phases are aligned with off-peak and peak tariff periods, respectively.

Building on this idea, [49] introduced the Reduced Fixed Levels in Additional Time Slots (RFLATS) formulation, which refines the optimization of trigger levels by incor-

Figure 2.9: Variable Trigger Levels and Reduced Fixed Levels in Additional Time Slots methodologies for setting on/off trigger levels for one pump. The main difference between these models lies in the strategy employed to define the minimum water level during off-peak periods and the maximum water level during peak periods. This strategy aims to ensure the water level is positioned close to the maximum allowed level at the beginning of the peak period.

porating additional time slots around tariff transitions. In a two-tariff daily structure, one extra slot of duration DP_s is inserted at the end of the off-peak period, just before the start of the peak tariff, during which an on-trigger level S_{on} must be specified. Similarly, another slot of duration DP_e is added at the end of the peak period, immediately before the return to the off-peak tariff, where an off-trigger level S_{off} is defined. This design ensures that tank levels are maximized at the onset of high-cost tariff periods and minimized at the beginning of low-cost periods, thereby improving cost-effectiveness.

Figure 2.9 illustrates examples of the water level limits produced by the VTL and RFLATS formulations for a system with two daily tariffs. In the VTL case, the choice of the power law exponents directly influences the switching levels, exemplified by the reference levels (a) to (f).

2.3 Quantitative comparison of different approaches

Given the diverse physical characteristics and operational behaviours of WSS, the performance of a mathematical formulation for pump scheduling can vary significantly across different contexts. The goal of this comparison is to identify a formulation capable of delivering efficient and robust performance under a wide range of operational conditions, which requires not only theoretical understanding but also empirical validation.

To this end, an initial quantitative comparison was carried out involving three explicit optimization models for the PSP: two TPR and one TPU. The performance of these models was evaluated using two well-established benchmark networks (single pump-tank and Van Zyl networks), and the results were compared with those from previous studies that applied their implicit models to the same benchmarks, providing a broader perspective on their strengths, limitations, and practical applicability.

2.3.1 Methodology

The model predictive control (MPC) framework, widely recognised for its efficiency in real-time control of WSS, requires solving the PSP as part of its operational process.

MPC is a comprehensive control strategy for managing dynamic processes under constraints and is structured into three core modules [57]: (a) a simulation module, which reproduces system dynamics over a defined future horizon; (b) a forecasting module, which predicts unknown future conditions; and (c) an optimization module, which determines the optimal control actions to achieve a specified objective, using the forecasted conditions together with the simulated dynamics. Among these components, the forecasting and optimization modules are typically the most computationally demanding [57]. MPC has been applied to a wide range of contexts, including centralized WSS control [50, 57, 58]. A schematic representation of the MPC framework is shown in Figure 2.10.

Figure 2.10: Model predictive control framework, where (a) represents the simulation module, (b) the prediction module, and (c) the optimization module. In this quantitative comparison, a framework based on the optimization and predictive modules was implemented.

For the purposes of this quantitative comparison, a framework that integrates the optimization and simulation modules of the MPC theory was implemented. As discussed in Section 2.2, due to the complexity of hydraulic constraints, these are typically excluded from the mathematical optimization model and instead verified externally through a hydraulic simulator [38]. In this structure, a candidate vector of decision variables \mathbf{X} is first generated, satisfying the explicit bound constraints (e.g., decision variable domains). This vector is then translated into control signals $s(t)$ and $f(t)$, which are evaluated in the WSS simulator to verify compliance with the system's implicit constraints ($\mathbf{AH} = \mathbf{F}$) and to produce the corresponding time series for hydraulic power (\dot{W}) and water levels (L). The feasibility of implicit bounds (e.g., water tank level limits, number of pump switches, etc.) is then verified, and the associated objective function value for \mathbf{X} is computed. This iterative process is repeated until the stopping criterion is met.

In this study, the EPANET hydraulic simulator was used as the WSS simulator. Three distinct optimization approaches were implemented in Python and tested in the

selected benchmark case studies:

- B-GA: binary formulation (Equations 2.13–2.17) solved with a binary genetic algorithm;
- RC-SLSQP: real-continuous formulation (Equations 2.27–2.31) solved with sequential least squares quadratic programming;
- DC-SLSQP: duty-cycle formulation (Equations 2.35–2.40) solved with sequential least squares quadratic programming.

For the binary formulation, the discrete nature of the decision variables required the use of a binary variant of the genetic algorithm implemented in Python, adapted from [59]. For the real-continuous and duty-cycle formulations, the optimization was carried out using the sequential least squares quadratic programming (SLSQP) algorithm available in the `scipy.optimize` library [60]. SLSQP is a numerical method for solving nonlinear constrained optimization problems and is particularly effective for convex or near-convex formulations [61].

To compare the performance of the three optimization approaches, the following KPI were chosen: number of decision variables, processing time, objective function evaluations, number of pump starts, and total cost. Additionally, the optimization approaches were run on an 11th Gen Intel(R) CORE(TM) i7-1185G7 CPU @ 3.00 GHz with 16 GB RAM.

2.3.2 Case study: single pump-tank network

A simple pump-tank network based on a real Portuguese water supply subsystem was implemented to carry out this initial analysis. It consists of one source, one fixed-speed pump P , one water tank F , and two consumption points (one consumption point before (CP 1) and one after (CP 2) the water tank F).

Figure 2.11: Schematic of the single pump-tank network, a benchmark based on a real Portuguese water supply subsystem.

The network schematic is shown in Figure 2.11. The water tank F has a quota of 100 m, 155 m² of area, and the water inlet is positioned at the bottom of the tank. For safety reasons, the tank's water level can only fluctuate between 2 and 8 m. This tank supplies

the consumption point 2 (CP 2) and also supplies the consumption point 1 (CP 1) when the pump P is not in operation. The pump curves and the water demands of these two regions are shown in Figure 2.12, and the energy tariff prices are listed in Table 2.1.

Figure 2.12: Characteristics curves of the pump in the single pump-tank network and water demands of each consumption point.

Table 2.1: Energy tariffs of the single pump-tank network.

Time interval (h)	Cost (€/kWh)
[0,2[0.0737
[2,6[0.006618
[6,7[0.0737
[7,9[0.10094
[9,12[0.18581
[12,24[0.10094

Single pump-tank network: results and discussion

Specific assumptions were made for each approach to balance solution accuracy and computational efficiency. For the B-GA, 48 time horizons ($N^{\text{B-GA}} = 48$) of 30 minutes each were adopted, providing a compromise between approximating continuous behaviour and avoiding an excessive number of decision variables. Additionally, for the B-GA, a population size of 100 individuals and a maximum of 1000 iterations was defined. For the RC-SLSQP approach, 6 time horizons ($N^{\text{RC-SLSQP}} = 6$) were defined, corresponding to the six energy tariff periods. For the DC-SLSQP approach, the maximum number of duty-cycles was set to 6 ($D = 6$). The results summary is presented in Table 2.2.

Figure 2.13 illustrates the solution obtained by each optimization approach, showing the pump status (solid green line), the evolution of the water tank level (solid blue line), the energy tariff prices (dotted orange line) with their division into time slots (solid grey vertical lines), and the water tank limits (dotted dark blue lines).

Table 2.2: Comparison of the single pump-tank network optimization results.

KPI/Optimization approach	B-GA	RC-SLSQP	DC-SLSQP
Number of decision variables	48	6	12
Processing time (s)/relative time	6249.78/5341.71	1.17/1	9.8/8.38
Objective function evaluations	100000	5	136
Number of pump starts	6	3	3
Total cost (€)	111.95 (+2.8%)	109.30 (+0.36%)	108.90

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 2.13: Results of the single pump-tank network optimization for (a) B-GA, (b) RC-SLSQP, and (c) DC-SLSQP approaches.

As shown in section 2.2.1, when comparing the general model formulation of each approach, if the number of time horizons is equal to the maximum number of duty-cycles, it is possible to conclude that the solutions space of the binary formulation is a subset of the real-continuous formulation, and the solution space of this last one is

a subset of the duty-cycles formulation. Therefore, it is possible to formulate these mathematical models starting from the duty-cycles formulation, and as a consequence, theoretically, it is possible to achieve any solution from the first and second models through the third one. As an inherent consequence of this hierarchical relationship, the duty-cycle approach contains a wider solution space, which may result in longer processing times and an increased number of objective function evaluations. However, in this practical case, it is not possible to make the same assertion. The B-GA approach fails to satisfy the essential condition of $N = D$. Consequently, it can only be stated that, in this case study, the solution space of the RC-SLSQP approach represents a subset of the DC-SLSQP approach.

Analysis of the single pump–tank WSS shows that the pumped flow is directly influenced by the water tank level. This relationship arises from the typical shape of the pump characteristic curve and from the fact that the water inlet is positioned below the tank. As a result, lower tank levels lead to reduced pump energy consumption, making it more cost-effective to operate the pump when the tank is at its lowest allowable level. The DC-SLSQP approach offers an advantage in this regard, as its TPU characteristic provides greater flexibility in selecting the pump starting times. In contrast, the B-GA and RC-SLSQP approaches operate with fixed pump starting times, limiting their ability to take advantage of low-level pumping opportunities.

Considering the discussion above, the DC-SLSQP approach was expected to deliver the lowest cost solutions. The results in Table 2.2 and Figure 2.13 confirm this expectation, however, the differences in final cost are relatively small, which can be explained by the simplicity of the case study, involving only one pump and one tank. To verify whether these differences become more pronounced, a more complex case study is analysed in the next subsection. Additionally, it is also important to evaluate whether the larger solution space of the DC-SLSQP approach impacts its computational performance compared with the RC-SLSQP approach as system complexity increases. In more complex networks, the expansion of the solution space could lead to longer processing times. Testing scenarios with multiple pumps and tanks will provide a broader perspective on the trade-offs between cost-effectiveness and computational efficiency, supporting more informed methodological choices. Regarding the processing time, for the single pump–tank WSS analysed, a single simulation required only 0.07 s, resulting in a total optimization time of approximately 10 s for the DC-SLSQP approach, which is acceptable for real-time decision-making applications.

Another relevant observation concerns the efficiency of the DC-SLSQP approach, which was found to be highly dependent on the quality of the initial solution provided. Multiple tests with different starting points showed that variations in the initial solution often led to different final results, indicating the presence of local minima. This issue is examined in more detail in the next chapter. Nevertheless, to ensure a fair comparison between optimization approaches in this case study, the same initial pumping schedule was used for all three.

The substantial differences observed in processing time and in the number of objective function evaluations between the B-GA and the other two approaches can be explained by the intrinsic characteristics of the binary genetic algorithm. Its stochastic search process and larger decision variable set inherently require more evaluations to converge to a satisfactory solution.

Regarding the number of pump starts, the decision variable structure of both the

RC-SLSQP and DC-SLSQP formulations limits them to a maximum of six pump starts. In this case, each achieved solutions with three starts, resulting in an identical impact on maintenance considerations. In contrast, the B-GA approach, with its larger decision variable set, allows up to twenty-four pump starts. In this case, it converged to a solution with six pump starts.

Table 2.3 compares the results of the DC-SLSQP approach, which achieved the best cost performance for this WSS, with two implicit models: the fixed trigger levels formulation solved with SLSQP (FTL-SLSQP) and the volume formulation solved with LINPROG [62] (V-LINPROG). These additional results, retrieved from [63], are also illustrated in Figure 2.14 for visual comparison.

Table 2.3: Comparison of optimization results for the single pump–tank network obtained with the DC-SLSQP approach and with implicit models (V-LINPROG and FTL-SLSQP) reported in the literature [63].

KPI/Optimization approach	V-LINPROG [63]	FTL-SLSQP [63]	DC-SLSQP
Number of decision variables	6	2	12
Objective function evaluations	-	27	136
Number of pump starts	3	2	3
Total cost (€)	110.77 (+1.72%)	118.53 (+8.84%)	108.90

As explained in Section 2.2.2, the volume formulation involves linearizing the optimization model, with its solutions specifying the volume of water pumped at the start of each time horizon. For this case study, [63] defined $N^V = 6$, matching the distribution of energy tariffs, as in the RC-SLSQP approach. Since the model disregards head losses and assumes constant flow rates, when its solution was tested in the EPANET simulation file of the real system, [63] found that the water tank level constraint was not respected by the end of the second time horizon (between 2:00 and 6:00). To address this issue, the author suggested a post-processing adjustment of the pumping operation, which explains why the second pump start in Figure 2.14a does not occur at the beginning of that time horizon (i.e., at 2:00). While the main advantage of this formulation is its linearity, allowing for near-instantaneous solution times, it requires post-processing adjustments and, as perviously mentioned, is only applicable to networks with a direct connection between pumps and tanks.

In the FTL-SLSQP approach, the decision variables define the water tank levels at which pumps should start and stop. For this formulation, [63] evaluated scenarios where the pump is on or off at the beginning of the simulation, with the off-state scenario producing better results, being the one illustrated in Figure 2.14b. This method mirrors a common operational practice in many utilities, where tank trigger levels are set manually by operators based on professional experience.

The numerical results in Table 2.3 highlight clear performance differences. The DC-SLSQP approach achieved the lowest total cost, outperforming both implicit models by a margin of +1.72% over V-LINPROG and +8.84% over FTL-SLSQP. In terms of pump starts, all three models produced solutions with a low number of starts (between two and three), suggesting similar implications for maintenance. The DC-SLSQP’s larger number of decision variables compared to the implicit models reflects its greater modelling flexibility, which allows it to explore a broader solution space and fine-tune pump operation

Figure 2.14: Results of the (a) V-LINPROG and (b) FTL-SLSQP optimization approaches applied to the single pump-tank network. Both results were retrieved from [63].

to tariff variations. The trade-off is a higher number of objective function evaluations, but still within computationally acceptable limits for real-time operation.

Overall, while implicit models offer advantages in simplicity and processing time, particularly for highly simplified networks, they lack the flexibility and accuracy of the DC-SLSQP approach, which explains its superior cost performance in this benchmark without compromising operational feasibility.

2.3.3 Case study: Van Zyl network

The well-known Van Zyl test network, proposed by Van Zyl et al. [35], was used as the second case study. This network, schematically illustrated in Figure 2.15, has been intentionally designed to accommodate a wide array of viable operational strategies [35], which makes it a suitable network to test the performance of optimization models.

This network comprises a source that feeds two tanks situated at higher elevations through a main and booster pump stations. At the source's pump station, there are two identical pumps, namely pump 1A and pump 2B, in parallel. The characteristic curves of each pump can be analysed in Figure 2.16.

In addition to the two parallel pumps at the source, there is a booster pump (referred as pump 3B) installed along the pipeline that supplies the higher of the two tanks, which is tank B. When one or both of the two parallel pumps in the pump station are active,

Figure 2.15: Van Zyl Test Network [35]. This water supply system was intentionally designed to accommodate a wide array of viable operational strategies.

Figure 2.16: Characteristics curves of the pumps in the Van Zyl test network. Both the hydraulic and efficiency curves are defined piecewise.

the booster pump increases the flow into tank B. However, in situations where neither pump 1A nor pump 2B are in operation, the booster pump transfers water from tank A to tank B.

Furthermore, both tanks are interconnected by means of a gravity line, and all demands are located at nodes along the gravity line. Consumption point 1 (CP 1) has a demand base of 100 L/s, while consumption point 2 (CP 2) has a demand base of 50 L/s, and both points multiply their demand base by the same pattern (Figure 2.17).

During periods of high demand, water is supplied from both tanks to meet the demand. Conversely, under conditions of low demand, water is naturally conveyed via gravity from tank B to tank A. The energy cost is 0.0244 £/kWh from 00:00 to 07:00 and 0.1194 £/kWh from 07:00 to 24:00, and it is defined that the 24-hour simulation would start at 07:00. Additional information about the system characteristics can be found in

Figure 2.17: Demand daily pattern of Van Zyl network. The demands change every hour during the total time horizon of 24 h.

the original paper [35].

The pump scheduling solution presented in the original paper [35] can be observed in Figure 2.18. From its analysis, one event stands out: the water level in tank A approaches closely its maximum capacity and remains in proximity for a considerable duration. A closer examination of this occurrence, from 07:00 to 10:00, shows that pump 2B is operating according to its pump scheduling, and there is a noticeable decline in water consumption during this time window (see Figure 2.17). This reduction in consumption during the above mentioned period should positively impact the water level in tank A. However, an intriguing discrepancy arises since the water level in tank A remains practically constant, not exceeding its maximum limit during this period. Upon examining the pump flow rates of each pump depicted in Figure 2.18b, it can be seen that there is an abnormal fluctuation in the pump flow during these periods. This phenomenon arises because the EPANET 2.0 hydraulic simulator disconnects the supply pipe from the tank when it reaches its maximum capacity, resulting in these irregular flow rate patterns. Consequently, it becomes evident that the simulator does not truly replicate the actual operation of the hydraulic network since it does not allow the tank to overflow. When the maximum levels of each tank are increased and the same solution is simulated again (Figure 2.18c), the maximum level of tank A is not respected, i.e., the solution proposed by Van Zyl et al. [35] does not seem to be technically feasible. To overcome this limitation and ensure a more accurate simulation, defining upper and lower bounds that differ from those specified in the original problem can be explored. By implementing this change, the flexibility to explore a wider range of potential solutions is gained, and, since the model inherently includes a constraint for water level limits, the final solution will be aligned with the required tank level limits.

Furthermore, another crucial aspect was identified, raising concerns about the results presented in other papers, such as in [53]. The EPANET simulation file provided by the original paper had hydraulic time steps and reporting time steps set at 1 hour intervals. This configuration implies that the data is treated as constant throughout these periods. Consequently, solutions involving one-hour intervals are not accurately simulated, leading to discrepancies between the reported tank levels, real-world conditions, and the associated cost estimations. To address this concern and ensure more realistic simulations, it is imperative to reduce the size of both the hydraulic and reporting time

Figure 2.18: Results from the original paper methodology [35] for the Van Zyl test network: (a) pump scheduling solution and water tank levels, (b) pump flows from the pump scheduling solution, and (c) pump scheduling solution and water tank levels with no water limit defined on the EPANET simulation file. As the Van Zyl case study defines the optimization process as starting at 07:00, the 00:00 time simulation in the graph corresponds to 07:00.

steps. This adjustment enables more precise modelling of the dynamic behaviour of the hydraulic network and returns more realistic results.

Therefore, modifications regarding water tank level limits and adjustment of hydraulic and reporting time steps in the EPANET simulation file were incorporated into the methodology of this study. The same conclusions were obtained in a recent study conducted by Marini et al. [55].

Van Zyl network: results and discussion

As in the previous case study, three explicit optimization approaches (B-GA, RC-SLSQP, and DC-SLSQP) were applied to the Van Zyl test network and their performance was evaluated using the same set of KPIs.

Specific conditions were established for each approach to ensure a fair basis for comparison. For the RC-SLSQP approach, seven time horizons were considered, each with varying durations (4, 4, 4, 5, 2, 2, and 3 hours, respectively). Considering the number of RC-SLSQP time horizons, for the DC-SLSQP approach, a maximum of 7 duty-cycles per pump was defined through the number of decision variables. Once again, in the B-GA approach, in order to become as close as possible to the continuum behaviour, 48 time horizons were used, each with a duration of 30 minutes. Additionally, an objective function penalty was introduced to limit the number of pump starts to a maximum of 7. Finally, it is important to note that all models incorporated a continuity constraint to ensure consistent water tank levels throughout the days. Specifically, the water level at the end of the day, $L_{wt}^{\text{end}}(\mathbf{X})$, must be equal or higher than the water level at the beginning of the day, L_{wt}^{initial} :

$$L_{wt}^{\text{initial}} \leq L_{wt}^{\text{end}}(\mathbf{X}), \text{ for } wt = \{1, 2\} \quad (2.63)$$

Furthermore, all models started with the same operation as the initial solution (Figure 2.19), which has a total cost of 215.76£. In Table 2.4, the results obtained for each optimization approach are presented. For the correct chart analysis, it is important to remember that Van Zyl's case study defines the optimization process as starting at 07:00, so the 00:00 time simulation in the chart is equivalent to 07:00.

Table 2.4: Results of each optimization approach (B-GA, RC-SLSQP and DC-SLSQP) for the Van Zyl network.

KPI/Optimization approach	B-GA	RC-SLSQP	DC-SLSQP
Number of decision variables	144 (48×3)	21 (7×3)	42 (14×3)
Processing time (s)/Relative time	81531.7/324.4	251.33/1	448.29/1.8
Objective function evaluations	4999	1749	3771
Number of pump starts (1A/2B/3B)	7/7/3	4/4/2	3/4/1
Total cost (£)	330.81 (+0.5%)	335.85 (+2.03%)	329.17

Figure 2.20 shows the solution obtained with each optimization approach, displaying the pumps status, the evolution of each water tank level, the energy tariff prices and its division into time slots, and the water tank level limits.

The B-GA approach exhibits a substantially higher processing time when analyzing the results. Specifically, it needed about 324 times longer (22.6 hours longer) to reach

Figure 2.19: Pumps operation of the initial solution. All optimization models started with the same operation as the initial solution. Since the Van Zyl case study defines the optimization process as starting at 07:00, the 00:00 time simulation in the chart corresponds to 07:00.

a solution than the RC-SLSQP approach, which was the one with lowest processing time. Furthermore, it is also the approach with the highest number of objective function evaluations, 2.9 times higher than RC-SLSQP. Once again, this significant differences in processing time and number of objective function evaluations observed for the B-GA approach, can be attributed to the intrinsic characteristics of the binary genetic algorithm. When conducting an analysis only between the RC-SLSQP and DC-SLSQP approaches, both using the same optimization algorithm, a proportional relationship of approximately 2 times between the number of decision variables and processing time becomes evident. As previously highlighted, time efficiency plays a crucial role in WSS real-time control, which demands prompt decision-making. Therefore, these results indicate that the B-GA approach could be unsuitable for such application.

Concerning the number of pump starts, the DC-SLSQP and RC-SLSQP approaches are implicitly constrained to a maximum of seven starts per pump due to the decision variables number. Nonetheless, the DC-SLSQP approach achieves a solution with fewer pump starts, which leads to a reduced impact on maintenance costs. In contrast, the B-GA approach has 48 decision variables for each pump, and consequently, each pump is constrained to a maximum of 24 pump starts. The approach achieved a solution with 17 pump starts despite the penalty cost added on the number of pump starts. In the case of the B-GA approach, the model could have achieved a better solution by increasing the maximum number of objective function evaluations. However, this change would have come at the cost of a further increase in processing time. Additionally, upon analyzing the distribution of pump starts across all approaches, pump 3B consistently exhibits the lowest number of starts across all solutions.

In conclusion, regarding cost-effectiveness, the DC-SLSQP approach achieved a solution 1.64£ and 6.68£ less expensive than those obtained through the B-GA and RC-

Figure 2.20: Results of the Van Zyl network optimization using (a) B-GA, (b) RC-SLSQP, and (c) DC-SLSQP approaches. Considering that the Van Zyl case study defines the optimization process as starting at 07:00, the 00:00 time simulation in the chart corresponds to 07:00.

SLSQP approaches, respectively, making it the most economically favourable option. Considering each approach results for the specified KPIs, it becomes evident that the DC-SLSQP approach emerges as the most efficient for this case study. This is aligned with the results from the previous case study.

Table 2.5 presents the outcomes of prior studies conducted on the Van Zyl test network. Only studies whose results were classified as technically feasible and could be successfully replicated were considered for the quantitative comparison. Despite the previous analysis in Section 2.3.3, the results presented in [35] were considered since the paper in question was the origin of this benchmark.

There are optimization methodologies proposed in the literature for the same network that achieved a lower operational cost. However, it is crucial to note that these studies operated under conditions distinct from those in this study. For example, the study by Vieira et al. [64] reported a total cost of 306.54£. This solution was achieved by allowing variations in the initial water tank level as long as the water tank level continuity was respected. Consequently, such results were not directly comparable to those of this study. Similarly, the cost of 306.88£ presented by Shao et al. [65] falls under the same category. Furthermore, the methodology proposed by Marchi et al. [48], whose solution reached a total cost of 312£, exhibits the same discrepancies as the Van Zyl optimization methodology, i.e., there are irregularities in the pump flow rate when its solution is tested. As explained in Section 2.3.3, these irregularities are attributed to the water tank reaching its maximum capacity, a scenario illustrated in Figure 2.18c of this study.

Analyzing Table 2.5 and comparing this study's solution with the solution derived from the original paper [35], it is noticeable that the DC-SLSQP approach can produce a cost reduction of approximately 5% with a smaller number of objective function evaluations. Moreover, the DC-SLSQP approach achieved fewer pump starts in comparison to the works of Van Zyl et al. [35] and López-Ibáñez et al. [66]. However, the optimization methodology proposed by Marini et al. [55] managed to achieve a solution with fewer pump starts. Nevertheless, despite being the paper that also verifies the technically incorrect solutions of other studies, it is worth noting that their solution exhibits two water tank level violations in tank A over the 24-hour simulation. This disparity could account for the difference in one pump activation compared to other studies.

Table 2.5: Comparison of Van Zyl test network optimization results.

Reference	Optimization methodology	Number of pump starts (1A/2B/3B)	Objective function evaluations	Total cost (£)
Van Zyl et al.[35]	Hydraulic simulator: EPANET Opt. algorithm: hybrid genatic algortihm Formulation: implicit (RFTL)	2/2/1	6000	344.43 (+4.64%)
López-Ibáñez et al. [66]	Hydraulic simulator: EPANET Opt. algorithm: ant colony meta-heuristics Opt. model formulation: TPU explicit	3/3/3	6000	333.09 (+1.19%)
Marini et al. [55]	Hydraulic simulator: EPANET Opt. algorithm: Pikaia genetic algorithm Opt. model formulation: TPU explicit	1/3/3	-	341.09 (+3.62%)
DC-SLSQP approach	Hydraulic simulator: EPANET Opt. algorithm: SLSQP Opt. model formulation: TPU explicit	3/4/1	3771	329.17

2.4 Final remarks

This chapter presented a comprehensive review of mathematical formulations for the PSP in WSS, covering both explicit and implicit approaches. The analysis demonstrated how the choice of formulation influences the flexibility of pump operation, the feasibility of solutions, and the computational effort required. Explicit formulations provide direct pump scheduling representations but often increase the number of decision variables and overall complexity, while implicit formulations are simpler but limited in terms of accuracy and adaptability to real-world networks.

A quantitative comparison was then carried out using two benchmark networks: single pump-tank and Van Zyl networks. Among the approaches tested, the duty-cycle formulation solved with SLSQP (DC-SLSQP) consistently achieved the best performance in terms of operational cost, outperforming both the binary and real-continuous explicit formulations, as well as the implicit models reported in the literature. Its broader solution space and operational flexibility allow for more economical operation schedules, confirming its potential as the most promising methodology for practical applications.

Additionally, the results also revealed some indications of limitations associated with the DC-SLSQP approach. These include higher computational effort, a larger number of objective function evaluations, and a noticeable sensitivity to the initial solution. While these issues were not explored in detail in this chapter, they highlight the need for a more thorough analysis of the formulation.

Therefore, the next chapter is dedicated to a deeper analysis of the DC-SLSQP approach. Its strengths and weaknesses are studied, and a new methodological development, the Smart-DLS heuristic, is proposed to address the problems identified, aiming to enhance the robustness and scalability of the optimization approach.

Intentionally blank page.

3 | Proposal of a novel optimization approach*

Among the formulations analyzed in the last chapter, the duty-cycle formulation combined with gradient-based optimization methods (in particular, SLSQP) demonstrated superior performance, achieving the most cost-effective solutions across different benchmark networks. Nevertheless, while obtaining the results, potential challenges were identified, such as sensitivity to initial solutions, multiple near-optimal solutions, and scalability issues in larger WSS. These aspects require further investigation before the methodology can be reliably applied to complex real-world water supply systems. Building upon these findings, this chapter focuses on a detailed study of the duty-cycle formulation, aiming to both identify its primary limitations and propose an improved hybrid optimization framework, the Smart Dynamic Local Search (Smart-DLS), to solve the problems identified.

This chapter is structured as follows. Sections 3.1 and 3.2 analyse the limitations of the duty-cycle formulation through sensitivity, stability, and scalability analyses. Section 3.3 introduces the Smart-DLS framework, designed to overcome the identified challenges by integrating deterministic local search with an intelligent shaking process. Section 3.4 demonstrates the applicability and effectiveness of Smart-DLS across three case studies: two literature benchmarks and the real-world Ronqueira WSS, allowing for comparison with literature results as well as validation under real-world operating conditions. The chapter ends with a summary of key findings and general conclusions.

*This chapter is based on the following published work:

M. Brás, A. Moura, A. Andrade-Campos, “A novel hybrid optimization approach for cost-efficient pump scheduling in water supply systems”, *Omega*, vol. 138, pp. 103378, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.omega.2025.103378

3.1 Problem of multiple optimal and near-optimal solutions

Optimal solution multiplicity occurs when different solutions meet all the constraints and produce similar optimal value for the objective function. This phenomenon is common in linear and nonlinear optimization problems and can create significant challenges in analysis and decision-making. In the context of WSS, this problem frequently manifests when the same energy tariff is applied for distinct time intervals within the total time horizon.

The existence of multiple local minima increases the complexity of the solution multiplicity. These points within the solution space represent points where the solution outperforms those in its immediate surroundings but might not represent the best possible solution (i.e. global minimum) for the entire problem domain. The distinction between local and global optima is crucial, particularly in non-convex problems where such pitfalls characterize the solution space and highlight the need for sophisticated strategies/solutions to achieve the most efficient overall solution. These solutions are usually achieved through global search optimization algorithms [68].

This section analyses the issues of multiple optimal solutions and local minima through a sensitivity analysis (Section 3.1.1) and a stability analysis (Section 3.1.2) of the optimization model under study. The single pump-tank WSS, previously introduced in Section 2.3.2, was used for this purpose, with the maximum number of duty-cycles set to five ($D = 5$).

3.1.1 Sensitivity analysis

Conducting a sensitivity analysis improves confidence in the model and its outcomes by offering insights into the model response to variations in input parameters [69]. Therefore, a sensitivity analysis was conducted for the objective function and the constraints using the Finite Difference Method (FDM). Based on the Taylor series expansion principles, the FDM is a numerical approach for a derivative approximation [70]. It estimates the impact of small variations in input variables on the model outputs by calculating the derivatives of those outputs concerning the inputs. This method can be defined for a generic continuous and differentiable function f as:

$$\frac{df(\mathbf{x})}{dx_i} \simeq \lim_{\Delta x_i \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(\mathbf{x} + \Delta x_i) - f(\mathbf{x})}{\Delta x_i}, \text{ for } i = 1, \dots, |\mathbf{x}|, \quad (3.1)$$

where Δx_i is a small perturbation of x_i [71].

The sensitivity analysis of each model function (objective function and constraints) is divided into two parts: the sensitivity analysis of the decision variables related to the starting time of each duty-cycle and those related to the duration of each duty-cycle.

Cost sensitivity: duty-cycles starting time (st_d^{dc})

Considering the maximum number of duty-cycles predefined, a pump operation was randomly defined represented by the decision variables vector $\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}} = [0, 2, 3, 4, 17, 1, 1, 1, 1, 2]$. Considering the operation of each duty-cycle, the starting time of the fourth duty-cycle was defined as $st_4^{\text{dc}} = 4 + 0.1 \times i$ [h], $\forall i \in \{0, \dots, 199\}$, with a duration of 1 h $\Delta t_4^{\text{dc}} = 1$. For each st_4^{dc} possible value, the corresponding cost sensitivity was calculated and presented in Figure 3.1. The analysis of Figure 3.1 shows that the cost sensitivity

Figure 3.1: Cost sensitivity to the decision variables related to the duty-cycle starting time st_4^{dc} (dC/dst_4^{dc}). For a WSS with one pump and one water tank with water inlet from below, and considering the randomly chosen pump operation, $\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}} = [0, 2, 3, st_4^{\text{dc}}, 17, 1, 1, 1, 1, 2]$, the cost sensitivity was calculated for different values of the fourth duty-cycle starting time ($st_4^{\text{dc}} \in [4, 15.9]$ h). It should be highlighted that $\Delta t_4^{\text{dc}} = 1$ h.

(the sensitivity to the optimization objective function) to the starting time of a duty-cycle varies with the value of this decision variable. A clear pattern is associated with the energy tariff transitions, indicating that duty-cycles moving into higher or lower energy tariffs result in increased or decreased cost sensitivity, respectively. Additionally, it is possible to verify that there are starting time values whose cost sensitivity is similar. This behavior occurs when the duty-cycle is within the same energy tariff conditions, either within the same tariff or transitioning between tariffs. Since the variation of the starting time does not influence the volume of pumped water, the cost variations will have similar magnitudes, leading to identical sensitivity levels.

When the duty-cycle falls within a single energy tariff, the cost sensitivity for the starting time decision variable seems insignificant, approaching zero. However, on closer inspection of the right zoom of Figure 3.1, it is possible to verify that these values, although extremely close to zero, are slightly negative. This slight difference arises from the configuration of the WSS in analysis where the water tank is filled from the bottom. Each WSS is regulated by energy and mass balance. As a consequence, the pump operation point is adjusted within the pump characteristic curve (Figure 3.2a) according to the needs of the WSS to maintain the balance. In this WSS design, the water tank level, in addition to the consumption point between the pump and the tank, influences the pump flow and, consequently, the hydraulic pump power required to pump water into the tank. Specifically, a lower water level (head) leads to a higher pumping flow, resulting in lower hydraulic power consumption by the pump, as demonstrated in Figure 3.2b. Therefore, in scenarios where the duty-cycle is confined to a single energy tariff, the cost sensitivity to the duty-cycle starting time is only related to the power consumption variations associated with changes in the consumption point demand (increase in each 0.5 h) and the water tank level (decrease in each 0.1 h in the right zoom of Figure 3.1). Considering that the consumption patterns are defined in 30-minute time-steps, successive starting

times contained in the same consumption time-step and having similar energy tariff conditions (whether remaining within a single energy tariff or transitioning between tariffs) will exhibit a decreased tendency regarding cost sensitivity, as shown in the left zoomed points of the Figure 3.1. The same conclusion could be achieved through the analysis of the \dot{W}/η curves in Figure 3.2b. The curve head vs. hydraulic power exhibits a quadratic behavior, which means that identical changes in the pump head at different operating points do not lead to the same hydraulic power variations, leading to non-constant cost sensitivity. Consequently, later starting times, which correspond to lower pump heads, result in higher negative variations in pump hydraulic power for the same decrease in the water tank level. This translates to reduced cost sensitivities for higher starting times.

On the contrary, for WSS tanks supplied from the top, the cost sensitivity would solely depend on energy tariff transactions and consumption point demands. In such WSS designs, the water level within the tank does not influence the pump power consumption. Consequently, when the starting times of the duty-cycles fall under identical energy tariff and consumption conditions, the cost sensitivity values remain practically constant, showing no decline between consecutive starting times. Moreover, in scenarios where duty-cycles are entirely contained within a single energy tariff, the cost sensitivity would be zero, indicating no impact from the starting time of the duty-cycle on the cost due to the constant energy tariff applied throughout the duty-cycle. To complement the cost

Figure 3.2: Pump curve and hydraulic power relation to the variation in the pump operating point. For water tanks fed from below, as the water level in the tank varies, the pump operating point shifts along its characteristic curve. This movement implies that a lower head, directly associated with the tank level, reduces power consumption. Additionally, given the quadratic nature of the curve relating the head to hydraulic power, identical alterations in the pump head at distinct operating points lead to different adjustments in the hydraulic power and, as a consequence, in the energy consumption cost.

sensitivity analysis to the duty-cycle starting time, variations were introduced at the starting time of the third and fourth duty-cycles. Figure 3.3 represents the cost for each possible combination of these two decision variables (considering $\Delta t_3^{\text{dc}} = 1$ and $\Delta t_4^{\text{dc}} = 1$), providing an understanding of how alterations in the starting times of these duty-cycles impact the total cost. Figure 3.3a demonstrates the reduced cost sensitivity for starting times when duty-cycles fall within the same energy tariff, evident from the multiple

plateaus/levels on the cost surface. When solved with local optimization algorithms, these plateaus could suggest a potential limitation that concerns the possible dependence on the initial solution to achieve a global optimal rather than a minimum local solution. This problem is analyzed in the following sub-section.

Figure 3.3b highlights the impact of the temporal logic constraint, expressed in Equations 5 and 6, limiting the optimization model solution space. For this WSS, if the water tank level constraint was ignored and if the objective was exclusively on optimizing these two decision variables (st_3^{dc} e st_4^{dc}) while keeping other variables constant, a global minimum would be identified on the cost surface at $st_3^{\text{dc}}=3$ e $st_4^{\text{dc}}=4$. However, considering the aforementioned, when the WSS tank is supplied from the top, numerous combinations of st_3^{dc} and st_4^{dc} could lead to the same minimum operation cost.

Figure 3.3: Cost surface for the possible values of the 3rd and 4th duty-cycles starting time, considering a randomly chosen pump operation $\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}} = [0, 2, st_3^{\text{dc}}, st_4^{\text{dc}}, 17, 1, 1, 1, 1, 2]$.

Cost sensitivity: duty-cycles duration (Δt_d^{dc})

Similarly, to evaluate the cost sensitivity concerning the decision variables associated with the duration of each duty-cycle, the duration of the fourth duty-cycle was defined as $\Delta t_4^{\text{dc}} = 0.25 \times i$ [h], $\forall i \in \{1, \dots, 51\}$. For every value of Δt_4^{dc} , the corresponding cost sensitivity was calculated and is depicted in Figure 3.4. As expected, the cost function shows sensitivity to the duration variable, regardless of its value, due to its direct impact on the pump operation. The possible values for the decision variables st_4^{dc} and Δt_4^{dc} were explored, with the associated costs illustrated in Figure 3.5. The cost results show that an increase in Δt_4^{dc} led to a corresponding increase in cost for each possible value of st_4^{dc} . Conversely, Figure 3.5 confirms the reduced sensitivity of the cost to the starting time variable since, for a constant duration value, the cost remains relatively constant across different starting time values with the same energy tariff conditions.

Figure 3.4: Cost sensitivity to the decision variables related to the duty-cycle duration, Δt_4^{dc} . Considering the randomly chosen pump operation $\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}} = [0, 2, 3, 4, 17, 1, 1, 1, \Delta t_4^{\text{dc}}, 2]$, for a WSS with one pump and one water tank with water inlet from below, the cost sensitivity was calculated for different values of the fourth duty-cycle duration ($\Delta t_4^{\text{dc}} \in [0.25, 12.75]$ h). For this case, $st_4^{\text{dc}} = 4$ h.

Figure 3.5: Cost surface for the possible values of the starting time st_4^{dc} and time duration Δt_4^{dc} of the fourth duty-cycle, considering the randomly chosen pump operation $\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}} = [0, 2, 3, st_4^{\text{dc}}, 17, 1, 1, 1, \Delta t_4^{\text{dc}}, 2]$.

Constraints sensitivity: water tank level (L_{wt})

In the context of the pump scheduling problem, without considering a water tank level continuity constraint ($L_{wt}^{\text{end}} \geq L_{wt}^{\text{initial}}$), a solution is considered potentially optimal if the pump feeds the WSS with the minimum water volume necessary to meet the consumption demands. This premise is verified by analyzing the water tank level for the proposed solution, i.e., if the tank level at the end of the total time horizon aligns with the predefined minimum level ($L_{wt}^{\text{end}} \simeq L_{wt}^{\text{min}}$), the pump has pumped the minimum required water volume. However, it is possible to pump the same volume of

water with different pumping operations and, consequently, different operating costs. Using a potentially optimal pump operation defined by the decision variable vector $\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}} = [0.95, 1.70, 10.84, 14.80, 17.80, 0.75, 5.24, 6.14, 1.05, 3.27]$, the sensitivity of the water tank level to the starting time of a duty-cycle was evaluated. Figure 3.6 illustrates the water tank level across two different values of st_4^{dc} (14.8 and 14.82) and the constraint sensitivity to the same decision variable for $st_4^{\text{dc}} = 14.8$ h.

The water tank level constraint, expressed mathematically in Equation 2.37, requires that the water level in the tank must remain between the specified minimum (L^{min}) and maximum (L^{max}) thresholds during the entire total time horizon. Considering that the tank level only varies due to consumption requirements and pump operation, it is sufficient to confirm the water level only at the start and end of each pump operation and at the end of the total time horizon to verify compliance with the constraint. As a result, for D duty-cycles, a total of $2 \times D + 1$ time instants are enough to be considered for the water tank level constraint. In the scenario represented in Figure 3.6, only 9 time instants are presented instead of 11 due to the overlapping of time instants resulting from a duty-cycle with no duration and consecutive duty-cycles.

Figure 3.6 demonstrates that the starting time of a duty-cycle exclusively affects the water tank level of its duty-cycle since this variable do not change significantly the volume of water pumped but merely shifts the timing of the pump operation. Consequently, sensitivity is observed only in the time interval directly associated with the specific duty-cycle tank level, with other time instants remaining unaffected. Finally, despite variations in starting time, the same volume of water is pumped, and the water tank level at the end of the total time horizon reaches the minimum threshold. However, as explained in the previous section, for this WSS the operation characterized by the higher starting time is the most cost-effective, as it involves pumping at lower water tank levels, thus optimizing operational costs. In a WSS with a tank fed from the top, these slightly different pumping operations would result in exactly the same cost.

Alternatively, changing the duration of the same duty-cycle reveals sensitivities not only at the water tank level instants of that specific duty-cycle but also at subsequent time instants throughout the total time horizon. As demonstrated in Figure 3.7, modifying the duty-cycle duration impacts the water pumped volume, affecting water levels at later times. The sensitivity increases at the time corresponding to the end of the duty-cycle since the actual duty-cycle operates for a longer time. As a result, it will increase the water level in which the subsequent duty-cycles will be operating, resulting in the sensitivity of the subsequent time instants that the water level is evaluated.

Constraints sensitivity: duty-cycles temporal logic (g_d^{dc})

The analysis of the duty-cycle temporal logic constraint, defined in Equations 2.38 and 2.39, is more straightforward than the previous analysis as it is focused on the temporal intervals between successive duty-cycles, which have a linear characteristic. When a duty-cycle starting time or duration is changed, sensitivity arises at constraint points directly associated with the affected duty-cycle, while other points show no sensitivity.

Considering the WSS under analysis ($P = 1$) and the definition of the \mathbf{g}^{dc} , if the st_d^{dc} ($\forall d \in \{1, \dots, D - 1\}$) is positively increased, it will result in a non-zero sensitivity at the constraint point related to time difference between the d and $d + 1$ duty-cycles ($dg_d^{\text{dc}}/dst_d^{\text{dc}} = -1$), as well as between the $d - 1$ and d duty-cycles ($dg_{d-1}^{\text{dc}}/dst_d^{\text{dc}} = 1$).

Figure 3.6: Water tank level and corresponding sensitivity of the fourth duty-cycle starting time st_4^{dc} , considering the possible optimal pump operation for 5 duty-cycles ($D = 5$) $\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}} = [0.95, 1.70, 10.84, 14.80, 17.80, 0.75, 5.24, 0, 1.05, 3.27]$.

Figure 3.7: Water tank level and corresponding sensitivity of the fourth duty-cycle duration Δt_4^{dc} , considering a possible optimal pump operation for 5 duty-cycles ($D = 5$): $\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}} = [0.95, 1.70, 10.84, 14.80, 17.80, 0.75, 5.24, 0, 1.05, 3.27]$.

Conversely, when the Δt_d^{dc} is positively increased, only the constraint points related the time difference between the d and $d + 1$ duty-cycles will have sensitivity ($dg_d^{\text{dc}}/d\Delta t_d^{\text{dc}} = -1$). Increasing the start or duration of the last duty-cycle ($d = D$) will both lead to a negative sensitivity on the last point of the temporal logic constraint ($dg_D^{\text{dc}}/dst_D^{\text{dc}} = -1$ and $dg_D^{\text{dc}}/d\Delta t_D^{\text{dc}} = -1$).

Given the WSS used in this initial analysis and the previous conclusions, the sensitivity matrix (jacobian) of the temporal logic constraint to the decision variable vector \mathbf{X}^{dc} could be expressed as:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{g}^{\text{dc}}}{d\mathbf{X}^{\text{dc}}} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & -1 & 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots & 0 & \ddots & \ddots & & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 & \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \ddots & 1 & \vdots & & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 & -1 & 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3.2)$$

3.1.2 Stability analysis

A stability analysis is a type of sensitivity analysis that measures the effect of small perturbations in the model input parameters on the optimal solution provided by the optimization model. From the purpose of this work, this analysis aims to estimate the robustness of the model solutions regarding the initial solution set. As an initial approach, the duty-cycle optimization model was solved using the SLSQP algorithm. As a gradient-based optimization method, SLSQP relies on gradients (or its approximations) of the objective function and constraints, which can be easily associated with the sensitivity information analyzed in the previous section.

To investigate the model stability, a strategy based on the multi-starting technique was employed, involving the definition of four approaches for selecting potential initial solutions:

- Approach 1: uniformly distributed initial solution by dividing the total time horizon by the maximum number of duty-cycles ($D = 5$), placing all duty-cycles sequentially with uniform duration.
- Approach 2: initial solution with duty-cycles at energy tariff transitions. As this WSS operates under 6 different energy tariffs, each duty-cycle ($D = 5$) of 1 h duration is centered at each tariff transition point.
- Approach 3: initial solution with one duty-cycle within each energy tariff. Given the existence of 6 energy tariffs, it was necessary to test this approach by setting $D = 6$, with each duty-cycle centered within the duration of its respective tariff period.
- Approach 4: initial solution with 6 duty-cycles ($D = 6$), where the first two duty-cycles are in the same position as those of the initial set of Approach 3, and the other four are distributed in the last energy tariff of the total time horizon.

The four approaches were evaluated by applying equal stopping conditions in the SLSQP algorithm. The results of each method are exposed in Table 3.1 and shown in Figure 3.8 by the pump status for each solution and the respective water tank levels.

Upon examining the water tank levels resulting from each solution, it is clear that all solutions involve pumping the minimum volume of water required to satisfy the consumption demands, as indicated by the water levels reaching the minimum level at the end of the day. Although the values of the decision variables are different for the four solutions,

Figure 3.8: Optimization results applying different approaches to define the initial solution: (a) uniformly distributed initial solution with $D = 5$, (b) one duty-cycles at each tariff transition by setting $D = 5$, (c) one duty-cycle centered in each energy tariff by defining $D = 6$, and (d) initial solution with 6 duty-cycles ($D = 6$), where the first two duty-cycles are in the same position as those of the initial set of Approach 3, and the other four are distributed in the last energy tariff of the total time horizon.

Table 3.1: Results of each optimization approach for the single pump-tank network.

KPI/Approach	1	2	3	4
Number of duty-cycles available	5	5	6	6
Number of duty-cycles in use	5	5	4	4
Pump starts	4	2	2	4
Total cost (€)	108.91	109.15	109	108.94

the operations resulting from Approaches 2 and 3 are notably similar. Approach 1 is the most cost-effective by exploring the network characteristics, where pumping at lower levels results in lower costs. A common strategy across all solutions is the preference to pump early in the day to benefit from lower energy tariffs.

However, only Approaches 1 and 4 effectively leverage the tank level at the end of the day to minimize operating costs. These approaches advantage derives from their initial solution of having more duty-cycles defined in the last energy tariff compared to Approaches 2 and 3, which have only one duty-cycle after midday. Despite Approach 3 having an additional available duty-cycle compared to Approach 1, which theoretically should produce better results, it does not outperform the others due to its initial solution. By changing the initial solution, keeping the $D=6$ (Approach 4), the optimization model reveals distinct differences in the decision variables and the pumping operation, achieving a cost reduction through the successful use of the tank level. These results highlight the optimization model sensitivity to the initial solution set, a significant limitation to overcome in the proposed framework.

3.2 Model scalability analysis

Within optimization modeling, scalability is defined by the model capacity to handle an increase in the problem size by adding decision variables or constraints. Evaluating scalability is essential to confirm the model applicability to more complex scenarios and ensure that increases in problem complexity do not adversely affect its performance.

The simple pump-tank WSS characterized in the previous chapter was implemented, and the same algorithm (SLSQP) was used to solve the optimization model. This scalability analysis consisted of testing several number of duty-cycles within the $D \in \{2, 10\}$ interval. This adjustment affects the number of decision variables as well as the total number of constraints since each constraint number of evaluation points is directly related to the number of duty-cycles.

Considering the conclusions from previous analyses regarding the model sensitivity to initial solution and the relation between operating costs and the water tank levels, the initial solution was strategically defined for each D value, focusing on prioritizing duty-cycles towards the day's end. Figure 3.9 shows the pump operation solutions across each D value.

Across all solutions illustrated in Figure 3.9a, a constant pattern is observed in the pump operation during the first half of the day. In every solution, the pump operates for an identical duration, mainly due to the lower energy tariffs in the early hours. The minor differences among these solutions, which affect the total cost, occur from using the

Figure 3.9: Optimization results with the initial solution strategically defined for each D value ($D \in \{2, 10\}$), focusing on prioritizing duty-cycles towards the day's: (a) pump status and (b) respective costs.

available duty-cycles to optimize the water tank level usage in the latter half of the day. Moreover, Figure 3.9b shows the correlation between the increase in the number of duty-cycles and the consequent cost reduction. For instance, the solution with 9 duty-cycles proved to be 0.06€ less expensive than that with 3 duty-cycles. However, it is important to mention that the solution with $D = 9$ has four additional pump starts compared to the $D = 3$ solution, raising a question about the optimal number of duty-cycles to employ in the problem formulation. This problem is addressed in the next sub-section. In real WSS, this decision is made by the WSS management company.

In summary, the allocation of duty-cycles throughout the total time horizon is influenced by both the energy tariffs and the water tank levels. Nevertheless, the energy tariffs are decisive in achieving an optimal solution. In scenarios where the energy tariff is uniform, such as at night, operating the pump at reduced tank levels contributes to minimizing costs. Additionally, it is important to highlight that for $D > 4$, practically all solutions did not use all the available duty-cycles for end-of-day operation, with the only exception of $D = 7$ solution. This phenomenon suggests that the initial solutions might not have been appropriate, leading to non-optimal solutions.

In a theoretical scenario where this WSS tank is designed to be supplied from above, selecting the D value would be more straightforward, as the advantage of water level over operating cost would disappear. Consequently, the choice would be for the minimal D value meeting all other requirements, i.e. $D = 2$.

3.2.1 KPIs for a global optimum: energy consumption cost vs. maintenance cost

Each water management company faces different operational challenges and priorities, leading to diverse optimization objectives for their pump scheduling strategies. These priorities are shaped by various factors, including geographical location, regulatory requirements, energy costs, infrastructure conditions, and environmental considerations. As a result, companies may focus on different goals, such as minimizing pump energy consumption costs, pump maintenance costs, pump demand charges, and the environ-

mental impact related to the carbon footprint of pump operations. Additionally, they may also prioritize maximizing operational reliability or water quality.

As previously mentioned, energy consumption is one of the largest marginal costs for water utilities, usually making it the primary goal for companies to optimize [10]. It is possible to combine this goal with the others mentioned above. The most common strategy among water management companies involves simultaneously minimizing energy consumption and pump maintenance costs [72–74]. While direct measurement of pump maintenance costs can be challenging, these costs are typically represented using surrogate indicators, such as the frequency of pump starts [10]. This approach not only helps lower operational cost but also extends the lifespan of the equipment.

The challenge for water management companies, particularly those with complex WSS, is to balance these objectives effectively. Optimizing solely for energy costs usually increases the number of pump starts, which could aggravate the maintenance costs. Conversely, focusing on minimizing pump starts might incur higher energy costs. This trade-off highlights the need for strategies that can address both energy consumption and the pumps maintenance.

The previous sub-section analysis demonstrates the duty-cycle formulation capability to balance energy cost reduction with the management of pump starts. By setting the maximum number of duty-cycles, D , the model can indirectly control the frequency of pump starts, influencing both energy costs and maintenance needs. The analysis showed that while increasing D can achieve lower energy costs, the difference may be marginal in some cases, as seen with a difference of only 0.20€ between $D = 2$ and $D = 10$. However, in more complex WSS, this difference could be significant, requiring a strategic approach that considers the trade-off between cheaper options with more frequent pump starts and more expensive options with fewer pump starts. In order to minimize operating costs and extend the life of equipment, water utilities need strategies that provide solutions to address both aspects of this trade-off to ensure that decisions follow their particular operational objectives and limitations. This issue should be addressed in the proposed framework.

3.3 Proposed optimization framework

The previous analysis of the duty-cycle optimization model has highlighted some aspects for improvement, which the proposed framework aims to address. The following points summarize the challenges that need to be overcome:

- Sensitivity to initial solutions: the results of the current model are influenced by the choice of the initial solution, making it challenging to find the best possible outcome.
- Optimization of water tank usage: there is an opportunity to use the water tank levels to optimize costs, ensuring that pump operations are adjusted based on tank conditions to achieve greater cost-efficiency.
- Flexible duty-cycle management: the framework should be able to adjust the number of duty-cycles to meet specific operational needs, balancing energy savings with equipment longevity.

To address the identified problems, the Smart Dynamic Local Search (Smart-DLS) was designed. This new methodology was developed based on the core principle of Variable Neighborhood Search (VNS), which applies local neighborhood search techniques. Originally designed for approximate solutions of combinatorial optimization problems, it was extended to address mixed integer programming, nonlinear programming, and recently mixed integer nonlinear programming [75]. VNS is a metaheuristic approach designed to overcome the limitations of traditional local search methods by systematically varying the neighborhood structures used during the search process [76]. The core idea behind VNS is to combine local search techniques with a shaking mechanism that diversifies the search and prevents the algorithm from getting trapped in local optima [77]. In VNS, the search alternates between a shaking phase, where a random solution from the current neighborhood is chosen, and a local search phase, typically using Variable Neighborhood Descent (VND) heuristic, to explore and refine solutions [78]. This procedure is repeated until the stopping condition is reached. This dual-phase approach allows VNS to explore a broader range of solutions and escape local optima more effectively than methods using fixed neighborhoods [76].

3.3.1 Smart Dynamic Local Search (Smart-DLS)

The Smart-DLS is a hybrid approach specifically designed to improve the performance of a pump scheduling optimization model, particularly in the context of duty-cycle formulation. This approach combines deterministic local search techniques with an intelligent shaking process governed by predefined rules. These rules were formulated based on conclusions drawn from the previous analysis of the existing optimization framework. As shown in Algorithm 1, the Smart-DLS process systematically modifies the solution set according to predefined rules, ensuring that each iteration starts with a new improved initial set.

The initialization phase starts with the definition of the initial solution set \mathbf{S}^* . Examples of initial solution sets include a warm start with a known solution, a uniformly distributed initial solution, or sets of duty-cycles defined based on periods of high consumption, energy tariff centers, or transitions. For the shaking process, it is necessary to define the maximum duration for duty-cycle elimination (Δt^{del}), the minimum time gap for a duty-cycle addition (Δt^{add}), the maximum time gap for duty-cycles merging (Δt^{gap}), and the minimum duration for duty-cycles division (Δt^{div}). The definition of these parameters depends solely on the water utility management strategy and the specific characteristics of its WSS. A key factor to consider is whether the pumps have soft-start and soft-stop mechanisms, as this limits both the minimum duration of each duty-cycle, directly affecting Δt^{del} , and the minimum time interval between two pump starts, which influences Δt^{div} , Δt^{gap} , and Δt^{add} . This guarantees that the methodology remains adaptable to the specific requirements of any water utility. The initialization phase ends with the definition of stopping conditions, determining when the algorithm will stop. It includes the maximum number of iterations, a threshold for the number of iterations without improvement, a tolerance for cost improvement, or a maximum CPU time limit. The stopping conditions ensure that the algorithm concludes once a satisfactory solution is found or computational resources are exhausted. Additionally, users can prioritize KPIs, beyond total cost, to guide the evaluation and selection of solutions. Examples include the number of duty-cycles and duty-cycle durations. Users define the

Algorithm 1 Pseudo-code of Smart Dynamic Local Search (Smart-DLS).

-
- 1: */* Initialization */*
 - 2: **1. Define the initial solution set (\mathbf{S}^{ini})**
 Possible options: warm start with a previously known solution, uniformly distributed initial solution, duty-cycles defined in periods of higher consumption, duty-cycles centered on each energy tariff, and duty-cycles at tariff transitions.
 $\mathbf{S}^* = \mathbf{S}^{\text{ini}}$
 - 3: **2. Define the shaking rules parameters**
 Δt^{del} : Maximum duration for duty-cycle elimination
 Δt^{gap} : Maximum time gap for duty-cycles merging
 Δt^{div} : Minimum duration for duty-cycles division
 Δt^{add} : Minimum time gap for a duty-cycle addition
 - 4: **3. Define the stopping conditions**
 Possible options: Maximum number of Smart-DLS iterations, maximum iterations without improvement, cost improvement tolerance, and maximum CPU time limit.
 - 5: **4. Define the key performance indicators (KPI) priorities**
 KPIs, in addition to the total cost, are used to select or order the solutions in the last phase. Examples of additional KPIs: number of duty-cycles and their durations.
 - 6: */* Main Algorithm Loop */* stopping conditions are not met
 - 7: **5. Perform deterministic local search**
 Use a local search algorithm (SLSQP or COBYLA) to find a local minimum \mathbf{S} , using with \mathbf{S}^* as the initial solution. **any** ($L_{wt}^{\text{min}} - L_{wt}^{\text{end}} > 0.1, \forall wt \in \{0, \dots, WT\}$)
 $\mathbf{S} = \text{SLSQP}(\mathbf{S}^*)$
 $\mathbf{S} = \text{COBYLA}(\mathbf{S}^*)$
 - 8: **6. Analyze the solution**
 Store the current solution \mathbf{S} and compare it with the best-known solution \mathbf{S}^* .
 $\text{ObjF}(\mathbf{S}) < \text{ObjF}(\mathbf{S}^*)$
 Update the best-known solution: $\mathbf{S}^* = \mathbf{S}$
 - 9: **7. Check stopping conditions**
 If the stopping conditions are met, return the cached solutions and skip the shaking process.
 - 10: **8. Apply the shaking process**
 Based on predefined rules, modify \mathbf{S}^* by performing one or more of the following operations:
 - (a) Elimination of small duty-cycles ($\Delta t_{d,p}^{\text{dc}} \leq \Delta t^{\text{del}}$)
 - (b) Merging of duty-cycles with small gaps between them ($st_{(d+1),p}^{\text{dc}} - (st_{d,p}^{\text{dc}} + \Delta t_{d,p}^{\text{dc}}) \leq \Delta t^{\text{gap}}$)
 - (c) Strategic addition of duty-cycles ($st_{(d+1),p}^{\text{dc}} - (st_{d,p}^{\text{dc}} + \Delta t_{d,p}^{\text{dc}}) \geq \Delta t^{\text{add}}$)
 - (d) Division of long duty-cycles within the same energy tariff in the last Smart-DLS iteration ($\Delta t_{d,p}^{\text{dc}} \geq \Delta t^{\text{div}}$)
 - 11: **9. Final solution selection**
 Based on the KPIs, select or rank the final solution(s).
-

relative importance of these KPIs, which are then used to rank and select the final solutions. This approach ensures that decision-makers can explore alternative solutions that may offer operational benefits even at a slightly higher cost.

After the user-defined initialization, the algorithm enters the main iterative loop. During each iteration, a deterministic local search is performed using either the SLSQP or COBYLA (Constrained Optimization By Linear Approximations) algorithm. The choice of SLSQP is due to its good performance observed in previous chapters. However, COBYLA was included as an option since it was found that SLSQP did not perform well when, in the initial solution, the tank's final water tank level (L_{wt}^{end}) was close to its minimum limit (L_{wt}^{min}), i.e., when the initial solution was close to a possible minimum solution. As explained above, the shaking process can produce initial solutions with this characteristic when created from previous solutions. Therefore, in particular cases when constraints are near the feasibility boundary, COBYLA proved to be more robust. The local search can perform effectively across different scenarios by providing the flexibility to choose between these two algorithms. This phase of the local search focuses on exploiting the neighborhood around the current best solution \mathbf{S}^* , refining it to improve the objective function, ensuring that the solution found is a local minimum based on the conditions of the iteration. By implementing local searches, this approach efficiently explores the solution space while keeping computational times practical. As mentioned, in real-world applications, Smart-DLS will leverage warm-start solutions based on previous days' operations, as daily water demand patterns typically exhibit minimal variation. This will further reduce computational time while ensuring that the optimization process dynamically adapts to operational changes.

After finding the new solution \mathbf{S} , the algorithm compares it with the best-known solution \mathbf{S}^* . If the new solution has a lower objective function value, the best-known solution is updated to \mathbf{S} . This guarantees that the best solution found in terms of cost value is preserved throughout the process. Additionally, in each iteration, the resulting solution \mathbf{S} is always stored, allowing the algorithm to evaluate and rank them according to the KPIs prioritized by the user. The algorithm then checks whether the stopping conditions defined by the user are met. If these are, the algorithm stops and returns the best-known and cached solutions. If not, the algorithm proceeds to the smart shaking process.

The smart shaking process modifies the current best solution \mathbf{S}^* according to pre-defined rules rather than random perturbations as in VNS. All shaking operations are cached to avoid repeating the same shaking process in future iterations if a better solution is not found. The shaking process includes the elimination of duty-cycles with short duration ($\Delta t_{d,p}^{\text{dc}} \leq \Delta t^{\text{del}}$), as well as the merging of duty-cycles that have small gaps between them ($\text{gap} \leq \Delta t^{\text{merg}}$). In addition, new duty-cycles can be strategically added when gaps larger than Δt^{add} exist between duty-cycles, on the condition that no duty-cycle with zero duration was previously eliminated in those gaps. Another important operation is the division of long duty-cycles, those with durations greater than Δt^{div} . This operation is reserved for the final iteration, where it plays a key role in taking advantage of the water level to improve the best solution found so far. These shaking operations enable the algorithm to explore different configurations of duty-cycles, helping to escape local optima while maintaining diversity in the solution set. Each iteration applies these operations based on the conditions of the solution, ensuring that the search process remains dynamic and effective. As the solution is "shaken" in each iteration, the

algorithm may either increase or decrease the number of duty-cycles, making the search adaptive and responsive to the problem needs. This dynamic variation in the number of duty-cycles helps the algorithm refine the solution and reduce costs over time. Once the stopping conditions are met, the final solution is selected or ranked based on the user-defined KPIs.

The Smart-DLS framework directly addresses the challenges previously identified in the duty-cycle optimization model. To optimize the use of the water level in storage tanks, the framework implements a strategic addition and division of duty-cycles. By delaying the division to the last iteration, the framework maximizes the cost-saving potential from the water tank at the most opportune moment in the process, where the cost should be the minimum. When there are no duty-cycles long enough to be divided, it indicates that the algorithm has already introduced duty-cycles in previous iterations that successfully account for the water level to optimize the solution. Additionally, the framework introduces flexible duty-cycle management by dynamically adjusting the number of duty-cycles throughout the shaking process. By continuously varying the number of duty-cycles in response to solution improvements, the framework balances the trade-off between cost-efficiency and the wear and tear on pumping equipment, addressing the need for a more adaptable and robust solution to pump scheduling. Finally, the shaking process, along with the multi-start approach, addresses the sensitivity to initial solutions. As shown in Figure 3.10, this technique involves generating multiple initial solutions rather than relying on a single starting point [79], allowing the algorithm to explore a wider portion of the solution space from various entry points. This reduces the risk of the algorithm being trapped in local optima and improves the chances of finding a global optimum. The use of multi-starting has been proven to enhance robustness and solution quality in optimization problems by broadening the search scope [80].

Figure 3.10: Multi-starting approach of Smart-DLS. By exploring the solution space from multiple entry points, this strategy reduces the risk of getting stuck in local minima and increases the chances of finding a global optimum.

3.3.2 Demonstration of the Smart-DLS: single pump-tank network

The outcomes of implementing the Smart-DLS method to the previously mentioned pump-tank network, using $D=5$, are presented in Table 3.2. The cost decreases from iteration to iteration, although the difference in cost is reduced due to the simplicity of the network. Throughout the three iterations, the number of available duty-cycles remained the same. However, in the first iteration, the solution used only four of the five possible pump starts. Figure 3.11 illustrates the shaking process between iterations. From the solution of the first iteration (Figure 3.11a), the shaking mechanism merged the first two duty-cycles and added a new one during the midday gap, resulting in the updated initial solution shown in Figure 3.11b. From this initial solution, a new solution (Figure 3.11c) is achieved that takes advantage of the added duty-cycle to reduce costs by considering the water tank level. The solution is again subjected to a junction of duty-cycles, and a new duty-cycle is added in the new shaking (Figure 3.11d). This added duty-cycle is used once more to optimize the water tank level, resulting in the most cost-effective solution (Figure 3.11e). As explained earlier, the modifications made during the shaking process are cached to prevent repetitions. However, if these modifications yield better cost results, such as in the example where the duty-cycle is added at midday, an exception is made, and the shaking process is repeated.

(a) Solution achieved in the first Smart-DLS iteration.

(b) Output of the shaking process applied to the first solution.

(c) Solution achieved in the second Smart-DLS iteration.

(d) Output of the shaking process applied to the second solution.

(e) Solution achieved in the third Smart-DLS iteration.

Figure 3.11: Example of the shaking process using the single pump-tank network. A maximum of 3 iterations was defined for the stopping criteria of the Smart-DLS.

Regarding the number of objective function evaluations presented in Table 3.2, it is not possible to draw any conclusions from this case study's results, only that the

solution was achieved with a low number of objective function evaluations. However, in the following section, this KPI will be used to validate the application of this new methodology for a real WSS control by comparing its results with those from the water utility.

Table 3.2: Results of the Smart-DLS applied to the single pump-tank network. $\mathbf{X}^{\text{ini}} = [0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 2, 2, 2, 2, 2]$ was used as initial solution, which corresponds to an initial cost of 136.35€, and a maximum of 3 iterations for the stopping criteria.

KPI	Iteration 1 of Smart-DLS	Iteration 2 of Smart-DLS	Iteration 3 of Smart-DLS
Total cost (€)	109.24	108.98	108.9
No. of duty-cycles (1A)	5	5	5
Pump starts (1A)	4	5	5
Objective function evaluations	38	91	86

3.4 Results and validation

The Smart-DLS performance was tested on three case studies, two of which are well-known benchmarks in the literature (VanZyl and AnyTown modified networks) and a complex Portuguese WSS (Ronqueira network). Once again, the hydraulic simulator EPANET was used to simulate the networks behavior, and the optimization framework was run on an 11th-gen Intel(R) CORE(TM) i7-1185G7 CPU @ 3.00 GHz with 16 GB RAM.

The following Smart-DLS settings were applied for each case study: five multi-starts with a stopping condition set to three Smart-DLS iterations. Three multi-starts began with the same number of duty-cycles for each pump ($D = 5$), while the other two started with different values for the duty-cycles ($D = 4$ and $D = 6$). Regarding the shaking parameters, it was defined Δt^{del} as 0.15 h, Δt^{merg} as 0.1 h, Δt^{add} as 3 h, and Δt^{div} as 6 h. During the solution selection phase, the KPIs prioritized were total cost as the primary priority, followed by the number of duty-cycles as the secondary priority. The discussion of each case study's results is conducted in the following sections.

3.4.1 Case study: Van Zyl network

The Van Zyl network [35], previously explained in 2.3.3, was the first network implemented to validate the Smart-DLS performance. Table 3.3 presents the results of the Smart-DLS multi-start algorithm applied to the Van Zyl network. In this case, the second, third, and fourth starts began with the same number of duty-cycles ($D = 5$) but with different initial solutions in order to explore different regions of the solution search space. In all starts, the algorithm reduced costs from iteration 1 to iteration 2, except for the second start, and the reduction from iteration 2 to 3 was unsuccessful. This indicates that the cost optimization through the water tank levels, which occurs in the third/final iteration, was ineffective. The configuration of the Van Zyl network - in particular, the continuity constraint of tank levels near their maximum, the meshed structure of the network (the tanks are gravitationally connected), and the lowest energy tariff occurred

during the last hours of the day - prevents the effective use of water levels to minimize costs in the last iteration. Although reducing costs may not be possible, these iterations are essential for developing solutions requiring fewer pump starts.

A closer examination of the second start reveals that iterations 2 and 3 begin with a different number of duty-cycles, each exploring distinct solution spaces of different sizes. Despite this, both iterations converge to a very similar solution in terms of pumping operations, as shown in Figure 3.12. Both iterations were trapped in a local minimum in

Figure 3.12: Solutions obtained in different shaking processes within the same multi-start for the Van Zyl network. Although the initial solutions started with a different number of duty-cycles, both iterations converged to very similar solutions in terms of pumping operations but with completely different values of the decision variables: (a) iteration 1 and (b) iteration 2 of the Smart-DLS second start.

terms of pump operation, although the decision variables' values differed, highlighting the issue of multiple minimum local solutions. In the fourth start, iterations 2 and 3 arrived at

solutions with the same number of pump starts and identical costs but produced different pumping operations. Finally, an additional behavior was also observed in iterations 1 and 2 of the third start and in iterations 3 of the third and fifth start, where the same number of pump starts led to different operational outcomes and costs.

Table 3.3: Results of each Smart-DLS multi-start for the Van Zyl network.

Multi-start	Cost of \mathbf{X}^{ini} (£)	KPI	Iteration 1 of Smart-DLS	Iteration 2 of Smart-DLS	Iteration 3 of Smart-DLS
1	298.17	Total cost (£)	340.88	338.25	338.50
		No. of duty-cycles (1A/2B/3B)	4/4/4	4/5/4	4/4/3
		Pump starts (1A/2B/3B)	2/3/2	3/3/3	4/4/3
		Objective function evaluations	349	2212	3027
2	379.82	Total cost (£)	329.17	336.72	336.74
		No. of duty-cycles (1A/2B/3B)	5/5/5	4/5/2	3/3/1
		Pump starts (1A/2B/3B)	3/4/1	2/2/1	2/2/1
		Objective function evaluations	3771	124	324
3	234.85	Total cost (£)	340.69	337.93	346.33
		No. of duty-cycles (1A/2B/3B)	5/5/5	4/4/2	3/3/1
		Pump starts (1A/2B/3B)	2/2/1	2/2/1	3/3/1
		Objective function evaluations	811	226	19
4	445.93	Total cost (£)	351.32	336.37	336.38
		No. of duty-cycles (1A/2B/3B)	5/5/5	6/6/4	5/5/3
		Pump starts (1A/2B/3B)	4/3/3	3/2/2	3/2/2
		Objective function evaluations	197	1664	1372
5	350.93	Total cost (£)	335.45	334.27	338.71
		No. of duty-cycles (1A/2B/3B)	6/6/6	5/5/4	6/6/3
		Pump starts (1A/2B/3B)	3/3/2	4/3/3	3/3/1
		Objective function evaluations	1542	852	1839

This initial analysis once again demonstrates that different initial solutions can lead to significantly different results, validating the importance of the multi-start application. Although this initial test used a limited number of pump starts, increasing this value would increase the chances of finding the global optimal solution. In real-world applications, one advantage is that one of the initial solutions is often the previous day's pumping schedule, which generally serves as a strong starting point and reduces the sensitivity to initial conditions. In the Van Zyl case study, however, there was no pre-existing solution to serve as an initial solution, eliminating this potential advantage.

Additionally, to study different solution spaces, two more starts were conducted with different initial numbers of duty-cycles. The fifth start begins with the highest configuration (6/6/6) for duty-cycles, which should provide more scheduling flexibility. As mentioned before, the configuration of the Van Zyl network prevents the effective use of water levels to minimize costs. Consequently, increasing the number of duty-cycles does not result in further cost reductions, making a higher number of duty-cycles unnecessary in this context. Therefore, increasing the scheduling flexibility does not necessarily equate to reduced operational costs as it depends on the network configuration.

When reviewing the results, both the best solution in terms of cost and number of pump starts come from the third start, both highlighted in green in Table 3.3. Figure 3.13 illustrates the pump operation and the evolution of the water tank level for each

solution selected. The lowest cost obtained was 329.17£, matching the solution found in the previous chapter, while the solution with the lowest number of pump starts has five starts (2/2/1). The decision variables of both solutions can be consulted in Table A.2 (Appendix A.2).

Figure 3.13: Smart-DLS results for the Van Zyl network considering as priority KPI: (a) total cost and (b) number of pump starts. To analyze the chart, consider that the Van Zyl case study defines the starting time of the optimization process at 07:00; therefore, the 00:00 time simulation in the chart corresponds to 07:00.

Table 3.4 presents the outcomes of prior studies conducted on the Van Zyl test network. Only studies whose results were classified as technically feasible and could be successfully replicated were considered for the quantitative comparison. As mentioned in the last chapter, there are optimization methodologies proposed in the literature for the same network that achieved a lower operational cost. However, it is crucial to note that these studies operated under conditions distinct from those in this study (e.g. different initial water tank levels), so the results are not comparable. Compared with results from

Table 3.4: Comparison of Van Zyl network optimization results.

Reference	Optimization methodology	Pump starts (1A/2B/3B)	Objective function evaluations	Total cost (£)
Van Zyl et al. [35]	Hydraulic simulator: EPANET Opt. algorithm: Hybrid GA Opt. model formulation: RFTL	\sum pump starts = 5 (2/2/1)	6000	344.43 (+4.64%)
Lopez-Ibanez et al. [66]	Hydraulic simulator: EPANET Opt. algorithm: ACO Meta-heuristic Opt. model formulation: Binary	\sum pump starts = 9 (3/3/3)	6000	333.09 (+1.19%)
Marini et al. [55]	Hydraulic simulator: EPANET Opt. algorithm: Pikaia GA Opt. model formulation: Binary	\sum pump starts = 7 (1/3/3)	-	341.09 (+3.62%)
Previous chapter results	Hydraulic simulator: EPANET Opt. algorithm: SLSQP Opt. model formulation: Duty-cycles	\sum pump starts = 8 (3/4/1)	3771	329.17
Smart-DLS approach (KPI: best cost)	Hydraulic simulator: EPANET Opt. algorithm: SLSQP Opt. model formulation: Duty-cycles	\sum pump starts = 8 (3/4/1)	4219	329.17
Smart-DLS approach (KPI: pump starts)	Hydraulic simulator: EPANET Opt. algorithm: SLSQP Opt. model formulation: Duty-cycles	\sum pump starts = 5 (2/2/1)	4219	336.72 (+2.29%)

the literature, the Smart-DLS solution remains the lowest-cost solution reported so far, with an improvement that could achieve 4.64% when compared with [35] results. A more in-depth analysis of the results in terms of cost is not carried out, as these have already been analyzed in the previous chapter. Additionally, when considering the solution with the lowest number of pump starts, only one solution from the literature achieved the same number of pump starts, but with a higher cost. Therefore, the solutions achieved by the Smart-DLS are not only cost-effective but also optimal in terms of operational efficiency compared to the ones present in the literature. However, it is important to mention that although the results are promising, this case study does not validate the performance of Smart-DLS since it reached at the same solution as the last chapter approach. This is justified since, similar to the Smart-DLS second start, it was chosen a good initial solution in the previous study that achieved the global minimum with just one optimization iteration. In addition, the Smart-DLS achieved the lowest objective function evaluation, except for the previously mentioned work. Since a single simulation of the Van Zyl network takes 0.1 seconds, the total optimization time of this approach was about 7 minutes, which is reasonable for real-time applications.

Figure 3.14 presents the results of a multi-objective analysis that includes a penalty based on the cost per pump start added to the energy consumption cost of each solution. Regardless of the penalty value, the solutions produced by Smart-DLS remain the most economically advantageous compared to the results in the literature. When the penalty exceeds 3£ per pump start, the Smart-DLS solution with fewer pump starts becomes more advantageous than the solution chosen based on the best cost KPI. This highlights the importance of offering both solutions to the user.

Figure 3.14: Multi-objective analysis of the Van Zyl network optimization results considering different weights for the number of pump starts.

3.4.2 Case study: AnyTown modified network

The AnyTown network was initially proposed by Walski et al. [81] and afterwards modified by Rao and Alvarruiz [82] in order to make the optimization step more challenging. This well-established benchmark in the literature comprises 44 pipes and 25 nodes. It includes a water source located at node 10, three identical fixed-speed pumps in parallel (b1, b2, and b3), and three storage tanks at nodes 65, 165, and 265. Each node follows the same base demand pattern, scaled by its respective demand multiplier. The storage tanks operate within the same minimum and maximum levels, ranging from 66.53 m to 71.53 m. Figure 3.15 presents the network schematic, while Table 3.5 resumes the energy tariffs. Additional information about the system characteristics can be found in the original papers [81, 82].

Figure 3.15: AnyTown modified network [82], a modified version of the original network [81], designed to increase the complexity of the optimization process.

Table 3.5: Energy tariffs of the AnyTown modified network.

Time interval (h)	Cost (€/kWh)
[0,7[0.1814
[7,17[0.3528
[17,21[0.8097
[21,24[0.1814

Table 3.6 presents the results of the Smart-DLS approach applied to the AnyTown modified network. In this case, the shaking mechanism between iterations played a more effective role in improving the solution compared to the previous case study, as the cost consistently decreased from one iteration to the next, except for the one shake in the first, third, and fifth starts. Consequently, in all five starts, the initial iterations' costs are improved in one of the subsequent iterations.

Table 3.6: Results of each Smart-DLS multi-start for the AnyTown modified network.

Multi-start	Cost of \mathbf{X}_{ini} (€)	KPI	Iteration 1 of Smart-DLS	Iteration 2 of Smart-DLS	Iteration 3 of Smart-DLS
1	5017.56	Total cost (€)	3470.27	3488.43	3451.88
		No. of duty-cycles (b1/b2/b3)	4/4/4	4/6/7	2/6/7
		Pump starts (b1/b2/b3)	2/4/4	3/5/4	2/5/4
		Objective function evaluations	305	227	436
2	5649.21	Total cost (€)	3542.07	3488.03	3461.66
		No. of duty-cycles (b1/b2/b3)	5/5/5	6/6/7	9/5/6
		Pump starts (b1/b2/b3)	4/4/5	6/4/4	7/4/5
		Objective function evaluations	232	167	259
3	5222.19	Total cost (€)	3468.78	3416.18	3461.55
		No. of duty-cycles (b1/b2/b3)	5/5/5	6/6/6	7/8/8
		Pump starts (b1/b2/b3)	4/5/4	6/5/6	5/4/4
		Objective function evaluations	135	1592	327
4	3896.12	Total cost (€)	3528.28	3487.58	3458.51
		No. of duty-cycles (b1/b2/b3)	5/5/5	6/6/7	4/6/7
		Pump starts (b1/b2/b3)	5/5/5	2/3/5	4/6/5
		Objective function evaluations	232	369	367
5	4663.14	Total cost (€)	3452.09	3462.26	3445.17
		No. of duty-cycles (b1/b2/b3)	6/6/6	5/6/8	6/6/8
		Pump starts (b1/b2/b3)	3/4/5	5/4/5	4/5/7
		Objective function evaluations	466	536	640

Among the 15 solutions obtained by Smart-DLS, only 3 have a slightly higher total cost than the best solution found in the literature, which is 3575.74€ [83]. The increasing number of available duty-cycles from iteration to iteration can be observed, and as previously concluded in Section 3.2, the results confirm that a higher number of duty-cycles typically leads to lower costs. Similar to the previous benchmark, there are iterations, such as iteration 2 of the second and fourth starts, where they started with the same number of duty-cycles and converged to operations with identical costs but different numbers of pump starts and operations. From Table 3.6, the chosen solution in

terms of cost has 3416.18€, while the solution with the most balanced number of pump starts has a total of ten starts (2/4/4). Both selected solutions are illustrated in Figure 3.16, and its decision variables can be consulted in Table A.3 (Appendix A.2).

Figure 3.16: Smart-DLS results for the AnyTown modified network considering as priority KPI: (a) total cost and (b) number of pump starts.

Table 3.7 presents the results of previous studies on the AnyTown modified network. As in the previous benchmark, only studies whose results were classified as technically feasible and successfully replicated were included in the quantitative comparison. Optimization methods proposed in the literature for the same network [48, 64, 65] that achieved lower operating costs were not considered as those studies were conducted under conditions different from those in this study, e.g. different initial water tank levels.

Table 3.7: Comparison of AnyTown modified network optimization results.

Reference	Optimization methodology	Pump starts (1A/2B/3B)	Objective function evaluations	Total cost (€)
Rao and Salomons [84]	Hydraulic simulator: Artificial Neural Network Opt. algorithm: Genetic Algorithm Formulation: Binary	\sum pump starts = 10	10000 (population of 5 and 2000 iterations)	3612.84 (+5.76%)
Costa et al. [45]	Hydraulic simulator: EPANET Opt. algorithm: Branch and Bound Formulation: Binary	\sum pump starts = 8 (3/3/2)	292731236	3578.66 (+4.76%)
Cimorelli et al. [83]	Hydraulic simulator: EPANET Opt. algorithm: Genetic Algorithm Opt. model formulation: Binary	\sum pump starts = 11 (4/4/3)	200000 (population of 200 and 1000 iterations)	3575.54 (+4.66%)
Smart-DLS approach (KPI: best cost)	Hydraulic simulator: EPANET Opt. algorithm: SLSQP Opt. model formulation: Duty-cycles	\sum pump starts = 17 (6/5/6)	2054	3416.18
Smart-DLS approach (KPI: pump starts)	Hydraulic simulator: EPANET Opt. algorithm: SLSQP Opt. model formulation: Duty-cycles	\sum pump starts = 10 (2/4/4)	968	3470.27 (+1.58%)

A more recent study [85] reported a total cost of 2511.47€. However, upon examining the water tank levels, it is verified that all three tank levels remain constant at their maximum value for several hours. This would only be feasible if there were periods with no consumption, which is not the case in this study, as there is continuous consumption throughout the day. As concluded in the previous chapter, the explanation for these hours at maximum level is related to a characteristic of the EPANET 2.0 hydraulic simulator, which disconnects the supply pipe from the tank once it reaches full capacity. As a result, the simulator does not accurately replicate the real operation of the hydraulic network since it prevents the tank from overflowing. If the maximum tank levels were increased in the EPANET file and the same solution was simulated again, the maximum levels of the tanks would most likely not be respected. Since the pump operation data from this article is not available, it is impossible to verify this behavior directly. Therefore, given the previous explanation, its results were not considered.

When comparing the results of the AnyTown modified network obtained from Smart-DLS with those from the literature, it is clear that the Smart-DLS approach delivers superior performance in terms of cost, achieving an improvement of 159.36€ (-4.66%) when compared to the best solution presented in the literature so far. However, as stated previously, achieving such cost reductions involved more pump starts than all the results found in the literature. This trade-off between minimizing operational costs and increasing the number of pump starts reflects the challenge of balancing energy efficiency with maintenance costs and operational wear, underscoring the complexity of optimizing pump scheduling. Regarding the number of starts, only one solution from the literature has a smaller number of pump starts, with the difference of only two. However, it is worth remembering that this solution cost is higher, and a higher number

of multi-starts would most likely improve these results. Once again, the Smart-DLS achieved significantly superior results in the objective function evaluations compared to the literature methods. Considering that a single simulation of the AnyTown modified network takes 0.15 seconds to complete, the total optimization time for this approach was approximately 5.14 minutes, demonstrating its applicability in real-time control of WSS.

Similar to the previous case study, a multi-objective analysis was conducted, and its results are presented in Figure 3.17. Imposing a penalty of 11€ for each pump start makes implementing the Smart-DLS solution with fewer pump starts more economically viable. As previously mentioned, while the Smart-DLS methodology identified the lowest-cost solutions, the approach proposed by Costa et al. [45] has the fewest pump starts. For this solution to be economically beneficial, it would be necessary to consider a pump start cost of at least 55€, a high penalty value.

Figure 3.17: Multi-objective analysis of the AnyTown modified network optimization results considering different weights for the number of pump starts.

3.4.3 Real WSS: Ronqueira network

The Ronqueira network is a real-world WSS operated by the Portuguese water utility Águas do Centro Litoral (AdCL). As illustrated in the network schematic of Figure 3.18, this network supplies water to eight localities.

Figure 3.18: Ronqueira network, a real Portuguese network.

The system consists of one water source, six fixed-speed pumps (p_Al1, p_Al2, p_Av, p_SPD, p_Trav, p_OC), six tanks (t_Al, t_Av, t_SPD, t_Trav, t_OC, t_Esp), and one valve (v_Esp). The valve operates automatically based on the water level in tank t_Esp, opening when the level reaches 2.21 m and closing at 2.69 m. To evaluate the Smart-DLS algorithm performance, the pump operation optimization was conducted on February 20, 2024. The water demand of each consumption point is shown in Figure A.1 of Appendix A.2, and the costs of the eight energy tariffs are detailed in Table 3.8.

Table 3.8: Energy tariffs of the Ronqueira network on February 20th of 2024.

Time interval (h)	Cost (€/kWh)
[0,2[0.09571
[2,6[0.1003
[6,7[0.0957
[7,9.5[0.1139
[9.5,12[0.1804
[12,18.5[0.1139
[18.5,21[0.1804
[21,24[0.1139

Table 3.9 shows the results of the Smart-DLS multi-start algorithm applied to the Ronqueira network. The shaking mechanism reduced the costs in all the multi-starts iterations, except for the iteration 2 of the third start. In all starts, no solution exhibited repeated decision variables or pump operations. However, similar costs were obtained across different iterations, as seen between iteration 1 of the first start and iteration 2 of the fourth start.

Table 3.9: Results of each Smart-DLS multi-start for the Ronqueira network.

Multi-start	Cost of \mathbf{x}^{ini} (€)	KPI	Iteration 1 of Smart-DLS	Iteration 2 of Smart-DLS	Iteration 3 of Smart-DLS
1	660.44	Total cost (€)	485.53	485.16	484.10
		No. of duty-cycles (p_Al1/p_Al2/p_Av/p_Trav/p_OC/p_SPD)	(4/4/4/4/4/4)	(6/6/6/5/6/5)	(5/6/6/4/6/5)
		Pump starts (p_Al1/p_Al2/p_Av/p_Trav/p_OC/p_SPD)	(4/4/4/3/3/3)	(3/4/4/4/3/3)	(3/3/3/2/3/3)
		Objective function evaluations	409	565	639
2	544.74	Total cost (€)	490.57	488.93	485.09
		No. of duty-cycles (p_Al1/p_Al2/p_Av/p_Trav/p_OC/p_SPD)	(5/5/5/5/5/5)	(4/7/6/4/7/6)	(6/6/6/5/6/6)
		Pump starts (p_Al1/p_Al2/p_Av/p_Trav/p_OC/p_SPD)	(2/5/4/3/4/4)	(4/4/4/3/4/4)	(5/3/4/2/4/4)
		Objective function evaluations	502	213	364
3	515.15	Total cost (€)	486.67	487.16	485.98
		No. of duty-cycles (p_Al1/p_Al2/p_Av/p_Trav/p_OC/p_SPD)	(5/5/5/5/5/5)	(4/6/6/6/6/4)	(3/6/5/5/6/3)
		Pump starts (p_Al1/p_Al2/p_Av/p_Trav/p_OC/p_SPD)	(4/2/4/2/4/4)	(4/2/5/2/4/5)	(4/2/4/2/5/4)
		Objective function evaluations	816	740	280
4	806.21	Total cost (€)	486.90	485.50	484.78
		No. of duty-cycles (p_Al1/p_Al2/p_Av/p_Trav/p_OC/p_SPD)	(5/5/5/5/5/5)	(4/6/5/6/6/6)	(4/5/5/6/5/5)
		Pump starts (p_Al1/p_Al2/p_Av/p_Trav/p_OC/p_SPD)	(2/4/3/4/4/3)	(2/3/3/3/4/3)	(2/4/3/3/5/3)
		Objective function evaluations	384	346	252
5	701.95	Total Cost (€)	487.42	484.62	482.67
		No. of duty-cycles (p_Al1/p_Al2/p_Av/p_Trav/p_OC/p_SPD)	(6/6/6/6/6/6)	(6/7/5/8/9/4)	(5/8/5/4/9/4)
		Pump starts (p_Al1/p_Al2/p_Av/p_Trav/p_OC/p_SPD)	(4/2/3/5/6/3)	(3/5/3/1/7/3)	(5/4/3/2/6/3)
		Objective function evaluations	450	360	649

The structure of the Ronqueira network can easily be divided into four sub-networks (Travanca, Outeiro Castro-Entroncamento, São Pedro Dias-Casais, and Albarqueira-

Aveira-Espinheira), and this structural characteristic increases the probability of obtaining similar operational solutions for individual pumps. Therefore, some solutions revealed identical pump operations for the same sub-network, while the operations for the other pumps varied between solutions. For example, the SPD pump shows identical operational characteristics in iterations 1 and 2 of the second start. This observation presents a future opportunity to evaluate each sub-network's cost performance independently and then combine the optimal solutions from different sub-networks into a comprehensive, cost-effective operational strategy.

When comparing the 15 solutions achieved by the Smart-DLS with the company's solution of 498.25€, shown in Table 3.10, it is evident that all 15 solutions are more cost-effective. According to Table 3.9, the Smart-DLS most economical solution costs 484.10€, while the solution with the fewest pump starts has 17 starts (3/3/3/2/3/3). Both solutions are highlighted in green in Table 3.9 and illustrated in Figure 3.19. The decision variables of both solutions can be consulted in the Table A.4 (Appendix A.2).

To evaluate the quality of the solutions, both Smart-DLS solutions are compared with the actual operational strategy implemented by the water utility, illustrated in Figure 3.20. The water utility currently collaborates with Scubic [86], a start-up that provides smart solutions for water resource management. Its current methodology is based on the real-continuous explicit formulation, described in Chapter 2, and solved using the SLSQP algorithm. Upon analyzing Figure 3.20, it is clear that the level constraints for the t_{Av} , t_{SPD} , and t_{OC} tanks are not satisfied in the Scubic solution. This is explained by the need to find a quick solution while managing the network in real-time. Besides, security thresholds for the minimum and maximum operational water tank levels to address overload and underload water events are set by the water utility. The results in Table 3.10 prove that the Smart-DLS approach solution outperforms the Scubic solution regarding the total operational cost, which is more than 3% lower than the Scubic solution, and the number of pump starts, one less than the Scubic solution.

Figure 3.19: Smart-DLS results for the Ronqueira network considering as priority the total cost (a and b), and the number of pump starts (c and d). Pump operation and water tank levels of the left and right sides of the network.

Regarding objective function evaluations and considering the Smart-DLS methodology, it was anticipated that the proposed methodology would require more evaluations than the Scubic methodology, which is evidenced by the Table 3.10 results. However, it is crucial to note that the number of evaluations obtained is not excessive compared to other methodologies' results found in the literature, as demonstrated in the previous case studies, and does not compromise its implementation in real WSS. Additionally, given that a single simulation of the Ronqueira network takes 0.2 seconds to complete, the total optimization time for this approach was approximately 4.86 minutes, an acceptable value for real-time applications.

Table 3.10: Comparison of the Smart-DLS results with those of the Scubic company for the optimization of the Ronqueira network.

Reference	Optimization methodology	Pump starts (p_A1b1/p_A1b2/p_Av/p_Trav/p_OC/p_SPD)	Objective function evaluations	Total cost (€)
Scubic - Smart Software Solutions [86]	Hydraulic simulator: EPANET Opt. algorithm: SLSQP Formulation: Real-Continuous	\sum pump starts = 18 (4/1/3/3/4/3)	744	498.35 (+3.25%)
Smart-DLC approach (KPI: best cost)	Hydraulic simulator: EPANET Opt. algorithm: SLSQP Opt. model formulation: Duty-cycles	\sum pump starts = 23 (5/4/3/2/6/3)	1459	482.67
Smart-DLC approach (KPI: pump starts)	Hydraulic simulator: EPANET Opt. algorithm: SLSQP Opt. model formulation: Duty-cycles	\sum pump starts = 17 (3/3/3/2/3/3)	1313	484.10 (+0.3%)

Figure 3.20: Solution proposed by Scubic [86] for the day in analysis regarding the (a) left and (b) right sides of the Ronqueira network.

Consistent with previous case studies, a multi-objective analysis was performed (Figure 3.21). Given the minimal cost difference between the two Smart-DLS solutions, the solution with the fewest pump starts proves to be more economically advantageous than the option with the best cost KPI, regardless of the penalty considered. This reinforces the importance of presenting both solutions to users. Regardless of the value of the penalty, the Smart-DLS solution with the fewest pump starts will always be the superior option since it achieves lower costs and fewer starts than the water utility solution.

Figure 3.21: Multi-objective analysis of the Ronqueira network optimization results considering different weights for the number of pump starts.

3.5 Final remarks

This chapter provided an in-depth analysis of the duty-cycle formulation, which in the previous chapter had emerged as the most promising explicit approach for pump scheduling optimization. While the DC-SLSQP achieved the most cost-effective results, the analyses revealed important limitations, including sensitivity to initial solutions, the ex-

istence of multiple near-optimal solutions, and scalability concerns in larger networks. These findings highlighted the need for a more robust framework before the methodology could be confidently applied to real-world WSS.

To address these challenges, the Smart Dynamic Local Search (Smart-DLS) framework was proposed and systematically evaluated. By combining deterministic local search with a smart shaking process and a multi-start strategy, Smart-DLS proved capable of overcoming local minima, reducing sensitivity to initialization, and flexibly balancing energy costs with pump maintenance considerations. Its application to two benchmark networks and to the real-world Ronqueira WSS demonstrated consistent improvements over existing methods, confirming both its practical value and scalability.

Overall, the contributions of this chapter lie in (i) clarifying the limitations of the duty-cycle formulation under gradient-based optimization, (ii) proposing a novel hybrid heuristic framework that directly addresses these limitations, and (iii) validating its performance through diverse case studies, including a real WSS. These results establish Smart-DLS as a solid foundation for the subsequent developments of this thesis, where its integration into a decision support system for daily water utility operations is explored.

4 | Smart-DLS as the model management of a decision support system*

This chapter explores the integration of the Smart-DLS optimization methodology into a decision support system for pump scheduling in WSS. While the previous chapter addresses the methodological limitations of the duty-cycle optimization model and proposes the Smart-DLS as a solution, this chapter shifts the perspective toward practical implementation, evaluating how this optimization approach can effectively support water utility operators in daily decision-making.

The chapter is organized as follows. Section 4.1 presents a systematic literature review on DSS applied to pump scheduling, highlighting the scarcity of classical DSS in the water sector and the predominance of automated or optimization-only frameworks. Section 4.2 introduces the proposed framework, where Smart-DLS is formalized as the model management block of a complete DSS architecture complemented by data, knowledge, and user interface modules. Section 4.3 validates the applicability of the framework through two real-world networks. First, the Ronqueira WSS, operating with FSP, is used to demonstrate the methodology under simpler physical conditions and compare it against the current operational strategy adopted by the water utility. Second, the Portuguese Reference WSS (PRWSS), equipped with VSP, provides a more complex environment to test the scalability and flexibility of the approach. In addition, Section 4.4 suggests a control method designed to handle discrepancies between real and forecasted water consumption, which often compromise the performance of optimal schedules in practice. Finally, Section 4.5 concludes the chapter with some closing remarks.

*This chapter is based on the following submitted works:

M. Brás, M. Garuço, A. Moura, A. Andrade-Campos, “A decision support system for pump scheduling in water supply systems based on smart dynamic local search”, *Expert Systems with Applications*, 2025 (submitted for publication).

M. Brás, A. Moura, A. Andrade-Campos, “A hybrid optimization approach for a continuous and efficient pump operation scheduling in water supply systems,” in *Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Control, Decision and Information Technologies*, IEEE, July, 2025. DOI: 10.1109/CoDIT66093.2025.11321341

4.1 Decision support systems for pump scheduling optimization

As previously mentioned, the increasing complexity of WSS and their operational challenges have driven significant research into optimization strategies and decision support systems. Within the scope of the pump scheduling problem, numerous approaches have been proposed to reduce energy costs, improve operational efficiency, and ensure system reliability. However, the effective integration of optimization models into true DSS remains limited.

A DSS is traditionally defined as a computer-based tool intended to assist human decision-makers in addressing semi-structured or unstructured problems. Its primary objective is to support the decision-making process by offering interpretable results, scenario comparisons, and transparency, without automatically executing control actions [87]. According to Sprague [88] and further expanded by Shim et al. [87], a classical DSS is composed of three core components: (1) the data management module, which is responsible for collecting, storing, and preparing input data from various sources (e.g., real-time sensors, historical databases, forecasts); (2) the model management module, which includes optimization, simulation, or analytical models that generate feasible alternatives or scenarios; and (3) the user interface module, which facilitates interaction between the decision-maker and the system by displaying results and collecting preferences or inputs. More recent DSS frameworks also include a knowledge management layer, which stores past decisions, operator feedback, and domain-specific rules to support learning and adaptation over time [89].

In the WSS domain, particularly with regard to pump scheduling, this distinction is crucial. Despite offering no interaction, alternatives, or user interpretability, many published studies refer to optimization-based or automated control frameworks as "decision support systems". Such systems typically operate within closed-loop frameworks, executing actions autonomously and excluding human input entirely. This conceptual ambiguity has led to the term DSS being overgeneralized, and partly explains why so few studies qualify as true decision support systems under a rigorous definition.

To characterize the current state of the art, a systematic literature review was conducted focusing on peer-reviewed articles published between 2020 and 2025, available in the Scopus database [90]. The period 2020–2025 was selected to ensure the review reflects the most recent and relevant developments in the field. The Scopus database was chosen due to its broad multidisciplinary coverage, inclusion of peer-reviewed, high-quality publications, and established tools that support the rigor and reproducibility of a systematic review. The overall methodology implemented for the systematic review is illustrated in Figure 4.1, which summarizes the identification, selection, and inclusion processes applied throughout the analysis.

Initially, a search was performed using Query A, explicitly targeting decision support systems in the domain of pump operation in WSS. However, this query returned only 6 articles, reflecting the limited explicit use of DSS terminology in this field. To broaden the scope and capture additional relevant studies that might support decision-making without using DSS-related terminology directly, a complementary search (Query B) was carried out. This second query focused on optimization and control frameworks with potential decision support value. Together, these queries yielded a total of 270 articles (18 from Query A and 252 from Query B). After applying filters based on the publication

year, title, abstract, open-access availability, and removing duplicates, 44 unique articles were selected for in-depth analysis.

Figure 4.1: Methodology applied for the article selection of the systematic literature review on decision support systems.

Each selected article was analyzed in terms of the optimization approach employed, the case study applied (i.e., whether the method was tested on a real-world WSS or a synthetic network), and its classification within a structured framework reflecting the level of decision support provided. To ensure consistency and replicability, all articles were assigned to one of four predefined categories, presented in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Classification framework used in the literature review.

Classification	Description
Classical DSS (C-DSS)	Fully structured systems composed of a data layer, a model base (e.g., optimization or simulation), and a user interface. They support scenario analysis and operator-led decisions. Execution is not automatic, and the user remains in control.
Decision-Support-Oriented Optimization Framework (DSO)	Optimization-based tools that generate interpretable outputs to assist human decision-making. They are not full DSS: they lack interfaces, system integration, or real-time interaction, but their structure is aligned with decision support.
Optimization Model (OM)	Analytical models developed to solve PSP or related problems. These studies focus on formulation and computational efficiency. Outputs are usually singular and used for performance analysis or benchmarking.
Automated Optimization Controller (AOC)	Systems designed to automatically generate and execute control actions, often in real time. These may rely on optimization, predictive models, or rule-based logic. The key characteristic is autonomy: decisions are applied directly without operator input, interface, or feedback loop.

The results of this classification are summarized in Figure 4.2, which shows the dis-

tribution of articles by category, as well as the optimization model type (mono- vs. multi-objective) and the application context (real-world vs. benchmark). Notably, no articles were classified under Classical DSS, reinforcing the absence of complete decision support systems in this field.

Figure 4.2: Distribution of reviewed articles by classification, highlighting the optimization model type (mono *vs* multi-objective) and type of application (real-world *vs* benchmark). There are no articles classified as C-DSS, as reflected by the absence of data for that category.

The classification of the 44 reviewed articles revealed clear trends. The majority were categorized as Automated Optimization Controllers (AOC, 43%), followed by Optimization Models (OM, 36%), and Decision-Support-Oriented Optimization Frameworks (DSO, 21%). As mentioned, no articles met the criteria for a Classical DSS, highlighting a persistent gap in tools designed explicitly to support, rather than automate, decision-making.

When analyzing the optimization model types, a strong prevalence of mono-objective formulations was observed, especially in the AOC and OM categories. All AOC studies (100%) used mono-objective formulations, primarily focused on operational cost or energy minimization, and designed for automatic control without operator involvement. In contrast, multi-objective optimization appeared predominantly in the DSO group, where 56% of the articles presented formulations that balance competing objectives, typically cost *vs.* water leakage or cost *vs.* water quality, thus supporting human decision-making through trade-off exploration.

Regarding the application context, only a minority of studies were validated on real-world water supply systems. AOC studies had the highest proportion of real implementations (63%), while the majority of DSO and OM approaches were tested on benchmark or synthetic networks (78% and 62%, respectively). This reliance on simplified testbeds may limit the practical deployment of these approaches, particularly for methods not designed for autonomous control.

Overall, the literature presents a wide range of optimization-based solutions for pump scheduling. However, most approaches remain disconnected from actual decision support processes, either due to a lack of interpretability, limited flexibility, or absence of integration with operational environments. The few frameworks classified as DSO represent

promising steps toward human-centered decision support but remain relatively rare and underdeveloped.

4.2 Decision support system based on the Smart Dynamic Local Search

The Smart-DLS approach, presented in the previous chapter, is a hybrid optimization approach for cost-efficient pump scheduling in WSS. It combines deterministic local search techniques with a strategic shaking process and a multi-start approach to overcome key limitations of the duty-cycle optimization model, such as convergence to local minima, inefficient use of water tank levels for cost reduction, and limited ability to adapt the problem size dynamically. At the end of the multi-start process, the algorithm provides a set of top-performing solutions, supporting further analysis or integration into higher-level decision frameworks. Figure 4.3 provides an overview of the Smart-DLS framework.

Figure 4.3: Overview of the Smart-DLS algorithm, a hybrid optimization method combining deterministic local search with intelligent shaking operations and a multi-start strategy. It explores multiple initial solutions to avoid local minima, dynamically adjusts the number and timing of duty-cycles, and identifies cost-efficient schedules for WSS.

4.2.1 Decision support system architecture based on Smart-DLS

To enable practical implementation in operational environments, the Smart-DLS methodology was implemented as the model management component of a decision support system. The proposed architecture, shown in Figure 4.4, integrates real-time data, user preferences, optimization approach, and historical knowledge to provide operators with a flexible and transparent tool for pump scheduling.

Figure 4.4: Architecture of the proposed DSS for pump scheduling. The system integrates SCADA data, water demands and energy tariffs forecasts, user-defined inputs, and EPANET simulations. The Smart-DLS-based Model Management module generates and evaluates pump schedules using the user-defined KPIs, supported by historical data stored in the Knowledge Management module. The User Interface allows configuration and result exploration, while final decisions are made by the decision maker.

The system is structured into five main blocks:

- **Data management:** this component is responsible for collecting and preparing all required input data, including SCADA measurements, water demands and energy tariff forecasts, energy tariff structures, user-defined settings, and the hydraulic simulation model (EPANET input file). It ensures consistent and validated data flow for the optimization process.
- **Model management:** at the core of the system, this block runs the Smart-DLS algorithm using a multi-start approach. The optimizer generates multiple feasible pump schedules, and each solution is evaluated according to user-defined KPIs, and the best candidates are selected for further analysis.
- **Knowledge management:** this module stores historical solutions, operator feedback, and domain-specific operational rules (e.g., tank level thresholds, continuity requirements). It supports long-term learning and allows the DSS to adapt over time to recurring operational patterns and preferences.
- **User interface:** through the interface, operators define optimization settings (e.g., maximum number of duty-cycles, shaking parameters) and select the KPIs that guide solution ranking. The interface also displays results graphically and quantitatively, facilitating direct comparison between alternative pump schedules.
- **Decision maker:** the human operator remains in control of the final decision. After reviewing the DSS-generated alternatives, the operator selects the most suitable solution based on current operational goals. A possible direct feedback loop is established from the Decision Maker to the SCADA system, enabling automatic implementation of the selected schedule in the real water supply system. This ensures that human validation is preserved while allowing for the efficient deployment of optimized pump schedules.

This DSS bridges advanced optimization with practical, operator-driven decision-making, promoting transparency, and adaptability in daily operations. Its modular structure allows future extensions, such as real-time predictive models or automated post-decision validation. Most importantly, it addresses the gap identified in the literature concerning the lack of classical DSS implementations in water supply systems. By combining multi-scenario optimization, human-in-the-loop decision processes, and real-time system integration, the proposed framework represents the original concept of a decision support system, as outlined in Section 4.1.

4.3 Results and validation

The main objective of this chapter is to propose and validate the real-world applicability of the Smart-DLS methodology within a decision support framework. To this end, operational data from two Portuguese WSS, the Ronqueira network and the Portuguese reference water supply system (PRWSS), over five consecutive days were used to evaluate the performance of the proposed approach. Figure 4.5 presents the framework implemented for this validation.

Figure 4.5: Methodology conducted to test the Smart-DLS-based DSS.

The pump scheduling optimization was performed at the beginning of each day for a 24-hour horizon using the forecasted water demands (FWD) provided by Scubic [86]. After each optimization run, the selected solutions were evaluated in the real WSS, simulated in EPANET with real water demands (RWD) retrieved from the SCADA system. At the end of each day, the simulation file for the following day was updated with the real initial water tank levels (L^0) and the corresponding demand forecasts. This cycle was repeated until the fifth day was achieved.

As in the previous chapters, the framework was run on an 11th-gen Intel(R) CORE(TM) i7-1185G7 CPU @ 3.00 GHz with 16 GB RAM.

4.3.1 Real WSS: Ronqueira network

The Ronqueira network, previously described in Section 3.4.3, was optimized over the period from september 25 (wednesday) to september 29 (sunday), 2024. The dataset was chosen to include both weekdays and weekends in order to capture variations in energy tariffs and water demands. The applied energy tariffs are shown in Figure 4.6, while both the forecasted and real water demand patterns for each consumption point are provided in Figure A.2 of Appendix A.3.

Figure 4.6: Energy tariffs of the Ronqueira network from september 25 (wednesday) to 29 (sunday), 2024.

Regarding the Smart-DLS, the following settings were applied: five multi-starts with a stopping condition set to three Smart-DLS iterations. Three multi-starts began with the same number of duty-cycles for each pump ($D = 5$), while the other two started with different values for the duty-cycles ($D = 4$ and $D = 6$). Regarding the shaking parameters, it was defined $\Delta t^{\text{del}} = 0.15$ h, $\Delta t^{\text{merg}} = 0.1$ h, $\Delta t^{\text{add}} = 3$ h, and $\Delta t^{\text{div}} = 6$ h. During the solution selection phase, the KPIs were the total cost and the number of pump starts.

The optimization approach must be adapted for multi-day implementation to maintain continuity across successive days, ensuring water level stability while dynamically adjusting pump schedules in response to daily demand fluctuations. Therefore, a water tank level continuity constraint was incorporated into the mathematical formulation, requiring that the water level at the end of each 24 hours be equal to or greater than the minimum operational level plus an additional 10% of the available storage range. This constraint guarantees a smooth transition between optimization cycles and prevents unplanned overflow of water tanks.

An analysis of the available data revealed that the real initial water tank levels were below the minimum operational limit on certain days. To address this, a modified tank level constraint was implemented: for days when the initial level falls below the operational minimum, the constraint was adjusted until the 12:00, and the required minimum level remains equal to the lowest level recorded in the first half of the day. After the midday, the standard operational minimum level is reinstated as a constraint. This adjustment ensures a gradual recovery of storage levels, preventing excessive pump usage in the early hours while still meeting operational safety requirements.

Table 4.2 shows the results of the Smart-DLS approach alongside the network's real operation for each day. A comparison of the Smart-DLS solutions and the company's operational strategy indicates that Smart-DLS consistently outperforms the existing approach in terms of cost efficiency. The cost savings achieved by Smart-DLS range from 400.46€ (-14%) on the first day to 777.85€ (-25%) on the second day, demonstrating its

effectiveness in optimizing pump scheduling.

In terms of pump starts, Smart-DLS not only reduces costs but also achieves fewer pump starts compared to the company's approach in most cases. The only exception occurs on day 26, where the company's operation recorded one fewer pump starts than Smart-DLS. However, despite this slight increase in pump activations, the Smart-DLS solution still resulted in a significant cost reduction of 766.30€, demonstrating its superior ability to balance operational efficiency and energy cost savings. Conducting additional multi-starts with a lower number of duty-cycles in the initial solution could further enhance the optimization results regarding the number of pump starts.

Obtaining results in a short time is essential when applying an optimization methodology as a decision support system. By examining the number of objective function evaluations in Table 4.2, it becomes evident that Smart-DLS is well-suited for this purpose, as it requires significantly fewer evaluations compared to many optimization methods proposed in the literature [45, 66, 83]. For this case study, given the characteristics of the workstation, an objective function evaluation takes 0.2 seconds. Therefore, the maximum number of iterations recorded was 2559, which would mean a maximum of 8.5 minutes to achieve a solution. This highlights its efficiency and practicality for near-real-time operational decision-making in water supply systems.

Figure 4.7 illustrate the results, showing pump operations and tank levels for each day with respect to total cost (Figures 4.7a and 4.7b) and number of pump starts (Figures 4.7c and 4.7d), respectively. In each case, the upper chart depicts the pump operating schedules, while the three lower charts illustrate the evolution of water tank levels, where the light blue represents real measurements (real), green the optimized values obtained with forecasted demands (opt_fcst), and dark blue the optimized schedules tested with real demands (opt_real).

Table 4.2: Results of the Smart-DLS for each day using the forecasted water demands alongside with the real Ronqueira WSS operation.

	Day	Cost (€)	Pump starts	Objective function evaluations
Real operation		2900.67	21	-
Smart-DLS (best cost)	25/sept	2500.21	28	1619
Smart-DLS (pumps starts)		2515.42	20	
Real operation		3061.73	17	-
Smart-DLS (best cost)	26/sept	2283.88	19	1430
Smart-DLS (pumps starts)		2295.43	18	
Real operation		2752.11	19	-
Smart-DLS (best cost)	27/sept	2249.11	26	2039
Smart-DLS (pumps starts)		2255.23	19	
Real operation		2759.65	16	-
Smart-DLS (best cost)	28/sept	2051.86	23	937
Smart-DLS (pumps starts)		2056.01	16	
Real operation		2688.19	26	-
Smart-DLS (best cost)	29/sept	2220.03	25	2559
Smart-DLS (pumps starts)		2240.27	22	

(a) Solution selection KPI: total cost (Ronqueira network left side).

(b) Solution selection KPI: total cost (Ronqueira network right side).

(c) Solution selection KPI: pump starts (Ronqueira network left side).

(d) Solution selection KPI: pump starts (Ronqueira network right side).

Figure 4.7: Smart-DLS results for the Ronqueira network considering the total cost KPI (a and b) and number of pump starts (c and d).

Analyzing the results, it is possible to observe changes in the minimum water tank level constraint (dotted gray line), which vary according to the initial tank level at the beginning of each day, as previously mentioned. Due to significant discrepancies between forecasted and real water demands on certain days (see Figure A.2), the water tank level constraints were not respected when the optimal solution was tested in the real WSS simulation. For example, at the end of the fourth day (between 72 and 82 hours), the real water demand in Aveleira was considerably higher than the forecasted demand (Figure A.2h). As a result, in all solutions shown in Figure 4.7, the tank level of the optimal solution falls below the minimum threshold at the end of that day. Nevertheless, no tanks experienced underflow.

Since this work does not address the forecasting problem, such violations are not considered in the evaluation of the Smart-DLS performance. Under the optimization conditions (green line) the tank levels were consistently respected. For water utilities still facing this challenge, the Section 4.4 introduces an adaptive control approach designed to mitigate such discrepancies in real time.

Table 4.3 summarizes the results from the 5 day operation optimization. Throughout these five days, Smart-DLS achieved approximately a 20% reduction in operational costs, resulting in savings of 2857.26€. However, this cost-optimal solution required 14 additional pump starts compared to the company’s current operations. Moreover, when the Smart-DLS was selected to minimize pump starts through the KPIs priorities, it still achieved a cost reduction of 2799.99€ while reducing pump starts by 8 compared to the company’s operation. Ultimately, the decision between these solutions would depend on the company’s operational priorities, whether to prioritize cost savings or minimize pump wear. In conclusion, the Smart-DLS offers flexibility by making both options readily available, allowing decision-makers to select the most suitable strategy for each day.

Table 4.3: Results of the Smart-DLS for each day alongside the Ronqueira network real operation.

KPI		Results for 5 days	Variation (%)
Cost (€)	Real operation	14162.35	-
	Smart-DLS (best cost)	11305.09	-20.18 (-2857.26€)
	Smart-DLS (pump starts)	11362.36	-19.77 (-2799.99€)
Pump starts	Real operation	99	-
	Smart-DLS (best cost)	113	+14.14 (+14 pump starts)
	Smart-DLS (pump starts)	91	-8.08 (-8 pump starts)

4.3.2 Real WSS: Portuguese reference water supply system

This WSS, illustrated in Figure 4.8, is managed by a Portuguese water utility and, for confidentiality reasons, will be referred to throughout this chapter as the Portuguese Reference Water Supply System (PRWSS). The network supplies ten localities (Loc1 to Loc10) through a complex system comprising eighteen variable-speed pumps (R0 to R17), four automated valves (v1, v3, v27, and v33), nine water tanks (t0 to t8), and two

water sources.

Figure 4.8: Schematic of the PRWSS with tanks and pumps main characteristics.

For redundancy purposes, several pumps are configured as backups in case of failure, and these are marked in black in Figure 4.8. The figure also provides key operational characteristics of the network components, including water tank level limits and the allowable relative speed ranges of the pumps. Valves v27 and v33 are automatically controlled based on the levels of tanks t4 and t8, while valves v2 and v3 are time-controlled to ensure the daily renewal of water in tank t2. Pump P7 operates as a pumping station (PS) between 04h00 and 07h00, drawing water from tank t2, and as a hydroprocessor (HP) during the remaining hours, supplying water from tank t1. In addition, pump P11 is automatically controlled by the level of tank t7, and pump P9 by the level of tank t4.

In summary, the optimization problem for this network focuses on the operation of seven pumps (P0, P1, P4, P5, P7, P14, and P16), ensuring compliance with the level limits of six tanks (t0, t1, t2, t3, t5, and t6). The energy prices applied to the network during the study period are shown in Figure 4.9.

Figure 4.9: Energy tariffs of the PRWSS network from may 7 (wednesday) to 11 (sunday), 2025.

During preliminary simulations, the previously mentioned SLSQP algorithm imple-

mented in the SciPy library exhibited convergence issues. Although the obtained schedules satisfied most tank-level constraints, including tank t0, which consistently finished close to its lower bound, the level of tank t1 was repeatedly slightly below the minimum limit.

The algorithm had difficulty balancing the water tanks t0 and t1 levels while minimizing costs. Achieving the required level in t1 required the simultaneous operation of pumps P4 and P5 during the peak-demand period at the end of the day, which, in turn, increased the operation of the upstream pumps P0 and P1. These results indicated that the SLSQP was unable to generate a feasible trade-off between cost and water-level feasibility under the more complex dynamics of the PRWSS.

The cause of this behaviour lies in the numerical limitations of the classical SLSQP algorithm. At each iteration, SLSQP linearizes the nonlinear constraints and constructs a quadratic approximation of the Lagrangian using a quasi-Newton BFGS update. The corresponding quadratic subproblem provides a local search direction that is combined with a line-search procedure guided by a merit function. While this approach is computationally efficient for well-conditioned and nearly convex problems, it becomes sensitive in highly constrained, nonconvex domains. In such cases, SLSQP may produce ascending directions or infeasible quadratic subproblems when the linearization of constraints is inconsistent, leading to slight violations of feasibility even when a feasible solution exists.

To overcome these limitations, the local solver within the Smart-DLS framework was replaced by the Improved Sequential Quadratic Programming (I-SQP) algorithm proposed in the literature, by Ma et al. [91], for feasible-path process optimization. The I-SQP enhances the classical SQP method by explicitly preserving feasibility throughout the iterative process. It introduces a feasible-path approach, ensuring that all intermediate iterates remain within or very close to the feasible region. This is achieved through a modified line-search mechanism that dynamically adjusts the step length to prioritize feasibility restoration whenever constraint violations are detected. Furthermore, applying a positive-definite correction to the Hessian approximation (modified BFGS) ensures descent directions and prevents the generation of ascending steps. Additionally, the quadratic subproblem is stabilized by explicitly penalizing infeasibility, which enhances robustness when the linearizations are ill-conditioned.

With the I-SQP successfully implemented within Smart-DLS, the following analysis presents and discusses the results obtained for the PRWSS.

As previously mentioned, the daily pump scheduling optimization was performed at the beginning of each day over a total time horizon of 24 hours, using the forecasted water demands. For the Smart-DLS configuration, four multi-starts were executed, each with a stopping criterion defined as three Smart-DLS iterations. Two of the multi-starts were initialized with the same number of duty-cycles per pump ($D = 8$), except for pump P7, which was assigned $D = 9$. The third multi-start was initialized with $D = 7$ for all pumps, also with P7 set to $D = 7$. Finally, the fourth multi-start used as its initial solution the best cost-efficient schedule obtained from the previous day optimization. Regarding the shaking parameters, the following values were adopted: $\Delta t^{\text{del}} = 0.15$ h, $\Delta t^{\text{merg}} = 0.1$ h, $\Delta t^{\text{add}} = 3$ h, and $\Delta t^{\text{div}} = 6$ h.

In the final stage of the Smart-DLS, three KPIs were used to select the solutions: total energy cost, number of pump starts, and frequency variation (FV). The inclusion of the FV KPI (Hz/s) provides a measure of the smoothness of pump operation, aiming to penalize abrupt speed changes that may induce transient torques, vibrations, and

hydraulic shocks within the pump–motor assembly. Such dynamic effects have been associated with increased mechanical stress and reduced equipment lifespan in variable-speed pumping systems [92, 93]. For this KPI, the frequency variation of pump P7 was not considered, since it necessarily requires a larger frequency transition due to its operational characteristics.

Similarly to the previous case study, Table 4.4 summarizes the main results obtained, while Figures 4.10 and 4.11 illustrate the resulting water tank levels and pump operation schedules, respectively. In Figure 4.10, water tank levels are shown for the solutions obtained under forecasted water demands (opt_fcst) and tested under real water demands (opt_real), allowing a visual assessment of the influence of demand uncertainty on the optimized operation. As in the previous case study, although less frequently, there were days when the initial water tank level was below the minimum operational limit. In these cases, the minimum level constraint for the corresponding tank was adapted to maintain feasibility while preserving realistic operation.

From Table 4.4, it can be observed that the Smart-DLS produced economically efficient daily schedules. Regardless of the KPI used during the solution selection phase, the total energy cost was consistently lower in comparison to the cost of real network operation. The cost savings achieved by the Smart-DLS ranged from 213.26€ (-13%) on the fifth day to 537.29€ (-27%) on the fourth day. The pump operation schedules indicate that the pumps predominantly work close to their minimum allowable frequency and only operate in parallel when strictly necessary, typically during low-tariff periods, such as the early morning hours. This behaviour clearly demonstrates the model capability to explore time-of-use energy pricing while maintaining hydraulic feasibility and operational safety.

Conversely, the solutions selected according to the number of pump starts did not outperform the real operation. This outcome was expected, as the real water tank levels reveal several periods where operational limits were exceeded, mainly due to the reduced number of pump starts and/or longer pumping durations associated. These results emphasize the intrinsic trade-off between energy savings and hydraulic safety when the number of pump starts is overly restricted.

Regarding the maximum frequency variation KPI, all solutions achieved nearly zero variation rates, a substantial improvement when compared with the real operation. Such a solution results in smoother operation and reduced mechanical wear, promoting a more stable, sustainable long-term operation.

When the optimized schedules were simulated under real water demands, a few violations of the operational limits were observed, mainly for tank t5. These discrepancies arise from differences between forecasted and real water demand patterns. Nevertheless, the overall system behaviour remained hydraulically stable, and supply continuity was ensured. The impact of these deviations and a proposed solution are analysed in the next section.

Given the increased complexity and scale of the optimization problem, a higher number of objective function evaluations was expected compared to the previous case study. Considering that each hydraulic simulation required on average 0.35 seconds, the multi-start configuration with the largest number of evaluations required approximately 38 minutes to complete. With more powerful computational resources, this processing time could be significantly reduced. Nevertheless, considering the intended operational use of the framework, for highly complex case studies it may be preferable to increase the

Table 4.4: Results of the Smart-DLS for each day using the forecasted water demands alongside with the PRWSS real operation.

	Day	Cost (€)	Pump starts	FV (Hz/s)	Objective function evaluations
Real operation		2499.83	20	5.11	-
Smart-DLS (best cost)	07/may	1897.38	25	0.01	
Smart-DLS (pumps starts)		1901.14	21	0.03	5752
Smart-DLS (FV)		1898.37	27	0.00	
Real operation		2162.54	16	4.00	-
Smart-DLS (best cost)	08/may	1742.95	22	0.03	
Smart-DLS (pumps starts)		1754.73	19	0.04	3899
Smart-DLS (FV)		1748.09	21	0.01	
Real operation		2366.87	25	11.00	-
Smart-DLS (best cost)	09/may	1829.57	23	0.02	
Smart-DLS (pumps starts)		1834.56	22	0.14	5051
Smart-DLS (FV)		1841.36	26	0.00	
Real operation		2185.44	19	2.00	-
Smart-DLS (best cost)	10/may	1584.21	25	0.43	
Smart-DLS (pumps starts)		1584.21	25	0.43	6171
Smart-DLS (FV)		1592.66	27	0.02	
Real operation		1650.25	16	8.00	-
Smart-DLS (best cost)	11/may	1436.99	14	0.85	
Smart-DLS (pumps starts)		1436.99	14	0.85	6560
Smart-DLS (FV)		1446.41	20	0.00	

number of multi-starts while reducing the number of optimization iterations per multi-start, thereby achieving a balanced trade-off between computational effort and solution quality.

Table 4.5 summarizes the results from the five-day operational optimization. Throughout this period, the Smart-DLS achieved approximately a 22% reduction in the energy cost, corresponding to savings of 2373.81€ when compared to the company’s current operation. However, this solution required 13 additional pump starts relative to the existing schedule. Nonetheless, when the Smart-DLS was configured to prioritize the number of pump starts, the optimized operation still achieved a cost reduction of 2353.29€, only about 20€ higher than the previously mentioned solution, while requiring just five additional starts in total, i.e. one extra pump start per day. This analysis highlights the benefits of the Smart-DLS algorithm. Unlike the initial version of the optimization model, which would have selected only the lowest-cost schedule, the Smart-DLS provides the decision-maker with solutions that better balance cost efficiency and operational sustainability, an essential component in real-world implementation.

Regarding the solutions prioritized by the frequency variation KPI, the Smart-DLS achieved an improvement of nearly 100% compared with the real operation, substantially reducing rapid frequency transitions and, consequently, potential mechanical wear.

Ultimately, the selection among these solutions depends on the company operational priorities, whether to maximize energy cost savings or to minimize pump stress and maintenance demands. The Smart-DLS therefore provides the flexibility to pursue both objectives simultaneously, offering daily decision support tailored to different operational

strategies.

Overall, the Smart-DLS produced coherent and stable operation schedules across all simulated days. This consistency demonstrates the algorithm ability to handle the complexity of large-scale variable-speed water supply systems such as the PRWSS. Furthermore, the comparative analysis of the KPIs underscores the DSS capability to navigate trade-offs between energy efficiency, operational safety, and mechanical reliability, supporting more informed and sustainable decision-making in water-utility management.

Table 4.5: Results of the Smart-DLS for 5 days of operation alongside the PRWSS operation.

KPI		Results for 5 days	Variation (%)
Cost (€)	Real operation	10864.92	-
	Smart-DLS (best cost)	8491.11	-21.85 (-2373.81€)
	Smart-DLS (pump starts)	8511.63	-21.66 (-2353.29€)
	Smart-DLS (FV)	8526.88	-21.52 (-2338.04€)
Pump starts	Real operation	96	-
	Smart-DLS (best cost)	109	+13.54 (+13 pump starts)
	Smart-DLS (pump starts)	101	+5.21 (+5 pump starts)
	Smart-DLS (FV)	121	+26 (+25 pump starts)
FV (Hz/s) (5 days average)	Real operation	6.02	-
	Smart-DLS (best cost)	0.27	-95.52 (-5.75 Hz/s)
	Smart-DLS (pump starts)	0.30	-95.04 (-5.72 Hz/s)
	Smart-DLS (FV)	0.01	-99.84 (-6.01 Hz/s)

(a) Water tank levels in the solution of the total cost KPI (PRWSS).

(b) Water tank levels in the solution of the number of pump starts KPI (PRWSS).

(c) Water tank levels in the solution of the frequency variation KPI (PRWSS).

Figure 4.10: Water tank levels of the Smart-DLS results for the PRWSS considering the KPI: (a) total cost, (b) number of pump starts, and (c) frequency variation.

(a) Pumps operation in the solution of the total cost KPI (PRWSS).

(b) Pumps operation in the solution of the number of pump starts KPI (PRWSS).

(c) Pumps operation in the solution of the frequency variation KPI (PRWSS).

Figure 4.11: Pumps operation in the Smart-DLS results for the PRWSS considering the KPI: (a) total cost, (b) number of pump starts, and (c) frequency variation.

4.4 Real-time adaptive control

As shown in the previous sections, the company's water demand forecasting methods were unable to successfully predict the real water demand, compromising the performance of the optimized solutions. To temporarily address this limitation, and considering that anomalous days can still occur even when accurate forecasting techniques are available, a real-time adaptive control strategy is proposed. This strategy, referred to as the Slope-based Control Method (SCM), dynamically adjusts the duty-cycles scheduling to make the best possible use of the optimized schedule while ensuring that the water tank levels remain within safe operational limits.

4.4.1 Slope-based Control Method

Throughout the day, the current level of each tank wt is monitored to verify if it lies within the upper or lower critical zones, highlighted in orange in Figure 4.12. Therefore, when new data is received from the SCADA system, the critical zones conditions expressed in Equations 4.1 and 4.2 are evaluated for each predefined pump-tank pair:

$$CZ_{p,wt}^{\text{inf}} = (1 - s_p) \times \max\left(0, \text{sign}(AB_{wt}^{\text{inf}} - LD_{wt}^{\text{inf}})\right) \times \max\left(0, \text{sign}(L_{p,wt}^{\text{min}} - L_{p,wt}^{\text{hip}})\right), \quad (4.1)$$

for $p = 1, \dots, P; wt = 1, \dots, WT$

$$CZ_{p,wt}^{\text{sup}} = s_p \times \max\left(0, \text{sign}(AB_{wt}^{\text{sup}} - LD_{wt}^{\text{sup}})\right) \times \max\left(0, \text{sign}(L_{p,wt}^{\text{hip}} - L_{p,wt}^{\text{max}})\right), \quad (4.2)$$

for $p = 1, \dots, P; wt = 1, \dots, WT$,

where s_p is the current pump status, $AB_{wt}^{\text{inf/sup}}$ defines the range of the adaptive controller activation bands, and $LD_{wt}^{\text{inf/sup}}$ is the current level difference between the real water tank level L_{wt}^{real} and its minimum/maximum limit ($L_{wt}^{\text{min/max}}$). The term $L_{p,wt}^{\text{hip}}$ represents the hypothetical water tank level at the next pump state change, which is estimated as:

$$L_{p,wt}^{\text{hip}} = L_{wt}^{\text{real}} + (t_p^{\text{pred}} - t^{\text{current}}) \frac{dL_{wt}}{dt}, \quad (4.3)$$

where the slope of the water tank level variation is computed as:

$$\frac{dL_{wt}}{dt} = \frac{L_{wt}^{\text{real}} - L_{wt}^{\text{prev}}}{\Delta t^{\text{prev}}}, \quad (4.4)$$

with L_{wt}^{prev} being the previous tank level measurement and Δt^{prev} the time interval between the current moment and the last water tank level reading.

If one of the critical zone conditions is satisfied, an anticipation time ($t_{p,wt}^{\text{a_inf/a_sup}}$) is calculated for the next pump state change, ensuring that the water tank level remain within predefined operational limits while minimizing unnecessary pump operations:

$$t_{p,wt}^{\text{a_sup}} = t_p^{\text{pred}} - t^{\text{current}} - LD_{wt}^{\text{sup}} \frac{dL_{wt}}{dt}, p = 1, \dots, P; wt = 1, \dots, WT, \quad (4.5)$$

$$t_{p,wt}^{\text{a_inf}} = t_p^{\text{pred}} - t^{\text{current}} - LD_{wt}^{\text{inf}} \frac{dL_{wt}}{dt}, p = 1, \dots, P; wt = 1, \dots, WT. \quad (4.6)$$

This anticipation time is subtracted from the next pump state change time to determine the new adjusted duty-cycle:

$$t_{p,wt}^{\text{new}} = t_{p,wt}^{\text{pred}} - t_{p,wt}^{\text{a_inf/a_sup}}. \quad (4.7)$$

In cases where a pump is associated with more than one tank, the highest anticipation time is applied, ensuring that the most critical tank condition is addressed first. For pumps operating in parallel, the adjustment is applied only to the pump whose next pump state change is closest to the current time, i.e., the one with the smallest value of $t_{p,wt}^{\text{a_inf/a_sup}}$.

An additional control feature was implemented to handle emergency conditions. This mechanism is triggered when the pumps associated with a given tank, even after anticipation adjustments, are unable to compensate for the demand flow rate. In such cases, if possible, the operating frequency of the corresponding pumps is temporarily increased to their maximum value.

Figure 4.12: Example of superior ($t^{\text{a_sup}}$) and inferior ($t^{\text{a_inf}}$) duty-cycle time anticipation with slope-based method.

4.4.2 Real WSS: Ronqueira network

Figure 4.13 shows the results of applying the adaptive control method in real time to the Ronqueira network. In the three lower charts, the blue dotted line represents the water tank levels obtained through the adaptive control strategy. There were days, e.g. the fourth day for tank Av, when the difference between the forecasted and real water demands is too high, and even activating the pump Av in time is not sufficient to meet the water demand. Nevertheless, when compared with the real network levels, represented by the solid dark blue line, the results demonstrate a significantly improved tank-level performance under the adaptive control approach.

Table 4.6 summarizes the KPI results for the operation with adaptive control. The increase in the number of pump starts was expected, since when discrepancies occurs, the real water demand was predominantly higher than the forecasted demand. Nevertheless, the adaptive control strategy maintained significant cost reductions compared to the real operation, achieving savings of approximately 20% while keeping the water tank levels within acceptable operational limits. Although a slight increase in pump starts frequency was observed in the cost-oriented optimization, the number of starts was effectively reduced when the secondary KPI, number of pump starts, was prioritized. These results confirm that the proposed adaptive control approach effectively preserves the benefits of the Smart-DLS optimization, even under demand uncertainty, ensuring operational safety and energy-cost efficiency in real-time applications.

Table 4.6: Results of the adaptive control method for the Ronqueira network.

KPI		Results for 5 days	Variation (%)
Cost (€)	Real operation	14162.35	-
	Smart-DLS (best cost) with SCM	11837.73	-19.64 (-2324.62€)
	Smart-DLS (pump starts) with SCM	11992.20	-18.10 (-2170.15€)
Pump starts	Real operation	99	-
	Smart-DLS (best cost) with SCM	116	+14.66 (+17 pump starts)
	Smart-DLS (pump starts) with SCM	95	-4.21 (-4 pump starts)

(a) Solution selection KPI: total cost (Ronqueira network left side).

(b) Solution selection KPI: total cost (Ronqueira network right side).

(c) Solution selection KPI: pump starts (Ronqueira network left side).

(d) Solution selection KPI: pump starts (Ronqueira network right side).

Figure 4.13: Results of the adaptive control method for the Ronqueira network considering the Smart-DLS solutions for the KPI:(a and b) total cost and (c and d) number of pump starts.

4.4.3 Real WSS: Portuguese reference water supply system

Figures 4.14 and 4.15 present the results obtained after applying the SCM to the three Smart-DLS solutions. The adaptive control method successfully maintained all tank levels within their operational limits throughout the simulation period. When deviations occurred due to unexpected increases in water demand, the SCM reacted by adding an extra duty cycle or, in more critical situations, by temporarily increasing pump frequencies, e.g. the increase in the frequency operation of pump P4 during the middle of the first day, as shown in Figure 4.15a. These corrective actions ensured hydraulic feasibility but inevitably resulted in a higher number of pump starts and a slight increase in frequency variation.

The impact of the SCM on system performance is summarized in Table 4.7. As expected, the cost reductions remained substantial, ranging from approximately 15% to 18% across the five-day period. Once again, this demonstrates that even with real-time corrective interventions, the DSS retained most of the economic benefits achieved in the open-loop optimization.

However, the application of adaptive control led to an increase in the number of pump starts, reaching a minimum of 26 additional pump starts over the five days, i.e., about five extra pump starts per day across the seven optimized pumps. This effect is particularly evident when long duty-cycles from the Smart-DLS solutions had to be subdivided to prevent violations of water tank level constraints.

Regarding frequency variation, the adaptive solutions exhibited slightly higher values than the open-loop optimization, as expected due to real-time corrective actions. Nevertheless, these values remained significantly lower than those observed in the real operation, with average reductions of up to 79% for the FV KPI. This confirms that the adaptive control effectively mitigates the impact of water demand uncertainty while maintaining smooth and energy-efficient operation.

Overall, the integration of the SCM with the Smart-DLS proved capable of combining the economic efficiency of optimization with the operational reliability of adaptive control, ensuring system feasibility under realistic and uncertain demand conditions. However, with an efficiency improvement of the demand-forecasting module, ideally achieving higher short-term accuracy, the need for frequent application of this adaptive method would be considerably reduced.

Table 4.7: Results of the adaptive control method for the PRWSS.

KPI		5 days results with SCM	Variation with SCM (%)
Cost (€)	Real operation	10864.92	–
	Smart-DLS (best cost)	8941.82	-17.70 (-1923.10€)
	Smart-DLS (pump starts)	9117.91	-16.08 (-1747.01€)
	Smart-DLS (FV)	9230.56	-15.04 (-1634.36€)
Pump starts	Real operation	96	–
	Smart-DLS (best cost)	131	+36.46 (+35 pump starts)
	Smart-DLS (pump starts)	122	+27.08 (+26 pump starts)
	Smart-DLS (FV)	132	+37.50 (+36 pump starts)
FV (Hz/s) (5 days average)	Real operation	6.02	–
	Smart-DLS (best cost)	1.66	-72.49 (-4.37 Hz/s)
	Smart-DLS (pump starts)	1.27	-78.90 (-4.75 Hz/s)
	Smart-DLS (FV)	1.33	-77.90 (-4.69 Hz/s)

(a) Water tank levels in the total cost KPI solution with the SCM (PRWSS).

(b) Water tank levels in the number of pump starts KPI solution with the SCM (PRWSS).

(c) Water tank levels in the frequency variation KPI solution with the SCM (PRWSS).

Figure 4.14: Water tank levels of the Smart-DLS results for the PRWSS with the adaptive control method considering the KPI: (a) total cost, (b) number of pump starts, and (c) frequency variation.

(a) Pumps operation in the solution of the total cost KPI with the adaptive control method (PRWSS).

(b) Pumps operation in the solution of the number of pump starts KPI with the adaptive control method (PRWSS).

(c) Pumps operation in the solution of the frequency variation KPI with the adaptive control method (PRWSS).

Figure 4.15: Pumps operation in the Smart-DLS results for the PRWSS with the adaptive control method considering the KPI: (a) total cost, (b) number of pump starts, and (c) frequency variation.

4.5 Final remarks

This chapter presented the integration of the Smart-DLS optimization approach into a decision support system for pump scheduling in water supply systems. Its application to two real Portuguese WSS, the Ronqueira and the Portuguese Reference Water Supply System, demonstrated both methodological robustness and practical feasibility, confirming the framework's adaptability to networks of different complexity and control characteristics.

In the Ronqueira system, composed by fixed-speed pumps, the Smart-DLS-based DSS achieved consistent energy-cost reductions of around 20%, while fully complying with operational and hydraulic constraints. These results confirmed that the duty-cycle formulation, combined with the hybrid local-search strategy, effectively balances the trade-offs between cost minimization, reliability, and system stability.

In the PRWSS, a more complex system equipped with variable-speed pumps, the DSS exhibited strong scalability and flexibility. It consistently generated feasible and energy-efficient daily schedules, achieving cost reductions of approximately 22% compared with the current operation.

Additionally, the subsequent integration of the slope control method further enhanced operational reliability under demand uncertainty. The adaptive control successfully maintained tank-level feasibility through real-time corrective actions, while preserving most of the economic benefits obtained in the open-loop optimization.

Overall, these results demonstrate that the proposed framework effectively reduces the gap between theoretical optimization models and real-world operational decision-making. By combining a robust optimization engine with an interpretable and modular decision support framework, the DSS provides water utilities with a flexible, transparent, and scalable tool capable of delivering cost-efficient and resilient management of pumping operations under realistic conditions.

5 | Conclusions and future perspectives

5.1 Closing remarks

The operation and control of pumping in water supply systems represents one of the most energy-intensive activities within the urban water cycle. With increasing energy prices, demand variability, and increasingly demanding sustainability targets, the optimization of pump scheduling has become a critical research topic that bridges hydraulic engineering and optimization. However, despite decades of scientific progress, the effective implementation of optimization models in daily operational practice remains limited. Although numerous methodologies have been developed in the literature, these often require significant preparation before they can be applied to real systems. This can be attributed to several methodological and practical factors, including the need for extensive data preparation and calibration to ensure reliable hydraulic simulations, and the lack of guaranteed scalability across different network topologies. These limitations highlight persistent challenges related to scalability, interpretability, and the integration of optimization frameworks into existing water utility workflows. Furthermore, in many water utilities, a traditional mindset that relies heavily on human expertise and resists operational change continues to delay the adoption of optimization tools.

The lack of practical implementation of optimization methods in WSS operations has significant implications for both system efficiency and sustainability. Water utilities continue to rely on rule-based or experience-driven decision processes that often lead to suboptimal energy use and limited operational flexibility. Bridging the gap between theoretical optimization models and real operational practice is essential to enable data-driven, transparent, and adaptive management strategies capable of addressing the growing economic and environmental pressures faced by the water sector.

Therefore, how can a pump scheduling optimization approach be made both universal and operationally feasible for real-world water supply systems? The analysis conducted throughout this thesis revealed that none of the formulations previously proposed in the literature provided a universally effective solution to the pump scheduling problem applicable to all WSS. The duty-cycle formulation validated in this work addresses this limitation by introducing a global and continuous-time representation that encompasses other explicit formulations as particular cases. Moreover, the proposed Smart-DLS algorithm efficiently explores this extended solution space, consistently generating high-quality and feasible pumping schedules with reduced computational effort when compared to approaches reported in the literature. Together, these developments establish a universal

and computationally efficient optimization framework for pump scheduling in real-world water supply systems.

The main contributions of this thesis can be summarized into three key and complementary areas:

1. **Scientific contribution:** a systematic analysis and quantitative comparison of existing pump scheduling formulations was carried out, evidencing the relationships between model complexity, operational flexibility, and computational performance for several pump scheduling optimization approaches. This theoretical study culminated in the definition of a promising alternative to current formulations, the duty-cycle formulation. The duty-cycle approach allows pumps to start operating at any moment within the optimization horizon and can reproduce any solution obtainable by other explicit formulations. The duty-cycle formulation was then employed for the subsequent developments of the work.
2. **Methodological contribution:** a novel hybrid metaheuristic, the Smart Dynamic Local Search (Smart-DLS), was proposed to overcome the limitations of traditional optimization methods. By combining deterministic local search with rule-based shaking and multi-start mechanisms, the algorithm achieves an effective balance between global exploration (searching diverse regions of the solution space) and local exploitation (refining promising solutions to improve their quality). Additionally, this hybrid approach mitigates the sensitivity to initial conditions typical of gradient-based methods. Validation on benchmark and real-world networks demonstrated that Smart-DLS can systematically generate high-quality solutions with reduced computational effort, outperforming conventional approaches in both cost-efficiency and operational stability.
3. **Operational contribution:** the Smart-DLS algorithm was integrated into a modular decision support system that incorporates the classical data-model-knowledge paradigm. This architecture enables operator-in-the-loop optimization, providing multiple optimized schedules evaluated against predefined KPIs, such as energy cost and number of pump starts. By employing optimization within a transparent decision framework, the DSS enhances trust and usability for operators, ensuring that advanced optimization can effectively inform daily decision-making processes rather than replace them.

Aiming to bridge one of the main previously mentioned challenges, i.e. the lack of practical implementations, the proposed DSS was successfully validated in two real WSS with distinct operational characteristics, evidencing also its versatility and scalability. For the Ronqueira network, operating with fixed-speed pumps, the proposed framework achieved impressive energy-cost reductions of 20%, over a five-day period, compared to current network operation, highlighting the advantages of the Smart-DLS optimization framework, while simultaneously maintaining safe operational levels and service reliability, two crucial requirements for real-world implementations.

In the Portuguese Reference WSS, equipped with variable-speed pumps, the DSS demonstrated both scalability and robustness when applied to complex hydraulic and operational conditions. It consistently generated feasible and energy-efficient pumping schedules over several consecutive days, achieving an overall cost reduction of approximately 22%. These outcomes confirmed the adaptability of the framework to different

technological configurations and scales, reinforcing its potential for widespread adoption by water utilities.

A final important feature of the proposed solution is the inclusion of an adaptive control mechanism designed to address discrepancies between forecasted and actual water demands. Acting as a real-time correction layer, this mechanism anticipates potential violations of water level limits and adjusts pump operation accordingly, thereby maintaining feasible and reliable system performance. Beyond its technical function, this mechanism can also help to mitigate the reluctance of operators to adopt optimization-based methodologies, as it provides an additional safeguard that ensures system safety even under unexpected operating conditions.

Overall, this thesis presents a decision support framework that bridges methodological innovation and practical implementation in the management of water supply systems. It proved that optimization-based decision support, when developed with operational awareness and under a human-centered perspective, can deliver substantial energy cost reductions while ensuring reliable system performance. The proposed optimization approach enhances, rather than replaces, human expertise by fostering a collaborative environment in which computational methods assist operators in making informed and transparent decisions. By integrating optimization and decision support functionalities within a modular and interpretable architecture, the framework contributes to the ongoing digital transformation of the water sector and establishes a clear pathway toward smarter, more sustainable, and resilient water management practices.

5.1.1 Perspectives for future work

The optimization of WSS operational management should remain an active research topic within the scientific community. Although the developed optimization framework is suitably prepared for application in real WSS operations, some perspectives for further study can be identified. The following points summarize the main recommendations for future research and development:

- **Smart-DLS extended validation.** Apply the proposed framework to additional WSS with diverse topologies and operational contexts, and assess its performance over longer operational horizons. Evaluate alternative sets of KPIs for the Smart-DLS, beyond energy cost, number of pump starts and frequency variation.
- **Improvement of the duty-cycle formulation for variable-speed pumps.** Study the inclusion of pump frequency at both the beginning and end of each duty-cycle as decision variables, allowing frequency to evolve dynamically within the duty-cycle. Assess the trade-off between the increased modeling flexibility and the associated computational cost to determine whether the additional complexity leads to measurable improvements in solution quality.
- **Renewable energy integration under the water-energy nexus.** Extend the mathematical model to incorporate on-site renewable energy generation (e.g., photovoltaic systems, battery storage, etc.) and to couple water storage dynamics with energy availability and time-varying electricity prices. This integration would enable the integrated optimization of pump scheduling, renewable energy utilization, and storage management under dynamic tariff structures. The objective is to

assess how the coordinated operation of hydraulic and energy resources can reduce operational costs, minimize carbon emissions, and increase the overall flexibility and sustainability of WSS operations.

- **Development of a forecasting module.** Investigate forecasting models, such as machine learning-based demand prediction and renewable generation forecasting, to enhance the performance and real-world applicability of the Smart-DLS results.
- **Full DSS development and deployment.** Complete the data, model, and knowledge management layers, and develop user interfaces for visualization, scenario and KPIs comparison. Deploy and test the full DSS in collaboration with the partner water utility to evaluate its usability, transparency, and operational impact.

Through these extensions, the Smart-DLS-based framework can evolve from a validated research prototype into an operationally mature, nexus-aware decision support platform for sustainable and resilient water utility management.

References

- [1] A. L. Reis, M. A. Lopes, A. Andrade-Campos, and C. Henggeler Antunes, “A review of operational control strategies in water supply systems for energy and cost efficiency,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 175, no. November 2022, p. 113140, 2023, DOI: 10.1016/j.rser.2022.113140.
- [2] B. Durin and J. Margeta, “Analysis of the possible use of solar photovoltaic energy in urban water supply systems,” *Water (Switzerland)*, vol. 6, no. 6, pp. 1546–1561, 2014, DOI: 10.3390/w6061546.
- [3] D. F. Moreira and H. M. Ramos, “Energy Cost Optimization in a Water Supply System Case Study,” *Journal of Energy*, vol. 2013, pp. 1–9, 2013, DOI: 10.1155/2013/620698.
- [4] I. Sarbu, “A study of energy optimisation of urban water distribution systems using potential elements,” *Water*, vol. 8, no. 12, 2016, DOI: 10.3390/w8120593.
- [5] European Commission, *Water - energy nexus in Europe*, D. Magagna, I. Hidalgo González, G. Bidoglio, and S. Peteves, Eds. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2019. DOI: 10.2760/968197.
- [6] B. Ghaddar, J. Naoum-Sawaya, A. Kishimoto, N. Taheri, and B. Eck, “A Lagrangian decomposition approach for the pump scheduling problem in water networks,” *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 241, no. 2, pp. 490–501, 2015, DOI: 10.1016/j.ejor.2014.08.033.
- [7] K. L. Lam, S. J. Kenway, and P. A. Lant, “Energy use for water provision in cities,” *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 143, pp. 699–709, 2017, DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.12.056.
- [8] M. Świątochowska and I. Bartkowska, “Optimization of Energy Consumption in the Pumping Station Supplying Two Zones of the Water Supply System,” *Energies*, vol. 15, no. 1, 2022, DOI: 10.3390/en15010310.
- [9] H. Oh, J. Eom, and T. Kim, “Case study of pump scheduling using sensor-based real-time pump efficiency monitoring,” *Desalination and Water Treatment*, vol. 181, pp. 141–150, 2020, DOI: 10.5004/dwt.2020.25162.
- [10] H. Mala-Jetmarova, N. Sultanova, and D. Savic, “Lost in optimisation of water distribution systems? A literature review of system operation,” *Environmental Modelling and Software*, vol. 93, pp. 209–254, 2017, DOI: 10.1016/j.envsoft.2017.02.009.

- [11] M. Brás, A. Moura, and A. Andrade-Campos, “Cost efficiency in water supply systems: an applied review on optimization models for the pump scheduling problem,” *European Journal of Operational Research*, no. July, 2024, DOI: 10.1016/j.ejor.2024.07.039.
- [12] United Nations, “Transforming our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development,” United Nations, New York, Resolution adopted by the General Assembly on 25 September 2015 A/RES/70/1, 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/post2015/transformingourworld/publication>
- [13] M. Brás, A. Moura, and A. Andrade-Campos, “Cost Reduction of Water Supply Systems Through Optimization Methodologies : A Comparative Study of Optimization Approaches,” in *Proceedings of the 6th European Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management*, 2023, DOI: 10.46254/EU6.20230097.
- [14] O. M. Awe, S. T. Okolie, and O. S. Fayomi, “Optimization of Water Distribution Systems: A Review,” *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 1378, no. 2, 2019, DOI: 10.1088/1742-6596/1378/2/022068.
- [15] K. E. Lansey, “The evolution of optimizing water distribution system applications,” *8th Annual Water Distribution Systems Analysis Symposium 2006*, no. 1992, p. 5, 2007, DOI: 101061/40941(247)5.
- [16] D. R. Broad, H. R. Maier, and G. C. Dandy, “Optimal operation of complex water distribution systems using metamodels,” *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, vol. 136, no. 4, pp. 433–443, 2010, DOI: 10.1061/(asce)wr.1943-5452.0000052.
- [17] D. G. Yoo, S. M. Lee, H. M. Lee, Y. H. Choi, and J. H. Kim, “Optimizing rechlorination injection points for water supply networks using harmony search algorithm,” *Water (Switzerland)*, vol. 10, no. 5, 2018, DOI: 10.3390/w10050547.
- [18] W. Kurek and A. Ostfeld, “Multi-objective optimization of water quality, pumps operation, and storage sizing of water distribution systems,” *Journal of Environmental Management*, vol. 115, pp. 189–197, 2013, DOI: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2012.11.030.
- [19] D. Kang and K. Lansey, “Real-Time Optimal Valve Operation and Booster Disinfection for Water Quality in Water Distribution Systems,” *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, no. August, pp. 463–473, 2010, DOI: 10.1061/(ASCE)WR.1943-5452.0000056.
- [20] P. N. Khatavkar and L. W. Mays, “Testing an optimization–simulation model for optimal pump and valve operations with required storage tank turnovers,” *Journal of Water Management Modeling*, vol. 2019, no. 2007, pp. 1–9, 2019, DOI: 10.14796/JWMM.C464.
- [21] D. Savić, H. Mala-Jetmarova, and N. Sultanova, “History of optimization in water distribution system analysis,” *1st International WDSA / CCWI 2018 Joint Conference*, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://ojs.library.queensu.ca/index.php/wdsa-ccw/article/view/11973>

- [22] M. Qun, J. Wang, and C. Liu, “Energy-saving optimization of water supply pumping station life cycle based on bim technology,” *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, vol. 100, no. 1, 2017, DOI: 10.1088/1755-1315/100/1/012201.
- [23] A. Marchi, A. R. Simpson, M. A. Thyer, S. Sutanto, and N. C. Do, “Optimisation of pump operations in water distribution systems taking into account the seasonality of the demand,” *14th Water Distribution Systems Analysis Conference 2012, WDSA 2012*, vol. 1, no. January 2015, pp. 602–612, 2012. [Online]. Available: <https://search.informit.org/doi/10.3316/informit.945873761719355>
- [24] B. Coelho and A. Andrade-Campos, “Efficiency achievement in water supply systems - A review,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 30, pp. 59–84, 2014, DOI: 10.1016/j.rser.2013.09.010.
- [25] S. Asadi, M. Asadi, and M. Patriksson, “Minimization of water pumps’ electricity usage: A hybrid approach of regression models with optimization,” *Expert Systems With Applications*, vol. 107, pp. 222–242, 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.eswa.2018.04.027.
- [26] B. Coelho and A. Andrade-Campos, “A new approach for the prediction of speed-adjusted pump efficiency curves,” *Journal of Hydraulic Research*, vol. 1686, no. May, 2016, DOI: 10.1080/00221686.2016.1175521.
- [27] A. K. Coker, “Pumping of liquids,” in *Ludwig’s Applied Process Design for Chemical and Petrochemical Plants*, 4th ed., 2007, pp. 303–369, DOI: 10.1016/b978-075067766-0/50012-9.
- [28] G. Wang, S. Ghoddousi, Z. Wang, and L. Song, “Development, validation and application of an energy model for energy efficient operation of parallel pump systems,” *Journal of Building Engineering*, vol. 59, no. April, p. 105098, 2022, DOI: 10.1016/j.jobe.2022.105098.
- [29] R. Menke, E. Abraham, and I. Stoianov, “Modeling Variable Speed Pumps for Optimal Pump Scheduling,” in *Proceedings of the 2016 World Environmental and Water Resources Congress*, 2016, pp. 199–209, DOI: 10.1061/9780784479858.022.
- [30] S. S. Hashemi, M. Tabesh, and B. Ataekia, “Ant-colony optimization of pumping schedule to minimize the energy cost using variable-speed pumps in water distribution networks,” *Urban Water Journal*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 335–347, 2014, DOI: 10.1080/1573062X.2013.795233.
- [31] M. Abdallah, S. M. Asce, Z. Kapelan, and M. Asce, “Fast Pump Scheduling Method for Optimum Energy Cost and Water Quality in Water Distribution Networks with Fixed and Variable Speed Pumps,” *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, vol. 145, no. 12, pp. 1–13, 2019, DOI: 10.1061/(ASCE)WR.1943-5452.0001123.
- [32] L. A. Rossman, H. Woo, M. Tryby, F. Shang, R. Janke, and T. Haxton, *EPANET 2.2 User Manual*, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, 2020. [Online]. Available: https://cfpub.epa.gov/si/si_public_record_Report.cfm?dirEntryId=348882&Lab=CESER

- [33] J. D. L. Vega and D. Alem, “An improved stochastic optimization model for water supply pumping systems in urban networks,” *Water Resources Management*, vol. 18052, p. 780, 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://optimization-online.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/03/4271.pdf>
- [34] J. G. Bene, I. Selek, and C. Hos, “Comparison of deterministic and heuristic optimization solvers for water network scheduling problems,” *Water Science and Technology: Water Supply*, vol. 13, no. 5, pp. 1367–1376, 2013, DOI: 10.2166/ws.2013.148.
- [35] J. E. V. Zyl, D. a. Savic, and G. a. Walters, “Operational Optimization of Water Distribution Systems Using a Hybrid Genetic Algorithm,” *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, vol. 130, no. 2, pp. 160–170, 2004, DOI: 10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9496(2004)130:2(160).
- [36] R. E. Burkard and J. Hatzl, “A complex time based construction heuristic for batch scheduling problems in the chemical industry,” *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 174, no. 2, pp. 1162–1183, 2006, DOI: 10.1016/j.ejor.2005.03.011.
- [37] C. A. Méndez, J. Cerdá, I. E. Grossmann, I. Harjunoski, and M. Fahl, “State-of-the-art review of optimization methods for short-term scheduling of batch processes,” *Computers and Chemical Engineering*, vol. 30, no. 6-7, pp. 913–946, 2006, DOI: 10.1016/j.compchemeng.2006.02.008.
- [38] L. Ormsbee, S. Lingireddy, and D. Chase, “Optimal pump scheduling for water distribution systems,” *Multidisciplinary International Conference on Scheduling: Theory and Applications*, 2009. [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:13808704>
- [39] L. Cimorelli, C. Covelli, B. Molino, and D. Pianese, “Optimal regulation of pumping station in water distribution networks using constant and variable speed pumps: A technical and economical comparison,” *Energies*, vol. 13, no. 10, pp. 25–30, 2020, DOI: 10.3390/en13102530.
- [40] B. Coelho and A. Andrade-Campos, “Improving water supply systems efficiency - A methodology for optimal control of variable-speed pumps,” *Proceedings of the 35th IAHR World Congress held in Chengdu, China, 8-13 September 2013*, pp. 1–15, 2013. [Online]. Available: <https://www.iahr.org/library/infor?pid=15100>
- [41] Y. Wang, G. Cembrano, V. Puig, M. Urrea, J. Romera, D. Saporta, and J. G. Valero, “Model Predictive Control of Water Networks Considering Flow,” in *Real-Time Monitoring and Operational Control of Drinking-Water Systems*. Springer International Publishing AG 2017, 2017, ch. 12, pp. 227–249, DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-50751-4_12.
- [42] M. M. P. Figueiredo and J. P. Martins, “Minimização do Custo da Energia em Estações Elevatórias de Abastecimento de Água,” *I Conferência INSSAA - Modelação de Sistemas de Abastecimento de Água. Implementação Sustentada e Integração na Indústria da Água*, 2007. [Online]. Available: <https://hdl.handle.net/10216/65837>

- [43] M. Paschke, K. Spencer, N. Waniarcha, A. Simpson, and T. Widdop, "Genetic algorithms for optimising pumping operations," *19th Federal Convention, Australian Water Association, Canberra, Australia*, no. January 2001, 2001.
- [44] M. D. Kazantzis, A. R. Simpson, D. Kwong, and S. M. Tan, "A new methodology for optimizing the daily operations of a pumping plant," *Proceedings of the 2002 Conference on Water Resources Planning*, no. October, 2002.
- [45] L. Costa, B. D. A. Prata, H. M. Ramos, and M. Aurélio, "A Branch-and-Bound Algorithm for Optimal Pump Scheduling in Water Distribution Networks," *Water Resources Management*, pp. 1037–1052, 2015, DOI: 10.1007/s11269-015-1209-2.
- [46] T. Luna, J. Ribau, D. Figueiredo, and R. Alves, "Improving energy efficiency in water supply systems with pump scheduling optimization," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 213, pp. 342–356, 2019, DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.12.190.
- [47] S. Alvisi and M. Franchini, "A robust approach based on time variable trigger levels for pump control," *Journal of Hydroinformatics*, vol. 19, no. 6, pp. 811–822, 2017, DOI: 10.2166/hydro.2017.141.
- [48] A. Marchi, A. R. Simpson, and M. F. Lambert, "Optimization of Pump Operation Using Rule-Based Controls in EPANET2: New ETTAR Toolkit and Correction of Energy Computation," *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, vol. 142, no. 7, pp. 1–11, 2016, DOI: 10.1061/(asce)wr.1943-5452.0000637.
- [49] C. Quintiliani and E. Creaco, "Using Additional Time Slots for Improving Pump Control Optimization Based on Trigger Levels," *Water Resources Management*, vol. 33, no. 9, pp. 3175–3186, 2019, DOI: 10.1007/s11269-019-02297-6.
- [50] Y. Wang, G. Cembrano, V. Puig, M. Urrea, J. Romera, D. Saporta, J. G. Valero, and J. Quevedo, "Optimal Management of Barcelona Water Distribution Network using Non-linear Model Predictive Control," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 50, no. 1, pp. 5380–5385, 2017, DOI: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2017.08.1070.
- [51] C. Giacomello, Z. Kapelan, and M. Nicolini, "Fast Hybrid Optimization Method for Effective Pump Scheduling," *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, vol. 139, no. 2, pp. 175–183, 2012, DOI: 10.1061/(asce)wr.1943-5452.0000239.
- [52] M. López-Ibáñez, T. Devi Prasad, and B. Paechter, "Optimal pump scheduling: Representation and multiple objectives," *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Computing and Control for the Water Industry, CCWI 2005: Water Management for the 21st Century*, vol. 1, 2005.
- [53] T. D. Prasad, M. López-Ibáñez, and B. Paechter, "Ant-colony optimization for optimal pump scheduling," *8th Annual Water Distribution Systems Analysis Symposium 2006*, p. 77, 2006, DOI: 10.1061/40941(247)77.
- [54] A. M. Bagirov, A. F. Barton, H. Mala-Jetmarova, A. Al Nuaimat, S. T. Ahmed, N. Sultanova, and J. Yearwood, "An algorithm for minimization of pumping costs in water distribution systems using a novel approach to pump scheduling," *Mathematical and Computer Modelling*, vol. 57, no. 3-4, pp. 873–886, 2013, DOI: 10.1016/j.mcm.2012.09.015.

- [55] G. Marini, N. Fontana, M. Maio, F. Di Menna, and M. Giugni, “A Novel Approach to Avoiding Technically Unfeasible Solutions in the Pump Scheduling Problem,” *Water (Switzerland)*, vol. 15, no. 2, 2023, DOI: 10.3390/w15020286.
- [56] S. Alvisi and M. Franchini, “A Methodology for Pumping Control Based on Time Variable Trigger Levels,” *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 162, pp. 365–372, 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.proeng.2016.11.076.
- [57] E. Salomons and M. Housh, “Practical real-time optimization for energy efficient water distribution systems operation,” *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 275, pp. 124–148, 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.124148.
- [58] D. M. Liu and S. Y. Li, “Predictive zone control of pressure management for water supply network systems,” *International Journal of Automation and Computing*, vol. 13, no. 6, pp. 607–614, 2016, DOI: 10.1007/s11633-015-0935-5.
- [59] M. K. Heris, “Practical Genetic Algorithms in Python and MATLAB,” 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://yarpiz.com/632/ypga191215-practical-genetic-algorithms-in-python-and-matlab>
- [60] The SciPy Community, “Optimization and root finding (scipy.optimize),” 2008–2023. [Online]. Available: <https://docs.scipy.org/doc/scipy/reference/optimize.html>
- [61] P. Fracas, K. V. Camarda, and E. Zondervan, “Shaping the future energy markets with hybrid multimicrogrids by sequential least squares programming,” *Process Systems Engineering: For a Smooth Energy Transition*, pp. 307–341, 2022, DOI: 10.1515/9783110705201-012.
- [62] The SciPy Community, “scipy.optimize. linprog.” [Online]. Available: <https://docs.scipy.org/doc/scipy/reference/generated/scipy.optimize.linprog.html>
- [63] I. B. Freitas, “Operational management of Water Supply Systems through implicit methodologies,” Master’s thesis, University of Aveiro, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://hdl.handle.net/10773/41021>
- [64] B. S. Vieira, S. F. Mayerle, L. M. Campos, and L. C. Coelho, “Optimizing drinking water distribution system operations,” *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 280, no. 3, pp. 1035–1050, 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.ejor.2019.07.060.
- [65] Y. Shao, X. Zhou, T. Yu, T. Zhang, and S. Chu, “Pump scheduling optimization in water distribution system based on mixed integer linear programming,” *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 313, no. 3, pp. 1140–1151, 2023, DOI: 10.1016/j.ejor.2023.08.055.
- [66] M. López-Ibáñez, T. D. Prasad, and B. Paechter, “Ant Colony Optimization for Optimal Control of Pumps in Water Distribution Networks,” *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, vol. 134, no. 4, pp. 337–346, 2008, DOI: 10.1061/(asce)0733-9496(2008)134:4(337).

- [67] M. Brás, A. Moura, and A. Andrade-Campos, “A novel hybrid optimization approach for cost-efficient pump scheduling in water supply systems,” *Omega*, vol. 138, no. January 2025, 2026, DOI: 10.1016/j.omega.2025.103378.
- [68] N. Mladenović, M. Dražić, V. Kovačević-Vujčić, and M. Čangalović, “General variable neighborhood search for the continuous optimization,” *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 191, no. 3, pp. 753–770, 2008, DOI: 10.1016/j.ejor.2006.12.064.
- [69] E. Castillo, R. Mínguez, and C. Castillo, “Sensitivity analysis in optimization and reliability problems,” *Reliability Engineering and System Safety*, vol. 93, no. 12, pp. 1788–1800, 2008, DOI: 10.1016/j.res.2008.03.010.
- [70] A. L. Sousa and A. Andrade-Campos, “Analytical Sensitivity Analysis and Optimization for Cost-Efficient Operation of Water Supply Systems,” *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, 2024, DOI: 10.1061/JWRMD5/WRENG-6295.
- [71] A. Andrade-Campos, J. Dias-de Oliveira, and J. Pinho-da Cruz, *Otimização Não-linear em Engenharia - Cálculo Estrutural e Computacional Multiescala*. ETEP - Edições Técnicas e Profissionais, 2015.
- [72] I. P. Kougiyas and N. P. Theodossiou, “Multiobjective Pump Scheduling Optimization Using Harmony Search Algorithm (HSA) and Polyphonic HSA,” *Water Resources Management*, vol. 27, no. 5, pp. 1249–1261, 2013, DOI: 10.1007/s11269-012-0236-5.
- [73] R. Menke, E. Abraham, P. Parpas, and I. Stoianov, “Exploring Optimal Pump Scheduling in Water Distribution Networks with Branch and Bound Methods,” *Water Resources Management*, vol. 30, no. 14, pp. 5333–5349, 2016, DOI: 10.1007/s11269-016-1490-8.
- [74] A. A. Abdelsalam and H. A. Gabbar, “Energy saving and management of water pumping networks,” *Heliyon*, vol. 7, no. 8, 2021, DOI: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e07820.
- [75] P. Hansen, N. Mladenovic, J. Brimberg, and J. A. M. Pérez, “Variable Neighborhood Search,” in *Handbook of Metaheuristics*. Springer International Publishing, 2019, vol. 272, pp. 57–97, DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-91086-4_3.
- [76] P. Hansen, N. Mladenović, and J. A. Moreno Pérez, “Variable neighbourhood search: Methods and applications,” *Annals of Operations Research*, vol. 175, no. 1, pp. 367–407, 2010, DOI: 10.1007/s10479-009-0657-6.
- [77] P. Hansen and N. Mladenović, “Variable neighborhood search,” *Computers & Operations Research*, vol. 24, no. 11, pp. 1097–1100, 1997, DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-07124-4_19.
- [78] N. Sluijk, A. M. Florio, J. Kinable, N. Dellaert, and T. Van Woensel, “Two-echelon vehicle routing problems: A literature review,” *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 304, no. 3, pp. 865–886, 2023, DOI: 10.1016/j.ejor.2022.02.022.

- [79] I. G. Tsoulos, A. Tzallas, and D. Tsalikakis, “Use RBF as a Sampling Method in Multistart Global Optimization Method,” *Signals*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 857–874, 2022, DOI: 10.3390/signals3040051.
- [80] R. Martí, J. A. Lozano, and A. Mendiburu, *Multi-start Methods*. Springer International Publishing, 2016. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-07153-4.
- [81] T. M. Walski, E. D. Brill, J. Gessler, I. C. Goulter, R. M. Jeppson, K. Lansley, H. L. Lee, J. C. Liebman, L. Mays, D. R. Morgan, and L. Ormsbee, “Battle of the network models: epilogue,” *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, vol. 113, no. 2, pp. 191–203, 1987, DOI: 10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9496(1987)113:2(191).
- [82] Z. Rao and F. Alvarruiz, “Use of an artificial neural network to capture the domain knowledge of a conventional hydraulic simulation model,” *Journal of Hydroinformatics*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 15–24, 2007, DOI: 10.2166/hydro.2006.014.
- [83] L. Cimorelli, A. D’Aniello, and L. Cozzolino, “Boosting Genetic Algorithm Performance in Pump Scheduling Problems with a Novel Decision-Variable Representation,” *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management*, vol. 146, no. 5, pp. 1–11, 2020, DOI: 10.1061/(asce)wr.1943-5452.0001198.
- [84] Z. Rao and E. Salomons, “Development of a real-time, near-optimal control process for water-distribution networks,” *Journal of Hydroinformatics*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 25–37, 2007, DOI: 10.2166/hydro.2006.015.
- [85] T. Batista do Egito, J. R. G. de Azevedo, and S. d. T. Marques Bezerra, “Optimization of the operation of water distribution systems with emphasis on the joint optimization of pumps and reservoirs,” *Water Supply*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 1094–1105, 2023, DOI: 10.2166/ws.2023.065.
- [86] Scubic, “Scubic - Smart Software Solutions,” 2017-2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.scubic.pt/>
- [87] J. P. Shim, M. Warkentin, J. F. Courtney, D. J. Power, R. Sharda, and C. Carlsson, “Past, present, and future of decision support technology,” *Decision Support Systems*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 111–126, 2002, DOI: 10.1016/S0167-9236(01)00139-7.
- [88] R. H. Sprague, “A framework for the development of decision support systems,” *MIS Quarterly*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 1–26, 1980, DOI: 10.2307/248957.
- [89] D. J. Power, *Decision Support Systems: Concepts and Resources for Managers*, 67th ed. Gallery, Faculty Book, 2002. [Online]. Available: <https://scholarworks.uni.edu/facbook/67>
- [90] Elsevier, “Scopus.” [Online]. Available: <https://www.scopus.com>
- [91] Y. Ma, X. Gao, C. Liu, and J. Li, “Improved SQP and SLSQP algorithms for feasible path-based process optimisation,” *Computers and Chemical Engineering*, vol. 188, no. May, 2024, DOI: 10.1016/j.compchemeng.2024.108751.

- [92] T. F. Kaiser, R. H. Osman, and R. O. Dickau, “Analysis guide for variable frequency drive operated centrifugal pumps,” *PROCEEDINGS OF THE TWENTY-FOURTH INTERNATIONAL PUMP USERS SYMPOSIUM*, 2008.
- [93] A. Marchi, A. R. Simpson, and N. Ertugrul, “Assessing variable speed pump efficiency in water distribution systems,” *Drinking Water Engineering and Science*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 15–21, 2012. [Online]. Available: 10.5194/dwes-5-15-2012
- [94] J. Bohórquez, J. Saldarriaga, and D. Vallejo, “Pumping pattern optimization in order to reduce WDS operation costs,” *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 119, no. 1, pp. 1069–1077, 2015, DOI: 10.1016/j.proeng.2015.08.936.
- [95] F. De Paola, N. Fontana, M. Giugni, G. Marini, and F. Pugliese, “Optimal solving of the pump scheduling problem by using a harmony search optimization algorithm,” *Journal of Hydroinformatics*, vol. 19, no. 6, pp. 879–889, 2017, DOI: 10.2166/hydro.2017.132.
- [96] T. C. Pereira, R. V. Arbos, and A. Andrade-Campos, “Multiservice System for Water Supply Systems: A Smart Predictive Digital Twin Proposal,” *IEEE International Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation, ETFA*, 2024, DOI: 10.1109/ETFA61755.2024.10710851.
- [97] S. Anbarasu, K. Hinkelman, and W. Zuo, *Tracing the Dependency of Water and Energy in Smart and Connected Communities Through a Multi-domain Modeling Framework*. Springer Nature Singapore, 2023, no. January 2024, DOI: 10.1007/978-981-19-9822-5_19.
- [98] D. Tarek, H. H. Mahmoud, and T. Ismail, “Energy Optimization and Cost Reduction in Water Distribution Networks,” *2022 13th International Symposium on Communication Systems, Networks and Digital Signal Processing, CSNDSP 2022*, pp. 368–372, 2022, DOI: 10.1109/CSNDSP54353.2022.9907950.
- [99] J. Bhardwaj, J. Krishnan, and B. Beferull-Lozano, “Data-driven pump scheduling for cost minimization in water networks,” *ICAS 2021 - 2021 IEEE International Conference on Autonomous Systems, Proceedings*, pp. 1–5, 2021, DOI: 10.1109/ICAS49788.2021.9551168.
- [100] M. Maskit and A. Ostfeld, “Multi-objective operation-leakage optimization and calibration of water distribution systems,” *Water (Switzerland)*, vol. 13, no. 11, 2021, DOI: 10.3390/w13111606.
- [101] A. J. Ulusoy and I. Stoianov, “Distributed solution of the day-ahead pump and valve scheduling problem for dynamically adaptive water distribution networks with storage,” *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 323, no. 1, pp. 267–275, 2024, DOI: 10.1016/j.ejor.2024.11.035.
- [102] F. De Paola, F. Pugliese, N. Fontana, and M. Giugni, “A new Digital Harmony Search algorithm for optimizing Pump Scheduling in Water Distribution Networks,” *Water Research X*, vol. 27, no. December 2024, p. 100300, 2025, DOI: 10.1016/j.wroa.2024.100300.

- [103] S. A. Putri and F. K. Moazeni, “Stability-guaranteed data-driven nonlinear predictive control of water distribution systems,” *Control Engineering Practice*, vol. 157, no. September 2024, p. 106243, 2025, DOI: 10.1016/j.conengprac.2025.106243.
- [104] C. O. Maxwell, Z. I. Oonge, P. M. Odira, G. O. Ouma, M. Lompi, T. Pacetti, M. D. Bacco, and E. Caporali, “Water–Energy Nexus-Based Optimization of the Water Supply Infrastructure in a Dryland Urban Setting,” *Water (Switzerland)*, vol. 16, no. 21, 2024, DOI: 10.3390/w16213073.
- [105] D. H. Kim and D. W. Jang, “Optimization of Water Distribution Network Demand Patterns Using Real-Coded Genetic Algorithms,” *Water (Switzerland)*, vol. 16, no. 20, 2024, DOI: 10.3390/w16202971.
- [106] D. Cariaga, Á. Lorca, and M. F. Anjos, “A Binary Expansion Approach for the Water Pump Scheduling Problem in Large and High-Altitude Water Supply Systems,” *Energies*, vol. 17, no. 16, pp. 1–32, 2024, DOI: 10.3390/en17164107.
- [107] T. Janus, B. Ulanicki, and K. Diao, “Optimal scheduling of variable speed pumps with mixed integer linear programming,” *Water Supply*, vol. 27, no. 7, pp. 2409–2426, 2024, DOI: 10.2166/ws.2024.118.
- [108] B. Brentan, F. Mota, A. Menapace, A. Zanfei, and G. Meirelles, “Optimizing pump operations in water distribution networks: Balancing energy efficiency, water quality and operational constraints,” *Journal of Water Process Engineering*, vol. 63, no. April, p. 105374, 2024, DOI: 10.1016/j.jwpe.2024.105374.
- [109] X. Zhou, S. Chu, T. Zhang, T. Yu, and Y. Shao, “Risk-Constrained Optimal Scheduling in Water Distribution Systems Toward Real-Time Pricing Electricity Market,” *Water Resources Research*, vol. 60, no. 4, 2024, DOI: 10.1029/2023WR035630.
- [110] Y. Shao, X. Zhou, T. Yu, T. Zhang, and S. Chu, “Pump scheduling optimization in water distribution system based on mixed integer linear programming,” *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 313, no. 3, pp. 1140–1151, 2024, DOI: 10.1016/j.ejor.2023.08.055.
- [111] H. Ma, X. Wang, and D. Wang, “Pump Scheduling Optimization in Urban Water Supply Stations: A Physics-Informed Multiagent Deep Reinforcement Learning Approach,” *International Journal of Energy Research*, vol. 2024, 2024, DOI: 10.1155/2024/9557596.
- [112] N. Hedaiaty Marzouny and R. Dziedzic, “AI-Assisted Pump Operation for Energy-Efficient Water Distribution Systems,” *Engineering Proceedings*, p. 3, 2024, DOI: 10.3390/engproc2024069003.
- [113] S. Yan, W. Yang, G. Liu, and C. Zhu, “Variable frequency constant pressure water supply system based on Siemens S-1200,” *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 2836, no. 1, 2024, DOI: 10.1088/1742-6596/2836/1/012003.
- [114] M. Ürkmez, C. Kallesøe, J. D. Bendtsen, and J. Leth, “Economic Predictive Control with Periodic Horizon for Water Distribution Networks,” *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 56, no. 2, pp. 4669–4674, 2023, DOI: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2023.10.982.

- [115] B. Du, D. Zha, J. Guo, and X. Yu, "Optimization of pump scheduling in waterworks considering load balancing using improved genetic algorithm," *Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems*, vol. 44, no. 6, pp. 9651–9669, 2023, DOI: 10.3233/JIFS-224245.
- [116] G. Perelman, A. Ostfeld, and B. Fishbain, "Robust Optimal Operation of Water Distribution Systems," *Water (Switzerland)*, vol. 15, no. 5, 2023, DOI: 10.3390/w15050963.
- [117] S. Hu, J. Gao, D. Zhong, R. Wu, and L. Liu, "Real-Time Scheduling of Pumps in Water Distribution Systems Based on Exploration-Enhanced Deep Reinforcement Learning," *Systems*, vol. 11, no. 2, 2023, DOI: 10.3390/systems11020056.
- [118] R. Cantu-Funes and L. C. Coelho, "Simulation-based optimization of pump scheduling for drinking water distribution systems," *Engineering Optimization*, vol. 55, no. 5, pp. 841–855, 2023, DOI: 10.1080/0305215X.2022.2044030.
- [119] A. Silva-Rubio Sergio, Y. Salgueiro, M. M. Daniel, and G. B. Jimmy, "Influence of Solution Representation in a Multi-Objective Pump Scheduling Problem," *Proceedings - IEEE CHILEAN Conference on Electrical, Electronics Engineering, Information and Communication Technologies, ChileCon*, 2023, DOI: 10.1109/CHILECON60335.2023.10418662.
- [120] Y. Guo, S. Wang, A. F. Taha, and T. H. Summers, "Optimal Pump Control for Water Distribution Networks via Data-Based Distributional Robustness," *IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 114–129, 2023, DOI: 10.1109/TCST.2022.3167844.
- [121] S. M. Zanoli, C. Pepe, G. Astolfi, and L. Orletti, "Applications of Advanced Process Control Techniques to an Italian Water Distribution Network," *IEEE Transactions on Control of Network Systems*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 1767–1779, 2022, DOI: 10.1109/TCNS.2022.3223574.
- [122] B. Soleimani, D. Keihan Asl, J. Estakhr, and A. R. Seifi, "Integrated optimization of multi-carrier energy systems: Water-energy nexus case," *Energy*, vol. 257, 2022, DOI: 10.1016/j.energy.2022.124764.
- [123] Y. H. Choi, "Development of optimal water distribution system design and operation approach considering hydraulic and water quality criteria in many-objective optimization framework," *Journal of Computational Design and Engineering*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 507–518, 2022, DOI: 10.1093/jcde/qwac017.
- [124] A. Candelieri, A. Ponti, I. Giordani, and F. Archetti, "Lost in Optimization of Water Distribution Systems: Better Call Bayes," *Water (Switzerland)*, vol. 14, no. 5, 2022, DOI: 10.3390/w14050800.
- [125] M. N. Sharif, E. Bakhtavar, H. Haider, G. Hu, K. Hewage, and R. Sadiq, "Staged energy and water quality optimization for large water distribution systems," *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, vol. 194, no. 3, 2022, DOI: 10.1007/s10661-022-09874-0.

- [126] M. Dini, M. Hemmati, and S. Hashemi, “Optimal Operational Scheduling of Pumps to Improve the Performance of Water Distribution Networks,” *Water Resources Management*, vol. 36, no. 1, pp. 417–432, 2022, DOI: 10.1007/s11269-021-03034-8.
- [127] P. D. Dai and N. H. Viet, “Optimization of Variable Speed Pump Scheduling for Minimization of Energy and Water Leakage Costs in Water Distribution Systems with Storages,” *Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on Electronics, Computers and Artificial Intelligence, ECAI 2021*, pp. 1–6, 2021, DOI: 10.1109/ECAI52376.2021.9515135.
- [128] J. Jafari-Asl, G. Azizyan, S. A. H. Monfared, M. Rashki, and A. Andrade-Campos, “An enhanced binary dragonfly algorithm based on a V-shaped transfer function for optimization of pump scheduling program in water supply systems (case study of Iran),” *Engineering Failure Analysis*, vol. 123, no. February, p. 105323, 2021, DOI: 10.1016/j.engfailanal.2021.105323.
- [129] Y. Li, E. Musabandesu, T. Fujiwara, F. J. Loge, and K. L. Ma, “A Visual Analytics System for Water Distribution System Optimization,” *Proceedings - 2021 IEEE Visualization Conference - Short Papers, VIS 2021*, no. 1, pp. 126–130, 2021, DOI: 10.1109/VIS49827.2021.9623272.
- [130] G. Güngör-Demirci, J. Lee, and J. Keck, “Optimizing pump operations in water distribution systems: energy cost, greenhouse gas emissions and water quality,” *Water and Environment Journal*, vol. 34, no. S1, pp. 841–848, 2020, DOI: 10.1111/wej.12583.
- [131] F. Moazeni and J. Khazaei, “Optimal operation of water-energy microgrids; a mixed integer linear programming formulation,” *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 275, p. 122776, 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.122776.
- [132] J. Studziński and A. Ziólkowski, “Control of pumps of water supply network under hydraulic and energy optimisation using artificial intelligence,” *Entropy*, vol. 22, no. 9, 2020, DOI: 10.3390/e22091014.
- [133] F. Moazeni, J. Khazaei, and J. P. Pera Mendes, “Maximizing energy efficiency of islanded micro water-energy nexus using co-optimization of water demand and energy consumption,” *Applied Energy*, vol. 266, no. March, p. 114863, 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.114863.

A | Appendices

A.1 Appendix of Chapter 2

A.1.1 Mathematical formulations proposed for the pump scheduling optimization problem

Table A.1: Model's mathematical formulations proposed for the pump scheduling optimization problem.

Ref.	Test network	Hydraulic simulator	Optimization algorithm	Formulation type	Objective function	Decision variables
Van Zyl et al. [35]	Anytown and Van Zyl networks	EPANET	Hybrid genetic algorithm + hillclimber search strategy	Implicit: RFTL formulation	Minimize energy cost	Pair of continuous decision variables for each tariff period: L_{\min}^{peak} , L_{\max}^{peak} , $L_{\min}^{\text{offpeak}}$ and $L_{\max}^{\text{offpeak}}$
López-Ibañez et al. [52]	Van Zyl network	EPANET	Multi-objective evolutionary algorithm meta-heuristic: strength pareto evolutionary algorithm version 2	Explicit: proposed TPU formulation	Minimize energy cost with penalty cost to maximize the minimum stopping time	Pair of integers t_{start} , t_{stop} : start and stop time of each pump operation
López-Ibañez et al. [66]	Van Zyl and Richmond networks	EPANET	Ant colony meta-heuristics	Explicit: proposed TPU formulation	Minimize energy cost	Pair of integers t_{off} , t_{on} : time during which a pump is inactive and active
Ormsbee et al. [38]	Not applied	Not applied	Not applied	Explicit: proposed TPR formulation	Minimize energy cost	Continuous decision variables $X_{n,st}^{\text{stat}} = II.CC$. II is the integer that identifies the combination of pumps of the pumping station st that is running, and CC is the % of time that operates within the time interval n
Giacomello et al. [51]	Anytown and Richmond networks	EPANET	LPG hybrid optimization method: linear programming + greedy algorithm	Implicit: volume formulation	Minimize energy cost	Pair of continuous $Q_{p,t}$ and $H_{p,t}$: hourly pumps flow rate and head

(continued on next page)

Table A.1: (continued)

Ref.	Test network	Hydraulic simulator	Optimization algorithm	Formulation type	Objective function	Decision variables
Broad et al. [16]	WSS of Wallan, Victoria, Australia	Artificial Neural Network Metamodel	Genetic algorithm	Implicit: RFTL formulation	Minimize material cost (energy and chlorine) with penalty costs	Pair of continuous decision variables for tank trigger levels for each energy tariff and continuous decision variable for chlorine dosing rates
Coelho and Andrade-Campos [40]	Simple Test Network (1 pump + 1 water tank) and Walski WSS	EPANET	Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm, Evolutionary algorithm and Differential Evolution algorithm	Explicit: real-time formulation with VSP	Minimize energy cost	Continuous decision variables for pump relative speed and percentage of pump operation time for each time-step
Bagirov et al. [54]	EPANET Net3 and Van Zyl networks	EPANET	Proposed algorithm: combination of the Grid Search with the Hooke-Jeeves Pattern search method	Explicit: proposed TPU formulation	Minimize energy and maintenance cost	Pair of vectors t_m , X_m : pump start/end operation times as continuous variables, and binary integer variables to describe the pump status at the beginning of each scheduling period
Moreira and Ramos [3]	WSS of Fátima, Portugal	Bentley's WaterGEMS	Genetic algorithm	Explicit: discrete time formulation with VSP	Minimize energy cost	Discrete decision variables $\mathbf{X}^{\text{pump}} \in \{0, M_1$ (minimum relative speed), M_2, M_3, M_4, M_5 (maximum relative speed)
Bohórquez et al. [94]	Example network with 159 pipes, 3 pumps and 1 water tank	EPANET	Genetic algorithm	Implicit: FTL formulation with VSP	Minimize energy cost with one penalty cost	Continuous decision variables for tank trigger levels and for tank levels at which each of the five possible speeds must be activated

(continued on next page)

Table A.1: (continued)

Ref.	Test network	Hydraulic simulator	Optimization algorithm	Formulation type	Objective function	Decision variables
Alvisi and Franchini [56]	Italian WSS	EPANET	NSGA-II algorithm	Implicit: VTL formulation	Minimize energy cost and number of pump switches	Continuous decision variables a_{peak} , k_{peak} , $a_{\text{off-peak}}$, $k_{\text{off-peak}}$, $Lpeak_{\text{start}}$, $Lpeak_{\text{end}}$: the exponents of the power law relationships representing the pattern of the switching on/off trigger levels in each time periods (peak and off-peak), and the values of the maximum and minimum levels at the time instants $tpeak_{\text{start}}$ and $tpeak_{\text{end}}$
Marchi et al. [48]	Van Zyl network	EPANET 2.0 + ET-TAR toolkit	Evolutionary algorithm	Implicit: RFTL formulation	Minimize energy cost	Pair of continuous decision variables for tank trigger levels for each energy tariff
De Paola et al. [95]	Modified Anytown e Van Zyl Networks	EPANET	Proposed algorithm: modified harmony search multi-objective	Explicit: proposed TPU formulation	Minimize energy cost and maintenance cost	Pair of continuous decision variables t_i, t'_i represents a single pump start. It specifies the transition from the inactive status (during t_i) to the active mode (during t'_i)
Wang et al. [41]	Barcelona's WSS, Spain	MATLAB with Simulink	GAMS/CONOPT solver	Implicit: volume formulation	Minimize energy cost	Continuous decision variable for pump flow at each time interval
Khatavkar and Mays [20]	City XYZ: 1427 junctions, 3 water tanks, 2 treatment plants, 1789 pipes, 4 pumps, 2 pressure release valves, and 6 flow valves	EPANET	Genetic algorithm	Explicit: binary discrete formulation	Minimize energy cost with penalty costs	Pumps control: binary variables, $x \in 0, 1$; Inflow valve controls $X_{\text{in}}(s, t)$ is 0 for input valve to tank s closed at time t and is 1 for valve open; Outflow valve controls $X_{\text{out}}(s, t)$ is 0 for output valve from tank s closed at time t and is 1 for valve open

(continued on next page)

Table A.1: (continued)

Ref.	Test network	Hydraulic simulator	Optimization algorithm	Formulation type	Objective function	Decision variables
Quintiliani and Creaco [49]	Case Study 1 (CS1): 1 water source + 1 pump + 1 water tank; CS2: CS1 + 2 pumps in parallel	Not mentioned	CS1: Technique of the Total Enumeration; CS2: Borg Multi-objective Evolutionary algorithm	Implicit: RFLATS formulation	Minimize energy cost	Continuous decision variables DPs, DPe, S_{on} and S_{off} : distance from $tPeak_{start}$, distance from $tPeak_{end}$, minimum trigger level at off-peak period and maximum trigger level at peak period
Luna et al. [46]	WSS of Algarve, Portugal	EPANET	Proposed hybrid genetic algorithm	Explicit: binary formulation	Minimize energy cost	Binary decision variables for hourly pump operation
Cimorelli et al. [39]	Modified Anytown e Van Zyl networks	EPANET	Genetic algorithm	Explicit: binary formulation with FSP and VPS	Minimize energy cost	FSP: binary variables $x \in \{0, 1\}$; VSP: Continuous variables $x \in 0 \cup [V_{min}, 1]$, where V_{min} is the minimum relative speed at which the pump can operate
Cimorelli et al. [83]	Any Town and Any Town Modified networks	EPANET	Proposed genetic algorithm variant with new chromosome representation	Explicit: binary formulation	Minimize energy cost	Binary decision variables for hourly pump operation
Marini et al. [55]	Van Zyl and Anytown networks	EPANET	Pikaia genetic algorithm	Explicit: proposed TPU formulation	Minimize energy cost	Pair of decision variables x_1, x_2 : dictate the starting time ($SonT$) and duration (OD) of each pump operation. $SonT = \Delta t_s \times int(x_1 \frac{1440}{\Delta t_s})$; $OD = \Delta t_s \times int(x_2 \frac{1440}{\Delta t_s})$

A.2 Appendix of Chapter 3

A.2.1 Smart-DLS results for each network

Table A.2: Smart-DLS results for the Van Zyl network.

	Number of duty-cycles (1A/2B/3B)	Solution's decision variables ($st_{p,1}^{dc}, \dots, st_{p,D}^{dc}, \Delta t_{p,1}^{dc}, \dots, \Delta t_{p,D}^{dc}$)
Smart-DLS Approach (KPI: Best cost)	5/5/5	1A: [0.64, 4.31, 6.53, 17.02, 23.8, 0, 0.06, 7.11, 6.78, 0.20] 2B: [4.62, 5.06, 5.85, 16.78, 20.83, 0.06, 0.15, 6.93, 4.05, 3.17] 3B: [9.06, 14.16, 16.71, 22.08, 23.16, 5.10, 2.55, 5.37, 1.08, 0.84]
Smart-DLS Approach (KPI: No of pump starts)	4/5/2	1A: [3.99, 5.64, 7.73, 16.95, 0, 2.09, 5.62, 7.04] 2B: [5.64, 9.06, 15.01, 16.98, 19.89, 3.42, 4.30, 0, 2.91, 4.11] 3B: [9.62, 23.41, 13.79, 0.59]

Table A.3: Smart-DLS results for the Anytown modified network.

	Number of duty-cycles (b1/b2/b3)	Solution's decision variables ($st_{p,1}^{dc}, \dots, st_{p,D}^{dc}, \Delta t_{p,1}^{dc}, \dots, \Delta t_{p,D}^{dc}$)
Smart-DLS Approach (KPI: Best cost)	6/6/6	b1: [0.01, 4.97, 9.56, 14.54, 20.66, 21.82, 1.67, 2, 4.10, 1.95, 0.13, 0.75] b2: [0, 2.49, 3.91, 7.26, 16.32, 21.94, 2.15, 1.29, 0.67, 1.10, 0.65, 0.30] b3: [0.02, 2.53, 6.77, 9.53, 16.71, 20.93, 1.76, 0.63, 0.55, 5.85, 0.67, 1.71]
Smart-DLS Approach (KPI: No of pump starts)	4/4/4	b1: [1.78, 13.67, 15.36, 21.16, 2.98, 0, 1.63, 0] b2: [0.04, 6.55, 12.33, 20.96, 2.13, 4.08, 3.36, 2.47] b3: [3.29, 9.52, 16.39, 20.72, 3.63, 4.79, 1.09, 0.15]

Table A.4: Smart-DLS results for the Ronqueira network.

	Number of duty-cycles (p_Al1/p_Al2/p_Av/ p_Trav/p_OC/p_SPD)	Solution's decision variables ($st_{p,1}^{dc}, \dots, st_{p,D}^{dc}, \Delta t_{p,1}^{dc}, \dots, \Delta t_{p,D}^{dc}$)
Smart-DLS Approach (KPI: Best cost)	5/8/5/4/9/4	p_Al1: [0, 4.17, 7.59, 16.33, 22.70, 2.02, 1.23, 1.76, 0.76, 0.44] p_Al2: [1.32, 1.89, 5.39, 9.59, 12.03, 18.53, 21.12, 23.30, 0.02, 2.28, 1.64, 0, 4.17, 0, 1.65, 0] p_Av: [0.01, 10.37, 13.31, 19.37, 21.79, 7.42, 0, 3.80, 0, 1.20] p_Trav: [0, 10.86, 14.28, 19.31, 7.52, 0, 0.44, 0] p_OC: [0, 4.01, 5.71, 9.54, 12.04, 14.45, 16.01, 18.98, 21.37, 2.17, 1.56, 1.43, 0, 0.60, 0.73, 0.54, 0, 0.51] p_SPD: [0, 9.84, 12.61, 21.01, 7.09, 0, 5.54, 2.83]
Smart-DLS Approach (KPI: No of pump starts)	5/6/6/4/6/5	p_Al1: [0, 8.66, 12.56, 17.52, 22.64, 3.21, 0, 2.28, 0, 0.44] p_Al2: [0.93, 3.02, 6.3, 10.37, 15.06, 21.3, 0, 3.27, 3.18, 0, 3.07, 0.53] p_Av: [0.20, 7.5, 10.52, 12.94, 19.14, 21.37, 7.29, 0.57, 0, 2.99, 0, 1.55] p_Trav: [0, 9.66, 12.05, 14.72, 7.28, 0, 0.67, 0] p_OC: [9, 4.70, 9.89, 12.0, 15.64, 19.91, 2.72, 2.7, 0, 2.06, 0, 0] p_SPD: [0, 10.15, 12.63, 19.46, 21.04, 7.65, 0, 5.30, 0, 2.51]

A.2.2 Ronqueira network: water consumption demands from February 20th of 2024

Figure A.1: Water demands of each consumption point on February 20th of 2024: (a) São Pedro Dias and Casais, (b) Outeiro Castro and Entroncamento, (c) Travanca, (d) Albarqueira, (e) Espinheira, and (f) Aveleira.

A.3 Appendix of Chapter 4

A.3.1 Ronqueira network: real and forecasted water demands from September 25 to 29, 2024

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Figure A.2: Real and forecasted water demands of each consumption point from September 25 to 29, 2024: (a) São Pedro Dias and Casais, (b) Outeiro Castro and Entroncamento, (c) Travanca, (d) Albarqueira, (e) Espinheira, and (f) Aveleira.

A.3.2 PRWSS: real and forecasted water demands from May 7 to 11, 2025

Figure A.3: Real and forecasted water demands of each location from May 7 to 11, 2025.

A.3.3 Systematic literature review: article analysis

Table A.5: Systematic literature review: article analysis.

Reference	Query	Optimization approach	Real-world applica- tion?	Classification	Explanation
Pereira et al. [96]	A + B	MPC (continuous formula- tion + SLSQP algorithm) + Digital Twin (EPANET)	No. Case study: EPANET Net3	AOC	The system includes predictive modeling (machine learning, ML), optimiza- tion using MPC, and simulation of control actions in a digital twin architec- ture. Although human operators are acknowledged theoretically, the article does not describe any human validation or decision-making step. Optimized pump schedules are automatically generated and applied in simulation.
Anbarasu et al. [97]	A + B	Modelica (simulation) + 2 optimization approaches: water tank level set points and demand-response control using simplex (continuous) and genetic algorithm (discrete)	No. Case study: Hypothetical single- family residential community in Cali- fornia	DSO	The article presents an optimization framework that compares rule-based and demand-responsive pump controls under realistic electricity pricing signals. The model explores both discrete and continuous pump control strategies and presents their impact on cost and energy savings. While the system is not deployed in real-time or coupled with an interface, it clearly produces interpretable, comparative outputs (e.g., time of use (TOU) vs. critical peaks (CP) scenarios, control strategies) that can inform future implementation and decision-making. It does not execute controls automatically and is not positioned as an autonomous controller.
Tarek et al. [98]	A + B	EPANET (simulation) + game theory (reservoir serv- ing patterns) + genetic al- gorithm (optimize tank de- mand pattern) + decision- making algorithm	No. Case study: Proposed WSS	AOC	The system integrates multiple optimization and control techniques into a structured decision-making framework: Game Theory to determine the reser- voir serving pattern; Genetic Algorithm to optimize the tank demand pattern over 24 hours; Decision Algorithm to control pumps and valves based on flow and pressure thresholds. All operations are executed automatically in a sim- ulated environment. No human intervention, supervision, or decision-making step is described.
Bhardwaj et al. [99]	A + B	Mixed-Integer Problem + Deep Neural Network (sim- ulation)	No. Case study: Proposed WSS	AOC	The authors solve multiple instances of the MILP using a solver (Gurobi) and use those solutions to train a deep neural network (DNN). The trained DNN replaces the need for the MIO solver, producing pump control decisions in milliseconds. All control decisions are automatically generated, and the system is tested entirely on synthetic data. There is no operator interface or human-in-the-loop.
Maskit and Ostfeld [100]	A + B	Multi-Objective Genetic Al- gorithm + EPANET (simu- lation)	No. Case study: Proposed WSS	DSO	The study presents a multi-objective optimization approach combining pump scheduling and leakage reduction using a genetic algorithm. The model gen- erates a set of Pareto-optimal solutions, allowing system operators to choose the best trade-off based on their preferences (e.g., energy vs. leakage). There is no automated execution. Instead, the system explicitly aims to facilitate human decision-making.

(continued on next page)

Table A.5: (continued)

Reference	Query	Optimization approach	Real-world application?	Classification	Explanation
Cimorelli et al. [83]	A	Genetic Algorithm + Binary Formulation + EPANET (simulation)	No. Case studies: Anytown and Anytown Modified Network	OM	The paper presents an improved representation method for encoding pump scheduling decisions within a genetic algorithm framework. The focus is entirely on algorithmic efficiency and solution quality in simulated scenarios using EPANET. There is no mention of user interaction, decision support, recommendation generation, or integration with operational systems. Therefore, the work is best classified as an Optimization Model, serving purely analytical purposes.
Ulusoy and Stoianov [101]	B	Mixed-Integer Nonlinear Programming (MINLP) + heuristic ADMM-based decomposition (Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers)	Yes. Case study: BWFL, an operational WDN in the UK	AOC	The system autonomously generates optimized day-ahead schedules for pumps and boundary valves. The proposed solution method (Algorithm 1) computes and directly executes control actions based on energy cost minimization without requiring human input. No interface, recommendation system, or user validation is described. Decisions are computed and intended for operational execution.
Brás et al. [11]	B	MPC (duty-cycles formulation + SLSQP algorithm) + EPANET (simulation)	No. Case study: Van Zyl Network	AOC	The article implements a MPC strategy combining a duty-cycle optimization model solved with SLSQP and validated using EPANET simulations. The approach updates pump control decisions dynamically over a predictive horizon without human intervention. There is no interface for decision-makers to select or approve solutions.
De Paola et al. [102]	B	Binary formulation + Digital Harmony Search (DHS) + EPANET (simulation)	No. Case studies: Van Zyl and Anytown Modified Networks	AOC	The study presents the Digital Harmony Search (DHS) metaheuristic to optimize pump scheduling by minimizing energy cost and pump switching. The system runs on predefined benchmark networks without human interaction. It uses EPANET simulations to validate hydraulic feasibility but does not offer an interface or recommendation system for human decision-makers. The control logic is autonomously executed.
Putri and Moazeni [103]	B	Quasi-Infinite Horizon Non-linear Model Predictive Control (QIH-NMPC) with data-driven prediction via sparse regression (SINDy)	Yes. Case study: WSS from Middletown, Pennsylvania	AOC	The fully automated system executes pump scheduling decisions without human input. It uses a nonlinear MPC controller with predictive models learned from operational data. The framework is designed for real-time execution, with no interactive interface or operator feedback loop. The main goal is autonomous control with guaranteed stability and feasibility. There is no scenario exploration or decision support interface.

(continued on next page)

Table A.5: (continued)

Reference	Query	Optimization approach	Real-world applica- tion?	Classification	Explanation
Maxwell et al. [104]	B	Binary formulation + Genetic Algorithm + EPANET Simulation	Yes. Case study: Lodwar WSS, Kenya	AOC	This study proposes a pump scheduling optimization method based on the water–energy nexus, applied to a real system in Lodwar, Kenya. It uses a genetic algorithm to determine optimal pump operation schedules that minimize energy costs while ensuring hydraulic reliability. The system automatically evaluates candidate solutions via EPANET simulations and selects the best solution based on cost and pressure performance. There is no human decision-making interface, no recommendation system, and the process is entirely automated.
Kim and Jang [105]	B	Binary formulation + Real-Coded Genetic Algorithm + EPANET Simulation	Yes. Case study: City in the Republic of Korea	AOC	The study develops and applies a real-coded genetic algorithm to optimize daily demand patterns in a real water distribution network. The optimization aims to reduce pump energy costs by adjusting water tank use and aligning supply with dynamic electricity tariffs. EPANET is used for hydraulic simulation, validating pressure and flow constraints. There is no interaction or recommendation interface for human operators; the solution is generated and selected autonomously.
Cariaga et al. [106]	B	MINLP reformulated as MILP	Yes. Case study: WSS from Radomiro Tomic Mine, Chile	OM	The article develops a binary expansion reformulation to efficiently solve pump scheduling as a MILP problem. It includes detailed hydraulic modeling and cost minimization, applied to a large-scale, high-altitude WDN in Chile. The model is solved offline and intended for day-ahead operational planning. There is no real-time integration, no operator interaction, and no automated execution of schedules. The work does not propose a decision support interface or a control architecture. Therefore, the system is best classified as an Optimization Model, as its goal is to advance mathematical formulation and planning efficiency, not to enable or automate operational decision-making.
Janus et al. [107]	B	MILP with piece-linear approximations for VSPs + tank and pipe modelling	No. Case study: Proposed WSS	OM	The paper introduces a comprehensive MILP formulation for pump scheduling that explicitly models variable-speed pumps (VSPs) using piece-linear approximations. The model incorporates pipe and tank dynamics and solves for energy-efficient pump schedules over a 24h horizon. Emphasis is placed on mathematical formulation and approximation techniques (not operational deployment). The study is clearly designed as a methodological contribution, not as an operational decision-making system. There is no operator interface, no scenario exploration, and no automated execution of control actions. Thus, the system is best classified as an Optimization Model, with a theoretical and algorithmic focus rather than real-time or interactive decision support.

(continued on next page)

Table A.5: (continued)

Reference	Query	Optimization approach	Real-world applica- tion?	Classification	Explanation
Brentan et al. [108]	B	Multi-objective optimization (energy cost and water quality, binary decision variables for pump status) + NSGA-II	No. Case study: D-town WSS	DSO	The article presents a multi-objective optimization model using NSGA-II to balance energy cost and water quality, producing a Pareto front of pump schedules. While it does not include a user interface or integration into operational workflows, the structured output enables human operators to evaluate trade-offs and select appropriate solutions. The model is clearly designed to support decision-making, although it is not implemented as a full decision support system.
Zhou et al. [109]	B	A Posteriori Random Forest (AP-RF) + Risk-Constrained MILP (with Conditional Value at Risk objective)	No. Case studies: Richmond Skeleton and C-Town	OM	The article proposes a risk-aware optimization model for pump scheduling under electricity price uncertainty. It integrates a posteriori random forest forecasting to estimate the probability distribution of real-time electricity prices, then applies scenario-based sampling and clustering to generate representative input scenarios. The resulting MILP model minimizes the Conditional Value at Risk (CVaR) of operational costs. While the method contributes to the robustness of pump scheduling strategies in volatile markets, it produces only a single optimized solution per case and does not offer alternative schedules, user interaction, or decision-making structure. Therefore, the work is best classified as an Optimization Model, analytically rigorous and risk-informed, but not designed to support or structure human decision-making.
Shao et al. [110]	B	MILP-based optimization model	Yes. Case studies: Van Zyl and Richmond Skeleton network, and H City in China	OM	The article proposes a MILP formulation to solve the pump scheduling problem by linearizing the original nonlinear hydraulic equations (e.g., head loss and pump curves). The core contribution lies in the efficient linearization approach that reduces auxiliary variables while maintaining model fidelity. The model is evaluated on two benchmark networks and a real large-scale network. The paper presents only a single optimized pump operation per instance and does not offer structured alternatives, decision logic, or operator interaction. Therefore, while technically rigorous and practically applicable, the study is best classified as an Optimization Model, not a decision support system.

(continued on next page)

Table A.5: (continued)

Reference	Query	Optimization approach	Real-world application?	Classification	Explanation
Mas et al. [111]	B	PI-LSTM surrogate model + Multiagent Deep Reinforcement Learning (MAD-DPG)	Yes. Case study: Baiyangwan WSS in Suzhou City, China	AOC	The article proposes a closed-loop control system for water supply pump scheduling using a multiagent deep reinforcement learning framework trained via a physics-informed LSTM surrogate model. Each pump is modeled as an autonomous agent that learns to coordinate with others in real time to minimize energy consumption while maintaining safe pressure and limiting pump switching. The trained model is directly applied for real-time control decisions without operator input, thus functioning as an autonomous controller. While explainability and visualization are discussed, the system is not presented as an operator-facing tool or as part of a broader decision-support interface.
Hedaiaty Marzouny and Dziedzic [112]	B	Large Language Model (ChatGPT) + EPANET hydraulic simulation in a closed-loop feedback framework, using prompt engineering strategies and iterative fine-tuning	No. Case study: EPANET Net3	DSO	The article proposes an interactive optimization framework for pump scheduling, where a large language model (ChatGPT) suggests pump control settings based on system state and operator prompts. The framework uses an iterative loop with EPANET to evaluate and refine suggestions, guided by different prompt engineering strategies. Although the optimization is fully data-driven and non-deterministic, it does not execute pump controls automatically. Instead, it enables an operator-like agent (or potentially a human) to iteratively improve energy efficiency while maintaining pressure constraints.
Yan et al. [113]	B	Closed-loop control system using PID + PLC (Siemens S7-1200) + frequency converter + pressure sensors and real-time monitoring via HMI	not mentioned	AOC	The article presents a fully automated control architecture for constant-pressure pump operation based on variable frequency drive (VFD) technology and PID regulation. The system integrates pressure feedback via sensors, automated speed adjustment via frequency converters, and real-time control through a Siemens PLC. Although an HMI allows operators to switch between manual and automatic modes, in automatic mode, the system operates without human intervention, adjusting pump operation dynamically in response to pressure fluctuations. Since it performs autonomous, closed-loop control of pump speed and scheduling without generating alternative scenarios or supporting human decision-making, it is best classified as an Automated Optimization Controller.

(continued on next page)

Table A.5: (continued)

Reference	Query	Optimization approach	Real-world applica- tion?	Classification	Explanation
Ürkmez et al. [114]	B	Adapted MPC that dynamically between two objective functions: Normal Control (NC) to minimize energy cost and average zone pressure, and Burst Control (BC) to minimize energy cost and supply deficit.	Yes. Case study: BWFL, an operational WDN in the UK	AOC	The proposed system executes real-time pump and valve control through a nonlinear MPC framework that autonomously adapts to burst events. It operates continuously, selects control actions based on updated network conditions, and does not involve human decision-making or recommendation structures. No alternatives are presented for operator evaluation, and no interface is described.
Du et al. [115]	B	Two-stage strategy using a genetic algorithm (GA). Stage 1: Optimizes the number of active pumps per hour and their operating speeds to reduce energy costs. Stage 2: Applies an improved GA to minimize the number of pump switches and enhance load balancing.	Yes. Case study: WSS from Suzhou, China	OM	Although the article uses real operational data and a detailed optimization model, the system produces a single optimized scheduling plan without alternative operational scenarios, decision-making layers, or human interaction in the loop. There is no evidence of operator-facing components, real-time feedback, or interface for decision-making. The tool is implemented and validated via simulation, not deployed as part of an operational system.
Perelman et al. [116]	B	Robust Optimization + Second-Order Conic Programming (SOCP) with demand and cost uncertainty	Yes. Case study: WSS of Sopron, Hungary	OM	The article presents a robust pump operation planning model focused on handling uncertainties in demand and energy prices. While the model is tested on real data, it is not implemented in an online environment, does not execute decisions autonomously, and lacks any user-facing interface or scenario selection logic. A single robust solution is computed per optimization run, without generating alternative schedules for operator evaluation.
Hu et al. [117]	B	Exploration-Enhanced Proximal Policy Optimization (E-PPO) + EPANET	No. Case study: EPANET Net3	AOC	The method is implemented as a real-time controller, where a trained RL agent determines and executes hourly pump speeds without operator involvement. Although highly efficient, it does not offer scenario alternatives, interfaces for operator choice, or recommendation logic, the agent directly decides and applies pump actions.

(continued on next page)

Table A.5: (continued)

Reference	Query	Optimization approach	Real-world applica- tion?	Classification	Explanation
Cantu-Funes and Coelho [118]	B	MINLP (binary with hydraulic constraints) + Adaptive Large Neighborhood Search (ALNS)	No. Case studies: Van Zyl, Richmond skeleton/standard, Florianópolis, Net1 networks	OM	The paper presents an optimization formulation validated through EPANET simulation and benchmark comparison. However, it operates strictly as an offline planning tool: it generates one optimized schedule at a time, does not update in real time, and does not offer user interaction or alternative operation plans. The system is not integrated into an actual WDS control environment.
Silva-Rubio Sergio et al. [119]	B	NSGA-II (multi-objective genetic algorithm) + 4 optimization models (different solution representations)	No. Case study: Anytown network	OM	The article presents a methodological study focused on how different solution representations affect the performance of a multi-objective optimization algorithm (NSGA-II) applied to the pump scheduling problem. Although it contributes significantly to understanding algorithmic behavior and encoding strategies, it does not involve real-time application, system integration, decision support structures, or operational deployment. Only one optimized schedule is returned per execution (per representation), and no decision-making framework is implemented.
Guo et al. [120]	B	MINLP reformulated as MILP (with Conditional Value-at-Risk incorporated)+ Model Predictive Control (MPC)	Yes. Case study: Barcelona WSS	AOC	The methodology is explicitly designed as a real-time control scheme: a closed-loop distributionally MPC. It updates pump schedules at each time step based on real-time forecast error data and operates under a feedback control structure. Although the paper includes significant theoretical modeling, it culminates in real-time control policy computation, not in offline multi-solution planning or abstract formulation. Control actions (e.g., pump schedules and reserve policies) are computed and applied dynamically over the 24-hour horizon using data-driven uncertainty sets, clearly placing the system in the realm of automatic operation.
Marini et al. [55]	B	NLOP (discrete duty-cycles formulation) + Pikaia Genet Algorithm + EPANET	No. Case studies: Anytown and Van Zyl networks	OM	The approach generates a single optimal schedule offline using a metaheuristic and simulation, and while it adds a smart feasibility check, it does not involve operator interaction, scenario presentation, or online reoptimization.
Zanoli et al. [121]	B	Rule-based pump scheduling + Two-layer MPC for pressure control with Kalman filtering	Yes. Case study: Subnet of Trento, Italian WSS	AOC	The article presents a fully implemented and deployed real-time control system combining pump scheduling and pressure regulation. The control strategies are automated and act directly on the system via SCADA, with no operator-in-the-loop decision-making or multiple solutions for selection. Although optimization logic is present (e.g., quadratic programming (QP) problems in MPC), it is entirely embedded in the controller design, aiming for autonomous operation, not operator guidance or support.

(continued on next page)

Table A.5: (continued)

Reference	Query	Optimization approach	Real-world applica- tion?	Classification	Explanation
Soleimani et al. [122]	B	Newton-Raphson water flow + Teaching-Learning-Based Optimization (TLBO)	Yes. Case study: IEEE 33-bus standard network (electrical system) + North Marin WDN	DSO	The article presents an optimization framework for the integrated operation of water and electrical networks. While the model includes pump scheduling and demand response programs, the solution is entirely offline and used for planning and analysis. It explores the impact of variable-speed pumps and tank use on energy savings, but does not implement the model in a real-time controller or interactive decision-making environment. The framework is suitable for integration into a decision support system (to decide between integrated or separately water-energy optimization), but no user interaction or automated control loop is implemented. Results are used for comparative scenario analysis, showing benefits of DR participation and energy-network coupling.
Choi et al. [123]	B	Optimization in 2 stages: 1. Pipe diameter optimization using Self-Adaptive Harmony Search (SaHS); 2. Pump scheduling optimization using Self-Adaptive Multi-Objective Harmony Search (SaMOHS)	No. Case study: Modified Apulian WSS	DSO	The framework produces multiple Pareto-optimal pump schedules that balance cost, water quality, and system robustness. The trade-off solutions are explicitly analyzed and presented as alternatives for operator evaluation, such as least-cost, marginal, and maximum-robustness schedules. Although not deployed in a real system or with human-machine interaction, it offers clear operational choices that could support planners or decision-makers.
Candelieri et al. [124]	B	Bayesian optimization + surrogate modeling (gaussian process/random forest) + implicit/explicit pump control	Yes. Case study: WSS of Milan, Italy	DSO	The article proposes bayesian optimization as a method for optimizing pump operations. It discusses learning control rules based on historical SCADA data or simulated models, without direct integration into an automatic control system. Multiple configurations are generated (especially in implicit control), allowing operators or designers to select optimal strategies. The framework is not deployed in real-time, nor is it coupled to SCADA execution, but it serves as a basis for decision support through interpretable optimization.
Sharif et al. [125]	B	Risk-based Chlorine Booster Optimization + Mixed-Integer Goal Programming (MIGP) for Pump Scheduling	Yes. Case study: WSS of Al-Khobar, Saudi Arabia	OM	The article presents a staged optimization framework combining water quality and energy objectives. Pump scheduling is formulated as a Mixed-Integer Goal Programming (MIGP) problem, solved via CPLEX, producing a single optimized schedule. While the model is applied to a real-world case and integrates both hydraulic and quality constraints, it does not provide multiple solution scenarios, user interaction, or real-time adaptability. As the system generates a unique operational plan without decision support features or human-in-the-loop structure, it is best classified as an Optimization Model.

(continued on next page)

Table A.5: (continued)

Reference	Query	Optimization approach	Real-world application?	Classification	Explanation
Dini et al. [126]	B	Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) + Active Pumps Index (API) + EPANET simulation	Yes. Case study: WSS in Ahar, Iran	AOC	The system proposes and executes fully automated control logic, adjusting the number of active pumps and their speeds on an hourly basis. Control decisions are not designed for operator review, nor are multiple scenarios presented for human selection. While the model is tested in simulation, the logic is structured to operate autonomously and update control settings without human intervention. The use of the API for dynamic pump number selection adds a layer of adaptability but remains fully automated and prescriptive.
Dai and Viet [127]	B	Genetic Algorithm + water loss and energy cost minimization (FSP and VSP) + EPANET (simulation)	No. Case study: Literature benchmark (not defined)	OM	The study focuses on developing and testing an optimization model for cost-efficient pump scheduling using GA. While it investigates realistic trade-offs (leakage vs. energy cost), the system is purely offline, outputs a single solution per run, and is not integrated into any control system or DSS. It does not include scenario selection, user interaction, or real-time operation logic.
Jafari-Asl et al. [128]	B	Binary Dragonfly Algorithm (BDA) + Binary model + EPANET (simulation)	Yes. Case studies: Van Zyl network and WSS of Doroudzan Dam-Shiran in Iran	OM	The study focuses on developing and testing an optimization algorithm, presenting a single optimal pump schedule per scenario. No user interface, multiple decision options, or interactive evaluation are provided. There is no automation of pump control or suggestion that the system runs in real-time, it is used offline for scenario testing and benchmarking.
Li et al. [129]	B	Simulation-based schedule evaluation + Decision Tree Learning + Visual Analytic	No. Case studies: NET3, RW4 and Richmond Skeleton networks	DSO	The article introduces a visual analytics framework designed to support the understanding and refinement of pump scheduling strategies. It does not propose a new optimization algorithm but builds on precomputed simulation data to extract interpretable operational rules using decision trees. These are presented through an interactive visual interface (including t-SNE and Sankey diagrams), enabling users to explore and select efficient and feasible pump control policies. The system supports human-centered decision-making but does not autonomously generate or execute schedules.
Güngör-Demirci et al. [130]	B	Multi-objective optimization (energy cost, GHG emissions and water quality) + Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-II) + EPANET (simulation)	No. Case study: Net3 network	DSO	The article generates sets of Pareto-optimal solutions for different objectives (energy cost, GHG emissions and water quality), explicitly framed as alternative operational plans for decision-makers. The work provides insights into operational trade-offs (cost vs. GHG vs. water quality), enabling utilities to choose schedules based on regulatory or environmental priorities. The discussion explicitly focuses on informing decisions, not replacing them, making it an example of a decision-support optimization framework.

(continued on next page)

Table A.5: (continued)

Reference	Query	Optimization approach	Real-world applica- tion?	Classification	Explanation
Salomons and Housh [57]	B	Flow Allocation Algorithm (FAA) + Naive Demand Forecasting + MPC real-time execution	Yes. Case study: WSS in Israeli	AOC	The system automatically computes and executes pump operation decisions in real-time, using a closed-loop control cycle implemented in local programmable logic controllers. There is no human-in-the-loop for plan selection or approval as decisions are directly implemented at each time step. The approach integrates forecasting, optimization, and execution autonomously, fulfilling the definition of an automated control system rather than a decision support framework.
Moazeni and Khazaei [131]	B	MILP and MINLP with piecewise linearization (minimize total energy cost using battery, solar, wind, and diesel generator constraints)	No. Case study: Proposed WSS	OM	The paper presents a detailed co-optimization model for the operation of water and energy systems, explicitly including pump scheduling decisions. However, the formulation is used strictly as a planning tool: it generates a single optimized schedule per run, with no alternative scenarios, no interactive decision-support interface, and no automation layer for real-time execution. While the results are applicable to future smart grid applications, the system does not support user choice, does not operate in real time, and is not integrated with control logic.
Studziński, Jan and Ziółkowski, Andrzej [132]	B	Fuzzy Logic + Modified Genetic Algorithm + EPANET	Yes. Case study: Bibiela pumping station, in Katowice, Poland	AOC	The system produces and executes optimized pump operation strategies automatically using fuzzy-based genetic optimization. There is no interface for user selection or presentation of multiple alternatives. Decisions (e.g., pumps frequencies) are determined and applied based on input conditions without human intervention. Though fuzzy sets allow for decision flexibility, this is used internally by the optimizer, not exposed to human users.
Moazeni et al. [133]	B	MINLP-based optimization of pump operation and energy dispatch + OPTI toolbox (MATLAB)	No. Case study: Proposed benchmark	OM	The paper proposes a mathematical optimization model aimed at planning and operational efficiency in micro water-energy networks. While the model provides pump scheduling outputs and cost analyses, it operates entirely offline and is designed as a planning tool. There is no interface, scenario analysis, or operator involvement in the decision process during runtime. Despite some mention of SCADA integration in context, no decision support or control mechanism is implemented.
Cimorelli et al. [39]	B	Genetic Algorithm + binary formulation + EPANET (simulation)	No. Case studies: Van Zyl and Anytown Modified Networks	OM	The article presents a pump scheduling optimization model with economic evaluation. It generates a single optimal solution per case (CSP and VSP). There is no human-in-the-loop, scenario-based recommendation, or interactive layer. The focus is on demonstrating cost savings under different technological assumptions, rather than supporting dynamic decision-making.